

Vertical Innovations in Transport And Logistics over 5G experimentation facilities

D1.3 VITAL-5G system specifications and architecture including experiment-based upgrades

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Glossary of terms and abbreviations used

Table 1: Glossary

Abbreviation / Term	Description
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
5GC	5G Core
5G PPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AMC	Autonomic Management and Control
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AN	Autonomous Networks
API	Application Programming Interface
AUSF	Authentication Server Function
CACC	Cooperative Adaptive Cruise Control
CAPIF	Common API Framework
CB	Context Blueprint
CD	Continuous Deployment
CDN	Content Delivery Network
CI	Continuous Integration
CNF	Container-based virtual Functions
CTXBs	Context Blueprints
DE	Decision-making-Element
DNS	Domain Name System
E2E	End to End
EC	European Commission
ELCM	Experiment Life-Cycle Manager
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EXPBs	Experiment Blueprints
EXPDs	Experiment Descriptors

Exp_ID	Experiment ID
GANNA	Generic Autonomic Networking Architecture
gNB	gNodeB
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GSMA	Global System for Mobile Association
GST	Global Slice Template
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HA	High Availability
HCI	Hyper Converged Infrastructure
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
HW	Hardware
ID	Identification
ICT	Information and Communications Technology
IMSI	International Mobile Subscriber Identity
INT	Interoperability Testing
IoT	Internet of Things
ITU	International Telecommunications Union
IWF	Interworking Framework
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LTE	Long Term Evolution
M2M	Machine to Machine
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
mIoT	Massive IoT
ML	Machine Learning
mMTC	massive Machine Type Communications
MNOs	Mobile Network Operators
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport

NAB	Network Application Blueprint
NBI	North-Bound Interface
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NetOps	Network Operations
NF	Network Function
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NFVI	NFV Infrastructure
NFVO	NFV Orchestrator
NR	New Radio
NRF	NF Repository Function
NRS	Name Resolution Service
NS	Network Service
NSD	Network Service Descriptors
NSO	Network Services Orchestrator
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NSSI	Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
OAS	Open API Specification
OEMs	Original Equipment Manufacturers
ONAP	Open Networking Automation Platform
OSM	Open Source MANO
PPDR	Public Protection and Disaster Relief
PPP	Public Private Partnership
QoS	Quality Of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
REST	Representational State Transfer
RRM	Radio Resource Management
SA	Standalone
SB	Service Blueprint
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SBI	South-Bound Interface

SCEF	Service Capability Exposure Function
SDN	Software Defined Network
SEAL	Service Enabler Architecture Layer
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
SotA	State-of-the-Art
SST	Slice/Service Type
SW	Software
T&L	Transport and Logistics
TaaS	Testing as a Service
TCB	Test Case Blueprint
TMV WG	Test Monitoring and Validation Work Group
UC	Use Case
UE	User Equipment
UK	United Kingdom
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable Low Latency Communications
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
VA	Vertical Agnostic
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VLAN	Virtual Local Area Network
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VNFD	VNF Descriptor
VNFM	VNF Manager
VPN	Virtual Private Network
VS	Vertical Specific
VSF	Vertical Service Blueprint
VSD	Vertical Service Descriptor
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides the final specification of the VITAL-5G system and introduces the 5G experimentation services for Network Applications and vertical services in the T&L sector. The VITAL-5G platform offers such services for both internal and 3rd-party experimenters, with tools that facilitate the design, provisioning and testing of Network Applications over T&L facilities enhanced with the latest versions of 5G network technologies and computing infrastructures. The final objective is to simplify and speed up the creation and delivery of new T&L services, especially from SMEs, promoting the exchange, re-usage, extension and composition of Network Applications distributed by different vendors and software providers on the VITAL-5G catalogue. The VITAL-5G platform, through its portal, gives experimenters the opportunity to onboard new applications, combine them into end-to-end services interacting with T&L devices and launch their provisioning in virtual environments integrated with realistic 5G infrastructures. Here Network Applications can be tested in a variety of highly configurable contexts replicating different operational conditions, with 5G network slices automatically established and monitored to meet the application requirements. Verticals and experimenters can benefit from embedded monitoring and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) collection, extensive results analysis and diagnostic mechanisms, combined with procedures for testing automation, closed-loop service orchestration, and network reconfiguration.

This document constitutes an updated version of the previous D1.2 [5]. It proposes new requirements and functionalities for the VITAL-5G platform, based on the practical experience and demands of experimenters and trials' users, including a small set of 3rd-party early adopters, that have been active in WP4 using the first release of VITAL-5G system. Some initial design choices have been also updated according to the feedback received by the developers that have implemented the VITAL-5G platform and integrated the three VITAL-5G testbeds in WP2 and WP3, respectively. As consequence, while this deliverable constitutes the final outcome of WP1, it should be considered as a joint result of the various technical WPs, that have cooperated in the continuous refinement of the initial set of requirements, functional components, interfaces, and workflows described in D1.2 [5].

This deliverable follows a top-down approach and it has been structured to facilitate its usage for different categories of readers: (i) 3rd-party users and experimenters, (ii) application developers and service providers, (iii) operators, research centers and owners of T&L facilities, and (iv) technicians, system integrators, platform software developers.

In detail, **VITAL-5G services, Network Applications and 5G experimentation capabilities** are introduced at the very beginning, in **section 2**, targeting a **wide audience of potential users** and providing details on the opportunities offered by each of the three VITAL-5G testbeds (sea port in Antwerp, river port in Galati, warehouse in Athens). To clarify the mapping between global architecture and VITAL-5G testbeds, the architecture of the VITAL-5G platform is briefly introduced at this stage and further detailed in the next sections dedicated to technicians and platform developers. This section 2, instead, specifically addresses **potential 3rd parties**, to help them in the selection of the most suitable facility for their own experiments. Per-testbed sections describe examples of network applications, use cases, services or tests that can be performed in each environment, giving an insight on the available devices, how they can be accessed, the public datasets, the additional tools and Network Applications which can be re-used to build new services. Section 2 also presents the various VITAL-5G stakeholders, analyzing the three categories of users, i.e., application developers, service providers and experimenters. Starting from the expectations of the various users, the document proceeds in **section 3** with the high-level requirements of the platform in the various experimentation phases. An initial classification and analysis of their impact on the VITAL-5G platform features and design is proposed as part of the requirements' analysis.

In the following **section 4, application developers and service providers** will familiarize with the **concept of Network Applications**, their categorization, their composition in end-to-end vertical services, for T&L sector and beyond, and their requirements on the mobile network capabilities and services. Here, the packaging structure

and the information models for Network Applications, vertical services, experiments and testcases are provided as reference to build and validate new applications. Application developers can also browse the VITAL-5G catalogue and select existing applications to further extend, configure and modify them for their own purposes.

Section 5 is more oriented towards **technicians and platform developers**. In particular, **network operators, facility administrators, or research centers**, interested in replicating testing environments similar to the VITAL-5G one, will find the **global picture of the VITAL-5G system** in section 5.1 and 5.2. These sections provide the baseline information on the macro-components of the VITAL-5G system at the VITAL-5G platform and testbeds' levels. The internal structure of the VITAL-5G platform is introduced, with the VITAL-5G Catalogue to publish, search and visualize Network Applications, and the VITAL-5G Portal to launch the provisioning and testing of Network Applications and vertical services. The VITAL-5G platform offers two mechanisms to interface with the system: a web-based GUI for manual interactions and REST APIs for programmable communications with external entities, both of them properly secured with access control mechanisms based on the users' roles and groups. The interactions with the three testbeds are completely wrapped by the VITAL-5G platform itself, which offers a single access point for all the experimentation services, independently on the target testbeds where the experiments are executed. Various experimentation services can be supported for the different categories of users (application developers, service providers and experimenters), from design, to provisioning, testing and evaluation phase. Centralized and distributed deployment models are proposed for the installation of the VITAL-5G platform, to further encourage its adoption in other testbeds and facilities, even after the conclusion of the project.

Finally, the specification of the **VITAL-5G platform architecture**, its functional components, external interfaces, and workflows can be found in section 5.3, with the entire **section 6** dedicated to the new functionalities introduced in this second release of the platform. The specification presents the **architectural principles** at the basis of the design and then moves to the **functional architecture with the list of components** constituting the VITAL-5G Catalogue and VITAL-5G Portal, as well as some backend management modules. The **workflows** for the interactions among the internal components of the VITAL-5G Platform defines the abstract messages for onboarding, service provisioning and termination, experiment creation, execution, monitoring and validation, and closed-loop service management automation. Two further subsections are dedicated to the **VITAL-5G Platform external interfaces**. The northbound interface offers the experimentation services to be consumed by VITAL-5G users in the form of REST APIs. The unified southbound interface enables the communication with the underlying testbeds, mediated through specialized plugins that perform the translation towards protocols and messages originally adopted in each testbed. This part of the documentation targets mostly **software developers and system integrators**, which can be interested in adopting and extending the VITAL-5G platform for additional customizations and enhancements. Accordingly, several references link to additional software documentation or OpenAPI specifications developed in WP2 and WP3, also exploiting the public software repository of the project, where the reader can find the open-source code of the VITAL-5G platform and examples of open-source Network Applications.

1 Introduction

Transport & Logistics (T&L) services have become increasingly complex over the past years, with an enormous amount of data collected from different sources embedded in mobile-connected devices, jointly processed on edge and cloud resources with results that influence the execution of real-time tasks to be properly controlled and coordinated in very low time intervals. Cameras, sensors, and other interconnected devices have to communicate across a mobile network with a reliable connectivity and, depending on the particular type of service, exchanging large amounts of data, e.g., for high-quality video distribution, or perceiving ultra-low latencies, round-trip delays and jitters. To overcome this complex transformation, VITAL-5G will embrace 5G technology to design a set of innovative Vertical Services for the T&L sector, composed of network applications running in virtual cloud/edge environments and adopting a cloud-native model, which are interconnected to User Equipment (UE) and on-field devices via 5G networks through custom network slices able to match the service connectivity requirements.

VITAL-5G offers a set of tools and functionalities to facilitate the design, development, provisioning and experimental validation of network applications and end-to-end vertical services for the T&L sector and beyond. VITAL-5G experimentation services, made available not only for the partners of the VITAL-5G consortium, but also for 3rd parties, aim to simplify and speed up the creation and delivery of new T&L services, promoting the exchange, re-usage, extension and composition of Network Applications distributed by different vendors and software providers. In this direction, VITAL-5G proposes an open catalogue of network applications, initially filled by the consortium's member but ready to host additional applications from 3rd parties. These applications, once onboarded on the VITAL-5G platform, can be easily deployed, interconnected and automatically orchestrated over a virtual computing environment in one of the three VITAL-5G testbeds and validated over a real 5G infrastructure, in combination with network slices configured on the basis of the service requirements. In order to facilitate the evaluation and tuning of the Network Applications, the VITAL-5G experimentation facility provides embedded capabilities for network and service monitoring, result analysis, diagnostics and automated test execution. Moreover, taking into account the feedback received from the VITAL-5G platform's users, the second release of the system has been extended with additional automation capabilities to further simplify the service provisioning process and the network configuration from the perspective of verticals and experimenters.

D1.3 describes the updated specification of the VITAL-5G system, which applies some changes and introduces new features to the initial design defined in D1.2 [5], on the basis of the feedback received from the implementation and integration/testing activities performed in WP2 and WP3, respectively. Moreover, this updated version integrates some suggestions received from experimenters executing the trials in WP4, as well as 3rd party partners using the platform to deploy and test their own applications (sometimes with more challenging requirements in terms of infrastructure capabilities) or to build new services re-using the Network Applications originally available in the VITAL-5G catalogue.

The deliverable is structured as follows.

Section 2 introduces the main concepts of the VITAL-5G experimentation services, providing a common terminology for the rest of the deliverable, identifying the actors involved in VITAL-5G as providers or consumers of VITAL-5G services, and defining the various phases of an experimentation carried out over the VITAL-5G platform. A dedicated section explains how different profiles of 3rd parties can use the VITAL-5G services and the related benefits, providing a brief summary of the capabilities offered in each particular testbed.

Section 3 reports the technical requirements that have been identified to drive the design and the implementation of the VITAL-5G system as a whole, the common VITAL-5G platform and the three VITAL-5G testbeds. The requirements are specified for each of the experimentation phases and provide an initial and high-level analysis of their impact in terms of functionalities to be supported by the VITAL-5G architecture and its macro building blocks.

Section 4 introduces the concept of Network Applications, explaining how they are modelled and categorized, and how they can be composed to build end-to-end vertical services for the T&L sector. This section also presents the various information models and package formats defined in the project to build and exchange network applications, describe templates of T&L services and related experiments, and specify test cases for testing automation.

Section 5 presents the VITAL-5G architecture, explaining in section 5.1 the structuring of the VITAL-5G system in a centralized and unified VITAL-5G platform that operates over three testbeds in Athens, Antwerp and Galati, each of them integrating T&L facilities with 5G network infrastructures. The focus then moves on the VITAL-5G platform, describing the services it offers to the various actors (section 5.2) and its architectural design (section 5.3). This starts from the functional architecture (the software architecture is covered in WP2 deliverables) and the workflows for the interactions among the internal components of the VITAL-5G platform. Two further subsections are dedicated to the VITAL-5G platform external interfaces. The northbound interface offers the experimentation services to be consumed by VITAL-5G users. The unified southbound interface enables the communication with the underlying testbeds, mediated through specialized plugins that perform the translation towards protocols and messages originally adopted in each testbed.

Section 6 is dedicated to the new features introduced with the second release of the VITAL-5G platform, providing a description of functionalities and procedures supported by the current version of the VITAL-5G system that were not yet present or mature enough during the preparation of D1.2 [5].

Section 7 provides an evaluation of how the requirements have been supported in the architecture design and if/how they match the features available in the VITAL-5G system implementation from WP2 and WP3. Finally, section 8 provides the conclusions.

The annexes provide an analysis of the state of the art, some of that used as baseline for the design and implementation of the VITAL-5G platform (Annex 1 – State of the art) and the updated version of the data models used to describe network applications and services (Annex 2 – Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint data models – updated version).

1.1 Mapping VITAL-5G Outputs

Purpose of this section is to map VITAL-5G’s Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the project’s respective outputs and work performed.

Table 2: Adherence to VITAL-5G’s GA Deliverable & Tasks Descriptions.

GA Component Title	GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
TASKS			
T1.2 VITAL-5G Platform functional requirements analysis & specifications	This task is responsible for the detailed description of the characteristics that VITAL-5G platform must have, based on WP’s objectives and Use case requirements stated in T1.1	Section 3 Section 5	Section 3 provides a description of the VITAL-5G system requirements, while section 5 provides the definition of the VITAL-5G platform architecture.
	The purpose is to create an open service validation platform utilizing real-life resources and facilities to	Section 2	Section 2.3 describes VITAL-5G’s platform experimentation services and section 2.4 explains how 3 rd parties can use VITAL-5G

	validate T&L related solutions and services, offering the user a trusted and secure service execution environment under realistic conditions.		platform, tools and services, with details on a per-testbed basis.
	The platform will capture information from use cases in order to verify the functionality of the software: business rules, reporting requirements, authorization levels, external interfaces, historical data management, etc.	Section 3 Section 5 Section 7	Section 3 describes the VITAL-5G platform requirements, as derived from the use cases. Section 5 describes the architecture, including the services authorized for and offered to the different types of users (section 5.2), as well as the procedures, northbound (NBI) and southbound interfaces (SBI) (5.3). Section 7 reports how the VITAL-5G architecture and its implementation match the requirements.
	The description will include detailed specifications of the online platform and the open repository and their mechanism (VNF/Network Application creation, onboarding, deployment, management, etc.) as well as the supported interfaces, APIs and interconnections	Section 4 Section 5 Section 6	A detailed description of the Network Applications and T&L services is reported in Section 4, with modelling of Network Application packages and Network Application / Vertical services / experiment / test case blueprints, as used in the VITAL-5G catalogue. Section 5 describes the architecture of the VITAL-5G platform and its catalogue (5.3.2), with the related workflows (5.3.3) and northbound interfaces (5.3.4). Additional functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform, introduced after the first release, are documented in section 6.
T1.3 VITAL-5G platform and 5G-testbed Architecture design	This task is responsible for deriving the VITAL-5G end-to-end conceptual architecture based on the requirements and specifications established on T1.1 & T1.2, and the 5G-testbed integration approach.	Section 5 Section 7	Section 5 describes VITAL-5G architecture and the VITAL-5G Platform components. In particular, the details of the VITAL-5G platform southbound interface that enables its interaction with the VITAL-5G testbeds is detailed in 5.3.5, describing the plugin-based approach to translate between the unified interface adopted at the VITAL-5G platform level and the testbed-specific interfaces exposed by the local platforms and management/monitoring systems. Section 7 reports how the VITAL-5G architecture and its implementation match the requirements.
	[...] elaborate a fine-grained architecture description, containing the description of all the functional blocks and	Section 5 Section 6	Section 5 introduces the functional components of the architecture (5.3.2) and describes the workflows (5.3.3) for their interaction, as well as the NBI (5.3.4) and SBI

	the high-level interfaces among them.		(5.3.5) of the VITAL-5G platform. The additional functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform, introduced after the first release, are documented in section 6.
	[...] defining the architectural interfaces for: i) the Network Application and VNF Package catalogues: defining the information models, the high-level workflows and the access-based collaboration procedures	Section 4 Section 5.3.3.1 Section 5.2.1	A detailed description of the Network Applications and T&L services is reported in Section 4, with modelling of Network Application packages and Network Application / Vertical services / experiment / test case blueprints, as used in the VITAL-5G catalogue. The high-level workflow for onboarding of Network Application packages (and related VNF packages) is reported in section 5.3.3.1. The rules for the role-based access control are reported in section 5.2.1, identifying the actions permitted for the different roles defined for VITAL-5G users.
	[...] ii) the interfaces, workflows and components for AI and ML based lifecycle management	Section 6.4, 6.5, 6.7	AI/ML procedures have been introduced in the second release of the platform and they are described in section 6.4. They constitute the baseline for closed-loop reactions in T&L service lifecycle management (LCM) and diagnostics, with related workflows reported respectively in section 6.5 and section 6.7.
	[...] the definition of the mechanisms for VNF licensing and validation to be used within the project	Section 4 Section 5 Section 6	The architecture (section 5.3.2) and workflows for on-boarding and service instantiation (section 5.3.3.1 and 5.3.3.2) identifies the components and the interactions to integrate licensing control. The modelling of software licensing in Network Application packages is reported in section 4.2. The workflows for experiment validation (section 5.3.3.5) and automated results analytics and diagnostics (section 6.7, introduced in 2 nd release) provides details on the validation approach used in the VITAL-5G platform.
	From the 5G-testbed design perspective this task will develop the integration approach in terms of platform and use cases.	Section 5	The modelling of a generalized VITAL-5G testbed is reported in section 5.1.1, while the VITAL-5G platform SBI to enable the interaction between platform and testbeds (with per-testbed adaptation mechanisms) is reported in section 5.3.5.

DELIVERABLE

D1.3 VITAL-5G system specifications and architecture including experiment-based upgrades

Report on the updated (final) specifications and architecture of the end to end VITAL-5G system based on the experimenters' feedback.

1.2 Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

This deliverable is structured with a top-down approach. It starts with the presentation of the experimentation services offered by the VITAL-5G system, the introduction of the various involved stakeholders and user categories (section 2), and the analysis of the high-level requirements of the platform in the various experimentation phases (section 3). Then, it proceeds with the more technical information on the modelling of Network Applications, T&L services and experiments (section 4). Finally, it addresses the internal design of the system in the following sections. In particular section 5 is dedicated to the definition of the overall architecture of the VITAL-5G system (5.1-5.2) and the internal design of the VITAL-5G platform for its baseline functionalities (5.3). Section 6 addresses additional features that have been introduced in the 2nd release of the VITAL-5G platform, while the matching of the architecture (both in terms of design and implementation) with the requirements is addressed in section 7.

It is important to note that this deliverable follows a similar structure to D1.2 [5], since it is considered its 2nd edition, but with two important differences. The first difference is that the internal description of the VITAL-5G platform components, introduced in D1.2 [5] as initial input for WP2 implementation activities, has been now removed, instead maintaining a high-level description of their functionalities and the specification of how they interact in the overall system architecture. In particular, for each component we refer directly to WP2 deliverables (now available, with D2.3 [1] as latest specification of the VITAL-5G platform components) where they are described in details, in terms of features, specification of OpenAPIs and internal software design. This approach has been preferred to keep the document within a reasonable length, while giving the opportunity to interested readers to go into deeper and software-related details with the dedicated documents.

The second difference is that additional sections have been added to highlight explicitly the new functionalities introduced with the second release of the architecture (section 6) and to verify the compliancy with the requirements (section 7). In particular, the modifications and updates to the VITAL-5G platforms have been performed considering the feedback received from the implementation activities in WP2 and WP3 and from the internal users (mainly Network Application developers and experimenters) that have worked on the platform during the trial activities in WP4. Important suggestions on how to enhance and complement the VITAL-5G platform have been also collected from external actors, like the small early set of 3rd parties involved from the 3rd quarter of the of the project second year, the advisory board, the technical reviewers, some participants in other ICT-41 projects and the audience of webinars and public events where the VITAL-5G platform has been presented. In this sense, fundamental feedback has been received from external verticals and application developers, since they brought a quite multi-faceted perspective. For example, Network Applications, T&L Services and experiment blueprints have been refined taking into account the knowledge gaps at the basis of how verticals perceive the complexity of the network and how they would like to simplify the declaration of their connectivity and monitoring requirements. Similarly, the survey with application developers showed the increasing interest in AI/ML, but also their difficulties to find suitable testbeds and datasets to properly validate the related applications, which led us to introduce the support of GPUs in at least one of the VITAL-5G testbeds and make datasets and AI/ML baseline components available for them.

A final note of the structure of this document with regards to different readers' categories. The top-down approach has been adopted specifically so that the wider audience of **potential users interested in VITAL-5G services** can read only the first sections to get a preliminary idea of VITAL-5G offerings and then proceeds with the next chapters to get more technical details. In particular section 4 provides an insight of how to model and package Network Applications and Vertical Services to run in the VITAL-5G system and, as such, it is suitable for **application developers and service providers** interested in creating their own new applications or building new end-to-end services. Section 5.1 and 5.2 presents the overall picture of the VITAL-5G system and it is of particular

interest for actors, like **network operators or research centers**, wanting to deploy a similar infrastructure for experimental testing of 5G-enabled services or innovative network solutions. Finally, **technology solution developers or system integrators** interested in building a similar experimentation platform for 5G networks and services (or a subset of its components) can go through section 5.3 and section 6 for the insight on how the VITAL-5G platform is designed.

1.3 Mapping reviewers’ comments to sections addressing feedback

The report is re-submitted as per reviewers’ comments and the table below illustrates the specific sections where comments are addressed.

Table 3 Mapping reviewers’ comments to sections

Review Feedback	Sections Addressing the feedback
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‘..It would be good that the description of Galati and Bucharest facility followed a structure more similar to the description of the Antwerp and Athens facilities, including also the goals, operations and enablers..’ 	Section 2.4.2.2 and figure 8 aligns the discussion on the Galati and Bucharest facilities in a similar manner and content to the Antwerp and Athens facilities in a uniform way
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‘.. in the case of the Antwerp facility, it is mentioned that one Network Application will be released as open source. What about the rest? Which type of licenses are planned?’ 	Section 2.4.2.1 discusses the open-source issue across network applications depending on commercial conditions
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ‘..rest of the architecture representations, such as that in Figure 18, should be updated accordingly, including this new block..’ 	Section 5.1 updates the representations

2 VITAL-5G Experimentation Services

VITAL-5G provides a complete framework that facilitates the design, provisioning and experimental validation of 5G-enabled vertical services in realistic and highly configurable 5G testing environments. As a major target, VITAL-5G addresses vertical organizations operating in the T&L sectors, offering three testbeds with T&L facilities that cover scenarios spanning from river and sea-ports to warehouses. Each facility is extended with pre-commercial deployments of 5G networks, providing the mobile connectivity required for the T&L services and offering advanced features of network programmability, slicing and monitoring, combined with virtual computing resources to run the service applications. This approach provides the opportunity to replicate a variety of operational conditions in a controlled and flexible manner, so that the verticals can build and configure different experiments to verify the functionalities and the performance of their T&L services in dedicated and tunable 5G environments.

The experimentation services offered by VITAL-5G are designed to meet the requirements of T&L vertical industries, which have usually a limited know-how in networking and, in particular, in 5G infrastructures. For this reason, the modelling of services and experiments follows an application-oriented pattern, which hides the internal details of the 5G network configuration and focuses on the application components that build the vertical service logic and their high-level requirements in terms of mobile network connectivity. A key role in this vision is covered by the concept of Network Applications. A Network Application is a virtual application that can be deployed in a 5G infrastructure and can make use of 5G connectivity and/or 5G services (e.g., to consume network data analytics or localization information offered by the 5G Core Network) to implement its internal logic and provide its functionalities for a service consumer. The composition, instantiation and configuration of one or more Network Applications, potentially designed and delivered by different software providers, gives the possibility to build complex T&L vertical services capable to exploit 5G mobile connectivity.

The VITAL-5G framework supports the verticals in all the phases of the experimental validation of T&L vertical services, starting from their design, and going through the different steps of 5G testing environment preparation and configuration, service instantiation, test execution and service performance evaluation (see Figure 1). This support is carried out with a number of experimentation services and tools which are provided by the VITAL-5G platform. The experimentation services, presented in Section 2.3, can be accessed by VITAL-5G users depending on their particular profile (e.g., differentiated for Network Application developers, experimenters, etc.) and they are made available through a web based graphical interface or programmable APIs, supporting both manual and automated interactions.

Figure 1: Experimental Validation of Vertical Services in VITAL-5G.

Indeed, it is important to note that several actors are usually involved in the overall process, cooperating to the whole experimentation chain with different roles. For example, software developers and Network Application providers (often participating as 3rd parties) contribute to the design phase bringing the building blocks of the vertical services and identifying the functionalities to be tested and the KPIs to be monitored. VITAL-5G testbed administrators, with network operators and administrators of the T&L facilities, act as mediators for the preparation of the testing environment, e.g., supporting the installation of additional hardware or the configuration of specific network settings that may be needed for particular experiments. Experimenters coordinate the experiment execution and analyze KPIs, results and reports as input for Network Applications and service tuning and refinements. Section 2.2 provides an overview of the various actors and roles identified in VITAL-5G. The particular case of 3rd-party involvement is addressed in Section 2.4, especially relevant for external Network Application developers and/or service providers that would like to use the VITAL-5G offerings to experimentally validate their applications and/or build and test new vertical services, respectively. In this context, it is fundamental to highlight that the engagement of 3rd parties as consumers of the VITAL-5G experimentation services requires the setup of operational procedures that involves aspects like training, cooperative identification of service requirements, continuous technical support and troubleshooting, thus going well beyond the implementation and the functional deployment of the VITAL-5G platform in a public production environment. These activities are being carried out in the context of tasks T6.3 (for engagement of 3rd parties, preparation of related documentation and training activities) and T4.3 (for actual technical support, from the service/experiment design phase up to testing and validation).

2.1 VITAL-5G Architecture Terminology

This section provides a definition of some of the terms used in the rest of the document (Table 4), in order to facilitate the understanding of the VITAL-5G system, its architecture and services.

Table 4: Architecture Terminology.

Terminology	Definition
VITAL-5G Platform	This refers to the VITAL-5G Open Platform (or VITAL-5G Platform). It includes the VITAL-5G Portal, the VITAL-5G Catalogue, and the Management Backend systems. Vertical users and/or vertical applications access the VITAL-5G Platform to conduct experiments using the VITAL-5G toolset and Network Applications. The VITAL-5G Platform interfaces with the VITAL-5G testbeds in order to enable provisioning and testing of 5G-enabled services.
VITAL-5G Testbed	These encompass all the network elements and infrastructure necessary to enable 5G connectivity, integrated in the VITAL-5G T&L sites. They include the 5G access and core network elements, edge network elements and associated cloud computing infrastructure, along with the wireless and fixed access equipment. In VITAL-5G these are the three 5G infrastructure installations being utilised in the use cases in Antwerp, Galati (and Bucharest) and Athens. The VITAL-5G testbeds include all control, management and orchestration elements necessary to configure and operate the 5G infrastructure from the core to the 5G antennas.
VITAL-5G T&L Facilities	These are also referred to as the VITAL-5G T&L Trial Facilities. They are the physical sites where the use case experiments will take place and include all the necessary hardware (sensors, actuators, gateways, vessels, Automated Guided Vehicles - AGVs, etc.) required to run the use case trials. In the VITAL-5G project, they are located at the sea port in Antwerp, the Danube river port area in Galati, and the warehouse in Athens.
VITAL-5G Portal	This is a core element of the VITAL-5G Platform and is a collection of tools/functions for Network Applications and service life cycle management (LCM). The portal allows

	the onboarding, instantiation, monitoring and benchmarking of Network Applications and (T&L) vertical services. Users use the VITAL-5G Portal to run experiments via a dashboard or programmable API. The intent-based Network Application descriptions from vertical actors are automatically translated into 5G slice and Network Function Virtualization (NFV) service descriptions and lifecycle management actions. The VITAL-5G Portal contains tools for Key Performance Indicator (KPI) monitoring, analysis and diagnostic.
VITAL-5G Open Repository called VITAL-5G Catalogue	This is also called the VITAL-5G Catalogue and it is a core element of the VITAL-5G Platform that facilitates the design, onboarding, and validation of Network Applications in target environments. The VITAL-5G Catalogue is used to share and compose Network Applications for complex services and implements a Network Application and service catalogue where internal or 3 rd -party software developers can onboard their own applications.
Network Application	A Network Application is a virtual application that can be deployed in a 5G infrastructure and can make use of 5G connectivity and/or 5G services (e.g., to consume network data analytics or localization information offered by the 5G Core Network) to implement its internal logic and provide its functionalities for a service consumer.
Vertical Service	The composition, instantiation and configuration of one or more Network Applications, potentially designed and delivered by different software providers, gives the possibility to build complex vertical services capable of exploiting 5G mobile connectivity.

2.2 Actors & Roles

Table 5 identifies the various actors/roles involved in the overall experimentation process and covers actors “internal” to the operation of the VITAL-5G platform, in addition to “external” actors/roles contributing with new Network Applications and experimenting with the platform. To aid understanding, each actor/role is followed by a description and an overview of their expertise.

Table 5: Actors/Roles identified as being key contributors to the VITAL-5G experimentation process.

Actor / Role	Description	Expertise
Actors contributing to provide VITAL-5G experimentation services		
Testbed Administrator /Technician	Administrators of one of the VITAL-5G testbeds, responsible for the overall testbed design, deployment and maintenance. They coordinate the scheduling of the experiments in the testbed and applies any custom configuration or installation that requires a manual intervention. Any service specific requirement with impact on the testbed functionalities should be discussed and agreed with the testbed administrators.	System integration, 5G network infrastructures and operations, cloud/edge computing, T&L infrastructures
T&L Site Infrastructure Manager	On-site at the T&L facility, responsible for the infrastructure and equipment (sensors, camera, actuators, AGVs, etc.) to be used in the experiment.	Equipment for T&L facilities, including IoT sensors, actuators, other IoT devices.

VITAL-5G Open Platform Administrator	Administrator of the VITAL-5G Open Platform (i.e., VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue), responsible for its deployment, operation and maintenance, as well as its secure interconnectivity to the VITAL-5G testbed and with the VITAL-5G Platform users (both internal and 3 rd -party users).	Cloud and service platforms and system integration
VITAL-5G Open Platform Technician	Interfaces between the Network Applications developers, service providers and experimenters using VITAL-5G services and the testbed technicians, to support in the design and execution of experiments and KPIs analysis.	Service platforms and system integration, some networking expertise.
Users of VITAL-5G services		
Network Application Developer (Internal or 3 rd party)	<p>Developers of vertical-specific or vertical-agnostic Network Applications. They use the VITAL-5G platform to onboard their own Network Applications in the catalogue.</p> <p>Once available on the VITAL-5G catalogue, Network Applications can be used by <i>Vertical Service Providers</i> to build new (T&L) vertical services and by <i>Experimenters</i> to perform testing and validation experiments.</p> <p>Network Application developers may also focus specifically on Virtual Network Functions (VNFs), related to networking functions only (e.g., virtual firewall, virtual IDS, etc.). In this case they are called <i>VNF Developers</i>.</p>	<p>(T&L) service applications</p> <p>Networking functions in case of VNF developers.</p>
Vertical Service Provider (Internal or 3 rd party)	<p>Developers of vertical-specific services, which can be built composing Network Applications and VNFs available in the VITAL-5G catalogue. Even if VITAL-5G addresses specifically the T&L sector, the platform services can be used by providers of 5G-enabled vertical services in any market sector.</p> <p>Vertical Service Providers can use the VITAL-5G platform to create and onboard new vertical services and deploy them in the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p> <p>Vertical Service Providers includes the particular roles of <i>Service Developers</i>, active also in the implementation and creation of their own services, and <i>System Integrators</i>, specialized in the delivery of vertical services composed by Network Applications provided by other entities.</p>	Vertical service design and implementation, service delivery and operation, system integration
Experimenter (Internal or 3 rd party)	<p>The VITAL-5G users interested in the experimental evaluation of Network Applications or vertical services in a 5G environment. Experimenters can bring their own Network Applications or re-use existing ones to build the services to be validated.</p> <p>Using the VITAL-5G platform, they can design their own experiments, identifying the KPIs to be monitored, the reports to be collected and the procedures for (automated) testing. They are also responsible for the management of their experiments, configuring and launching their executions, monitoring the results and analysing the produced reports.</p>	Service provisioning, tuning and testing, experimental validation and results analysis.

The three categories of VITAL-5G users defined in Table 5 (i.e., Network Application developers, Service providers and Experimenters) identify three different user profiles. Each of them can access a subset of VITAL-5G platform services, designed taking into account the interest and expertise of the various users, as described in the following:

- **Network Application developers**, in charge of Network Applications' design and implementation. The VITAL-5G platform offers the possibility to navigate the catalogue of existing Network Applications, which can be used as baseline to develop new ones, to onboard their Network Applications in the VITAL-5G system for testing and validation, and to make them available for other users for building new T&L services. It should be noted that Network Applications' developers may be not specifically focused in the direct experimental testing of their applications, but just interested in sharing them on the VITAL-5G catalogue to promote their adoption and assessment in a wide community.
- **Service providers**, in charge of building vertical services through the composition of one or more Network Applications and, optionally, network functions. Service providers can visualize and reuse public Network Applications, define and onboard new vertical services, as well as request their instantiation, operation, and monitoring in one of the VITAL-5G testbed. The category of service providers includes also roles like vertical service developers and system integrators. Service providers may be not specifically focused on the direct experimental testing of their vertical services, but just interested to orchestrate their deployment and execution for a successful and efficient delivery in the production environment of a VITAL-5G testbed. This may be the case of a post-testing phase, where the service is actually delivered and operated in its target environment.
- **Experimenters**, the broader category of users of the VITAL-5G platform. Experimenters are interested in validating new Network Applications or services that can be provided entirely by themselves, built using 3rd party Network Applications or simply available in the VITAL-5G catalogue. Consequently, experimenters have the access to all the VITAL-5G platform services: they can onboard new Network Applications or vertical services; visualize and download the already existing ones; instantiate, monitor, and manage new services; design, onboard and launch new experiments and visualize the related monitoring data, reports and diagnostic results. Experimenters are thus focused on the testing of Network Applications and services, usually performed before their final launch on the "public" catalogue for massive adoption from external users and their operational delivery in the target environment.

2.3 Experimentation Services in VITAL-5G Platform

The VITAL-5G platform provides a centralized access point for all the Network Applications' and T&L services' experimentation functionalities offered to the various actors that make use of VITAL-5G services on top of any of the three VITAL-5G testbeds.

The overall VITAL-5G functional architecture is shown in Figure 2. This helps to briefly introduce the interactions of the users with the VITAL-5G platform, the macro-functionalities of the platform in support the experiments and trials, as well as the interaction of the common platform with the VITAL-5G testbeds, mediated through per-testbed drivers. Further details on VITAL-5G architecture and the internal components of the VITAL-5G platform are provided in section 5.

VITAL-5G experimenters use the web-based interface offered by the VITAL-5G platform to access all the experimentation services, with the possibility to onboard, deploy and test services and Network Applications selecting the VITAL-5G testbed of interest. All VITAL-5G testbeds provides a common set of functionalities for management and monitoring of 5G networks, edge/cloud platforms for vertical applications, NFV orchestrator and catalogues to build and provision new services for extensive testing in realistic 5G environments. Even if based on solutions from different vendors and deployed with custom configurations, all the testbeds follow the same high-level design pattern. The communication between the VITAL-5G platform and the internal solutions of the testbeds, where needed, is handled with testbed-specific drivers that provide the adaptation to proprietary interfaces, information models and procedures. This approach allows VITAL-5G experimenters to use

the same procedures over the common VITAL-5G platform, independently on the testbed where they want to execute their experiment. Beyond the common functionalities for management of 5G, edge/cloud and NFV infrastructures, each testbed is specialized with additional devices, IoT platforms or applications that make them particularly suitable for experiments in given vertical sectors. For example, the Athens testbeds provides an indoor 5G network as well as AGVs and datasets for emulated warehouse scenarios that make it particularly suitable for experiments in the logistic area. The onboard sensors and cameras available in the Antwerp testbed simplify the execution of tests on applications for monitoring and assisted navigation in river or sea port environments. The reader can refer to section 2.4.2 for details on the specialized offerings of each VITAL-5G testbeds, in order to select the most suitable for his/her own experimentation purposes.

Figure 2: VITAL-5G Functional Architecture.

The VITAL-5G experimentation services allow the design, provision, monitoring, manual and automated lifecycle management, test and validation of vertical services, which can be composed of one or multiple Network Applications and make use of 5G network connectivity, network functions and services. This concept is valid for all the testbeds and the experimentation procedure follows a common workflow where all the various steps can be executed by the users through the VITAL-5G platform.

Figure 3: Phases of VITAL-5G experimentation process.

The different phases of a VITAL-5G experimentation process are represented in Figure 3. They are described below:

(T&L) Vertical Service Design. This phase has the objective of designing and implementing a vertical service to be experimentally validated in one of the VITAL-5G testbeds. It should be noted that, while VITAL-5G testbeds offers facilities and devices targeting the T&L sector, also more generalized vertical services composed of virtual applications making use of 5G connectivity can be successfully validated in VITAL-5G, independently on their market sector.

The Service Design phase involves an initial step for the analysis of the capabilities offered by the various VITAL-5G testbeds, to select the one more suitable for the target service. These capabilities include the following:

- Characteristic of 5G connectivity, e.g., coverage area, type of network slices supported, etc.
- Computing resources for execution of Network Applications, e.g., availability of VM-based or container-based virtualization infrastructure, dimension of resources that can be made available for a given experiment at edge and cloud nodes, added-value features like hardware acceleration or GPUs.

- Devices available in the T&L facility, e.g., IoT sensors and actuators, video cameras, AGVs, etc., and their access permissions. For example, actuators may have private access, video cameras may have restricted access, AGV may have private access but related simulators may be publicly available, etc. In some cases, specific agreements with the T&L Site Infrastructure Manager need to be put in place to obtain a controlled access to particular functionalities (in some cases under the supervision of the site personnel), especially for 3rd parties.
- Availability of public datasets, software drivers or Network Applications that can be used as baseline to develop new applications customized to operate on the given testbed.
- Opportunities for further extensions, e.g., the possibility to install new hardware, to extend the 5G radio coverage or create additional network slices.

It should be noted that the service design phase may require direct interactions between service and/or Network Applications' developers and VITAL-5G technicians, to jointly discuss service requirements and reach an agreement on potential site enhancements or custom configurations that may be needed for the particular service.

A typical vertical service in VITAL-5G is composed of one or more Network Applications, which can be selected from the public ones available in the VITAL-5G catalogue or developed as new Network Applications to be onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform. The formal definition of a vertical service is specified through a Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB), which describes the composition and interconnectivity of the various Network Applications, the configurable service parameters, the monitoring parameters and the high-level requirements in terms of mobile connectivity. Similarly, Network Applications are defined through a Network Application Blueprint (NAB) that describes Network Applications metadata like mobile connectivity requirements, software licenses, hardware dependencies, external interfaces and related protocols, usage of 5G network services, etc. (see section 4 for further information). Blueprints of pre-loaded Network Applications and Vertical Services can be downloaded from the VITAL-5G catalogue and used as example for the creation of new ones. The details of Network Applications and vertical services' deployment in a virtual infrastructure are modelled through Virtual Network Function (VNF) packages and Network Service Descriptors (NSD) following the ETSI NFV standards. This approach guarantees the compatibility with the NFV orchestrators available in the three VITAL-5G testbeds, which are responsible for the instantiation of Network Applications and vertical services in the target testing environments. Both VM-based and container-based Network Applications are supported in all VITAL-5G testbeds, with the related software images that can be onboarded in the public registries and repositories of each testbed.

Once a Vertical Service and related Network Applications have been designed, implemented, packed and modelled according to the VITAL-5G blueprints format, the related packages and blueprints can be onboarded in the VITAL-5G catalogue and they become available in the VITAL-5G catalogue for the experiments or for further usage in the composition of other services. During the onboarding procedure, NSDs and VNF packages are automatically uploaded in the target testbed and they become ready for deployment.

Experiment Design. This phase has the objective of defining an experiment for the validation of Network Applications or Vertical Services in a VITAL-5G testbed. The experiment is defined through an Experiment Blueprint (ExpB), which follows the format of 5G EVE experiment blueprints [2]. The experiment blueprint identifies the related Vertical Service or Network Applications, the characteristics of the testing environment (e.g., network slice parameters, background traffic, etc.), the service, infrastructure and network KPIs to be monitored, their evaluation criteria (e.g., in terms of max/min thresholds), as option some test scripts for testing automation, variable and configurable parameters, etc. At the end of the Experiment Design phase, the ExpB and the related test case blueprint are onboarded in the VITAL-5G catalogue, and they become available to execute the experiments or as reference for the definition of new experiments.

Preparation of 5G testing environment. This phase has the objective of preparing the testing environment for the execution of an experimentation campaign and, depending on the complexity of the scenario, it may require the manual intervention of the testbed administrators, in terms of 5G network settings or T&L facility

configuration. The initial step of this phase involves the customization and configuration of the experiment and its associated Network Applications and vertical service, as well as the scheduling of the experiment execution in the target testbed. The experiment customization is defined through an Experiment Descriptor (ExpD), again following the information model of 5G EVE ExpD [2], which is onboarded in the VITAL-5G platform. The scheduling of the experiments in dedicated time slots allows reservation of the required resources and guarantees the desired operational conditions, without unexpected interferences with the day-by-day activities in the testbeds' environments that may impact the experiment outcomes and limit the reproducibility of the results. Through the basic experiment configuration, the devices in the T&L facility and the network settings are properly configured, making the testbed ready for service provisioning and experiment execution. It should be noted that if the manual configuration of the testing environment is not required, the experimenter can immediately proceed with the following phases after the ExpD onboarding. Otherwise, an explicit notification from the testbed administrator is required to proceed.

Vertical Service Instantiation. This phase has the objective of provisioning the vertical service in the target testbed, triggering the instantiation of its Network Applications in the virtual infrastructure, their activation and configuration. If the Network Applications composing the vertical service are associated to restrictive software licenses (e.g., related to the number of instances that can be executed concurrently), these licenses are properly verified and validated. Depending on the dynamicity supported in the 5G testbed, the network slices dedicated to the vertical service may be instantiated on-demand during this phase, following the specification of the mobile connectivity requirements defined in the VSB. Finally, the collection of the monitoring data is properly activated and configured, according to the network, infrastructure and service KPI specified for Network Applications and vertical service. At the end of this phase, the vertical service instance is up and running in a dedicated virtual environment, with the Network Applications activated, properly configured, interconnected to the 5G network through the proper network slice and able to interact with the devices in the T&L facilities. The second release of the architecture introduces data-driven and closed loop mechanisms for automated lifecycle management actions, modelled through rules encoded in the vertical service blueprint.

Experiment Execution. This phase has the objective of executing the experiment and collecting the monitoring data required to evaluate the performance of the service. During the experiment execution, some test scripts can be automatically configured and executed by the platform. Moreover, the user will have secure access to the various Network Application components (via Virtual Private Network – VPN), with the possibility to operate directly on their internal processes. In parallel, the mechanisms offered by the orchestrators in VITAL-5G testbeds, exposed through suitable APIs, will give the possibility to operate on the lifecycle of the vertical service, e.g., to trigger re-configuration or scaling actions even from external orchestration entities. These options are useful to evaluate how service and network KPIs vary with different deployments, configurations and dimensioning of the overall vertical services or single Network Applications. The collected monitoring data can be visualized in real-time through graphs in the web based graphical interface or consumed by external entities via APIs. The combination of APIs for monitoring and service lifecycle management gives the possibility to implement external closed-loop strategies (independently on the ones already embedded in VITAL-5G platform), directly within the Network Applications or in dedicated service orchestration logic which can be developed in 3rd party systems.

In VITAL-5G the experiment execution and the vertical service lifecycle management will be two parallel and nearly independent procedures, i.e., an experiment can be executed over a vertical service whenever the service is in instantiated mode, but the lifecycle of the service can be managed independently without any particular relationship to the status of a particular experiment. This approach enables a higher level of flexibility in the dynamic lifecycle management of the service without the boundaries imposed by experiment executions.

Vertical Service Evaluation. This last phase has the objective of helping the experimenters in the evaluation and assessment of the vertical service performance in the 5G network. Elaborating the monitoring data and the network and service KPIs collected during the experiment execution phase, the platform analyses the results and generates experiment reports. Moreover, it performs some diagnostics evaluation (also supported by AI

techniques – see also section 6.7) to identify the potential causes of performance degradation or bottlenecks in the vertical service that may derive from networking issues at the various segments of the 5G infrastructure, poor performance of specific Network Application components or insufficient virtual resources in the computing infrastructure at the edge or core of the network.

2.4 Involvement of 3rd parties

The involvement of 3rd party experimenters that are not members of the VITAL-5G consortium (e.g., researchers, startups and companies) in the experimentation process and in the Network Application development and testing process, is a key aspect of the H2020 ICT-41 call and hence of the VITAL-5G project. VITAL-5G has the objective of engaging different kinds of stakeholders, mostly SMEs, but also research centers and industries, acting as experimenters of vertical services and developers of Network Applications. The 3rd party target profiles are described in section 2.4.1, analyzing the benefits for each category.

All 3rd party experimenters will have a secure access to the VITAL-5G platform and its entire set of experimentation tools and functionalities, e.g., VITAL-5G catalogue of public Network Applications, features for onboarding and validation of new Network Applications, automated service provisioning, management and monitoring, test execution, results analysis and diagnostics, as presented in this deliverable. All these features have been designed to facilitate the experimentation activities for both internal and 3rd party users, without requiring a deep knowledge of 5G technologies. This is expected to promote awareness of 5G capabilities for application developers and service providers, providing simplified mechanisms for results analysis and the drawing of useful conclusions regarding their service and/or Network Applications when deployed in operational 5G environments. Moreover, 3rd parties will have a secure access to the environment of the VITAL-5G testbed selected for their own experiment. They will be able to interact with and monitoring their Network Applications running in the computing infrastructure, communicate with equipment and devices in the T&L facility, possibly reusing software drivers or public Network Applications for programmable configuration or real-time data collection, access historical datasets for ML training, or make use of device simulators for more scalable testing. The assets made available for each testbed are described in section 2.4.2. It has to be noted that, as some of the Network Applications and equipment (e.g., vessels, sensors, etc.) provided by VITAL-5G partners can be commercially sensitive and/or require special permissions for usage, not all of the components of the trial sites will be fully available for the 3rd party experimenters, meaning that access will be restricted to a subset of hardware and software components or may require dedicated negotiations and collaboration agreements.

2.4.1 Target profiles of VITAL-5G 3rd parties

VITAL-5G addresses two main profiles of 3rd parties, as follows:

1. Vertical experimenters:

- a. Target audience: Vertical stakeholders, mostly stemming from the T&L ecosystem, that will be invited to observe, use, extend, and/or experiment over the VITAL-5G platform, using the Network Applications, services and equipment developed and deployed by the VITAL-5G partners.
- b. Goal: 1) To disseminate the project results and create impact in the community about the innovative solutions. 2) To offer the opportunity to experimenters to witness first-hand the benefits that 5G can bring to the T&L vertical sector. 3) To draw feedback from the T&L community as to how to further improve the solutions offered by VITAL-5G.

2. Network Application developers:

- a. Target audience: SMEs and technology development companies from the T&L and affiliated sectors (providers, consultants, IT experts), with in-house SW development capabilities, as well as research centers and universities, or research projects. Experience in platform/service deployments and experimentation with cutting-edge technologies (5G, IoT, AI/ML) will be of added value.

- b. **Goal:** 1) To enable the developments, onboarding, deployment and validation of Network Applications besides the ones deployed by the consortium partners, in order to assess the VITAL-5G platform’s openness, flexibility and usability. 2) To expand the offered services on the VITAL-5G platform. 3) To offer the means (5G testbed, end-equipment, etc.) and tools (blueprints, descriptors, results analysis and diagnosis) to external parties to perform pre-commercial evaluation of their envisioned products based on Network Applications.

It should be noted that while **SMEs** are the natural beneficiaries of VITAL-5G services, and more in general of all the initiatives that build open facilities for testing and experimentation of 5G-enabled services, the collaboration with external users provides fundamental benefits also when involving additional categories of 3rd parties. Examples are **big industries of vertical sectors, research centers and universities, and even research projects not only within 5G PPP and 6G IA initiatives, but also external ones**, e.g., at the national/regional level or within different research programs that are investigating the interaction and integration of different technologies with 5G networks. In this sense, the continuous cooperation, sharing and evolution of 5G/6G testing infrastructures among research initiatives is key to create synergies that:

- Help to advance in the research, making it more sustainable in the long term, facilitating the efficient replication of similar initiatives in geographically distributed environments and enabling more scalable testing infrastructures, through the creation of compatible sites with unified interfaces and common experimentation methodologies that facilitate multi-site federation.
- Facilitate the capillary availability of 5G experimental infrastructures across Europe, promoting not only their concept, but also the business offerings of 5G Testing-as-a-Service. On one hand, this would lower the barriers to introduce new services and new technologies, making it more affordable for SMEs that have difficulties to build their own 5G testing infrastructure. On the other hand, it would offer new revenue models and collaboration opportunities for the providers of such infrastructures – not only network operators, but also universities and research centres – that would see economic incentives for new investments in this area. This would clearly have a beneficial impact also in terms of education, with students and researchers accessing labs with the latest mobile network technologies and realistic deployments of operational 5G networks.

2.4.2 VITAL-5G testbeds offering to 3rd parties

This section provides information on the testbed-specific capabilities and assets offered to 3rd parties in each of the three VITAL-5G sites, as summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Assets and capabilities of VITAL-5G testbeds for 3rd parties.

VITAL-5G Testbed	Target VITAL-5G Use Case	5G Network	Computing Infrastructure	T&L Devices	Re-usable Network Applications	Additional Assets
Sea Port of Antwerp (BE)	Assisted Vessel Transport	5G SA Rel.16 with 3 gNBs in a selected area in the Port of Antwerp Network Slicing (eMBB and URLLC)	Edge infrastructure with ETSI OSM ¹ operating over Openstack ² and	High-bandwidth cameras and sensors on the vessels	Real-Time Digital Twin (VA5) Remote Vessel Monitoring (VS5) Assisted Vessel	Datasets on: Vessel position (longitude, latitude), speed and heading Data from on-board sensors

¹ <https://osm.etsi.org/>

² <https://www.openstack.org/>

		5G modem on the vessel	Kubernetes ³ platforms.		Navigation (VS6) On-Board Data Collection & Interfacing for Vessel Tercofin II (VS8) Navigation Speed Optimizer (VS7 – open source)	(radar, LiDAR, camera) Network data collected from radio and core functions, including network performance data
River Port of Galati and Bucharest (RO)	Assisted navigation Accurate navigation maps Predictive maintenance for ship safety	5G SA Rel.16 network with coverage in Galati port (Navrom ships and a limited area in the surrounding) and Orange 5G Lab in Bucharest. Network Slicing (eMBB and URLLC). Support of multi-slice connectivity for a single subscriber, by using an advanced 5G SA Nokia CPE. Transport network with HA features.	Edge infrastructure with ETSI OSM operating over Openstack and Kubernetes platforms. Openstack deployed in HA mode. Availability of GPUs.	High-bandwidth cameras on NAVROM vessels and Galati ports. Sensors on the NAVROM vessels (incl. engines data).	On board data collection & interfacing for NAVROM vessel (VS8) Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion & post processing (VA2) Remote inspection & risk assessment (VA3) Data stream organization (VA6)	Datasets on: Ships position and obstacles Weather and air quality sensors' data
Warehouse in Athens (GR)	Autonomous pallet transport within the warehouse Follow-me function for	5G SA Rel.16 with a gNB with two cells in a selected area of the warehouse (DIAKINISIS premises)	Edge infrastructure with ETSI OSM operating over Openstack and Kubernetes platforms.	Dedicated sensor Gateway with attached environmental sensors and video camera and an AGV.	Distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion and automation (VA1) Indoor robot navigation & coordination	Data from mounted sensors in the warehouse Non-sensitive historical data from warehouse

³ <https://kubernetes.io/>

	human-robot collaboration Remote monitoring and control of AGVs	Network Slicing (eMBB and URLLC) 5G modem in the warehouse			with task planning (VS1) Human-robot collaboration (VS2)	and AGV operations A Digital Twin & simulated warehouse environment which includes virtual Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs)
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2.4.2.1 Antwerp facility (BE)

In the Port of Antwerp trial site, we deploy and demonstrate **Assisted Vessel Transport** use case, which leverages **5G Standalone (SA) connectivity** and **network slicing** principles to assist vessels in the challenging environment of a port area, i.e., addressing: lack of safety in the port, too large waiting times and excessive gas consumption. To tackle these challenges, we enable **remote vessel monitoring** in a busy port area, increasing **situational awareness** in real time, and **optimizing assisted vessel navigation** through defining optimal routes and speed (see Figure 4).

In particular, a real-time **digital twin** is developed around the vessel to support the assisted vessel operation. In parallel, **real-time navigation speed optimization**, along with automated path planning and remote vessel monitoring, allow to reduce dwell times and improve operational planning of the vessel, thereby leveraging on AI/ML methodologies. The concept of **Network Applications** defined in the scope of VITAL-5G project has been used **to design and develop** these **vertical services** that support the use case. The high-bandwidth camera feeds and sensor data are sent in real-time from the vessels to the Network Applications running at the 5G edge platform, while assistance to the vessel captain is provided in real-time by sharing the navigable waypoints for an optimal route including the optimal speed. The same trial site can be leveraged by the external experimenters, i.e., the 3rd-party experimenters, which can be either involved in the use case Assisted Vessel Transport to enhance it and experiment with the existing vertical services, or create their own use cases by reusing the network infrastructure (radio, edge, and core), Network Applications, and other tools such as local monitoring platform and slice plugins.

Figure 4: Mapping the goals of the Assisted Vessel Transport use case to supported operations that can be exploited and further built upon by the 3rd-party experimenters.

In this Section, we provide further details on the 5G system components within the Antwerp trial site, as well as the Network Applications that can be reused by the 3rd party experimenters.

Concerning the Antwerp 5G-Testbed, as a core of the Antwerp trial site, it spans the usual 5G SA ecosystem components (as shown in Figure 5):

- User Equipment, i.e., a commercial vessel equipped with 5G modem, sensors, and cameras
- Radio Access Network (RAN) with three gNodeBs installed in the selected area of the Port of Antwerp
- Transport and Core network
- 5G Edge network that hosts the Network Application platform, designed and deployed to provide Network Function Virtualization (NFVI) resources for hosting and orchestrating Network Applications tailored to Assisted Vessel Transport use case, by using Open-Source MANO (OSM)-based orchestrator and Openstack/Kubernetes.

Figure 5: High-level overview of the Antwerp trial site.

As already mentioned in this section, the overall use case is developed via creating vertical services, which are further composed by Network Applications as building blocks. Thus, here we provide a brief overview of the Network Applications that are public and, as such, can be used as building blocks for new vertical services:

- Real-Time Digital Twin (VA5)
- Remote Vessel Monitoring (VS5)
- Assisted Vessel Navigation (VS6)
- On-Board Data Collection & Interfacing for Vessel Tercofin II (VS8)

The Network Applications developed by 3rd parties can reuse those public Network Applications by interfacing with them (mainly via REST-based interfaces or pub/sub mechanisms deployed via ZeroMQ⁴ technology), and thus, using them to build new vertical services, i.e., chains of Network Applications. In addition, we make one of the Network Applications fully available to the 3rd-party experimenters as open-source application whose codebase can be reused and extended to build new Network Applications:

- Navigation Speed Optimizer (VS7)

All the other Network Applications mentioned above have a closed software license (the software code is not open source) to facilitate further commercial exploitation. The particular license option to be adopted after the closure of the project will be considered and defined on a case-by-case basis, depending on potential customers, type of service bundle and commercial offer.

In case 3rd-party experimenters are not aiming to build new vertical services and Network Applications, but to rather leverage on VITAL-5G trial sites to collect realistic data for validating their theoretical or simulation-based models, we offer several data types, which can be further extended depending on the needs and requirements from the 3rd-party experimenters. At the moment, the data types available publicly through access to some of the public Network Applications are:

- Vessel position (longitude, latitude)
- Vessel speed
- Vessel heading
- Data from on-board sensors (radar and/or LiDAR and/or camera)
- Network data collected from radio and core functions, including the network performance

The role of the 3rd party experimenters in the Antwerp trial site depends on the background knowledge and expertise of the onboarded parties. Thus, we adjust the role based on that, and tune the support depending on whether the 3rd party belongs to T&L industry (SMEs and start-ups), or research and academia domains (research institutes, universities).

In the case of T&L industry, if 3rd party's business concerns safety and optimization of sailing operations, the following can be obtained:

- Tackling safety in sailing operations: the Network Applications for remote vessel monitoring (**VS8** and **VS5**) can be reused to remotely monitor the vessels in a busy port environment, or the digital twin one for improving the situational awareness.
- Decreasing large waiting times in sailing operations: the Network Applications for increased situational awareness (**VA5**), assisted path planning (**VS6**), and speed optimization (**VS7**), can be tested to experience and visualize how we address this issue.
- Reducing fuel consumption in port environment: the Network Applications for vessel speed optimization (**VS7**) and assisted path planning (**VS6**) can be leveraged to see how we address this issue.

On the other hand, if the 3rd party experimenter is involved in the research and development activities, or are interested in a telco-business-oriented perspective, the following activities can be performed:

- Testing the impact of 5G network on T&L or other vertical use cases: The Network Applications for assisted vessel navigation can be used on the Antwerp Network Application edge platform, and their performance over 5G SA can be tested in real-time (both real-time and historical data to be collected). Also, the datasets with 5G slicing performance measurements are available for further analysis, or for training ML models. The 5G testbed can be exploited to create and run 3rd party applications (not necessarily T&L, but from other vertical industries) in a vertical-tailored 5G environment.

⁴ <https://zeromq.org/>

- Designing 5G-enhanced applications for other types of verticals: The 3rd party experimenters can use the design principles of applications for assisted vessel navigation as a baseline, or customize the publicly available Network Applications to create their own solution.
- Testing AI/ML solution in a real-life environment: We offer datasets collected from the vessel sensors, lidar/radar, and 5G network, to train 3rd party ML algorithms, including the opportunities to test the performance of those algorithms in a real-life environment of Port of Antwerp.

Partners from the Antwerp trial site are focused on the engagement activities with the 3rd party experimenters by being active in all dissemination activities organized in the WP6 (T6.3). In particular, IMEC is heavily involved in engagement activities such as presenting the VITAL-5G project and the 3rd-party experimentation strategy in various conferences such as PortComms 2022⁵ and IEEE CCNC 2023⁶, where we successfully managed to gain interest from several 3rd-party experimenters. We will mention one example in this deliverable, whereas the detailed report on the 3rd-party experimenters in the Antwerp trial site will be provided in WP4 and WP6 deliverables. Currently, IMEC and TEL are closely working together with a company called Zinkworks⁷.

In particular, Zinkworks is interested in exploiting the network-related data collected from the Antwerp 5G testbed to train and validate their ML models for network traffic prediction, and UE mobility prediction. Both models are currently being designed as Network Applications, and as such, they will be deployed on the Network Application platform and further exploited in Use Case 1 and Antwerp trial site to improve network operation via e.g., dynamic slice configuration mechanisms. IMEC and TEL are providing daily support to the aforementioned 3rd party experimenters, with weekly calls organized for follow-up discussions on the progress.

2.4.2.2 Galati and Bucharest facility (RO)

The Romanian VITAL-5G testbed is built on an end-to-end (E2E) 5G SA network, 3GPP Release 16 compliant, which provides 5G coverage in Galati with a bi-sector gNodeB that covers Navrom ships located in the port and an additional limited area near the port, on the Danube River. This facility is used to demonstrate the “**5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras**” use case. Moreover, the testbed also includes the Orange 5G Lab in Bucharest, providing 3rd parties with the opportunity to perform tests and experiments in both a T&L operational facility and an indoor/outdoor lab environment.

As extensively reported in D3.2 [3], the 5G SA network in the Romanian testbed efficiently supports both eMBB and URLLC slices. The network KPIs measured on field are in the order of 600 Mbps for downlink (DL) throughput and 100 Mbps for uplink (UL) throughput for the eMBB slice and < 3.5 ms one way delay for the latency in the URLLC slice, using a subscriber connected to one of the slices. Moreover, as also mentioned in D3.2 [3], ORO has implemented, as a novel and key VITAL-5G output in industry, the 5G SA multi-slice implementation for a single subscriber, by using an advanced 5G SA Nokia CPE. A specific E2E network slice has been defined in the Galati environment and a subscriber has been attached, through the Slice Management Interface, in the multi-slice context, with PDPs contexts active at the same time for eMBB and URLLC, as shown in Figure 6.

```
oro-5g-upf01# show mobile-gateway pdn bearer-context supi 226107900000077 detail |
Gi Network Inst : orangeurllc
N3 DL packets   : 912839           N3 DL bytes      : 1212749520
SGI UL packets  : 143092           SGI UL bytes     : 6308403
Gi Network Inst : orange5glab
N3 DL packets   : 1556773           N3 DL bytes      : 2105226110
SGI UL packets  : 1499362           SGI UL bytes     : 565748002
```

⁵ <http://www.wireless-networks-in-ports.com/>

⁶ <https://ccnc2023.ieee-ccnc.org/>

⁷ Zinkworks: <https://zinkworks.com/>.

Figure 6: PDPs contexts active at the same time for eMBB and URLLC.

All the Romanian 5G testbed's components are fully deployed and integrated covering the needs to support the main capabilities and network features keys to respond to the 5G Network Applications deployment, starting with 5G RAN, Core, Transport, Virtualization and Orchestration and extending the infrastructure to support also VITAL-5G Platform. The Romanian testbed orchestrator, based on OSMv12, is integrated with the testbed VIMs, by using an Openstack platform deployed in High-Availability (HA) mode and a Kubernetes cluster. Taking into account requirements expressed by 3rd parties, the computing infrastructure has been extended with servers featuring GPUs.

The Romanian VITAL-5G testbed components are represented in Figure 7, which also highlights the high availability deployment of transport network and virtual computing infrastructure, which guarantees seamless resiliency and application migration. The high availability and reliability tests conducted by ORO registered no 5G SA network issues for several months (more than 5 months, with at least one user permanently connected to the 5G SA network and generating traffic).

Figure 7: Romanian testbed 5G SA components and HA transport network configuration.

Available T&L Services and Network Applications in RO testbed

The design and implementation of new services from 3rd parties can be accelerated and facilitated by the use of Network Applications designed for UC2, which can be reused and combined across numerous vertical services and even across Use Cases. With the aid of **assisted operations and navigation** that utilise the IoT detection system and video cameras installed in Galati port and also on ships and cargoes, the vertical services that are

used in UC2 as well as the corresponding Network Applications are used to ensure a safer operation in the port and to bring **more security to the navigation of ships in the port of Galati**.

Figure 8: Mapping the goals of the 5G connectivity and data-enabled assisted navigation using IoT sensing and video cameras use case to supported operations that can be exploited and further built upon by the 3rd-party experimenters.

The 5G network will encompass all this infrastructure to ensure quick transfer of data from the devices. Below a brief description of three types of vertical services that already use Network Applications developed in UC2, which can be used as examples for new 3rd party applications.

Service 1: Data-enabled assisted navigation

The service makes use of the Internet of Things sensing technology and NAVROM vessel's and Galati port's video cameras. For a specific data collection from the NAVROM vessel, **VS9** is used. **VA6** is used to classify the data stream, assign the appropriate slice (URLLC or mMTC) in accordance with the data supplied from the vessel, and provide interfaces for sending warnings and classifying events. Each incident can be quickly, clearly, and precisely categorized as either dangerous or non-threatening, as well as according to the type of dangerous occurrence. Instantaneous warnings are given to improve the vessel crew's response time.

Service 2: Accurate electronic navigation maps creation

The base of the service is determining the ideal safe distance for a ship. The accuracy of electronic navigational charts is improved by fusing velocity, heading, water, and wind speed data utilizing the distributed sensor data ingestion, fusion, and post-processing services provided by **VA2**.

Service 3: Predictive maintenance and sanity checks applied on the sensor data for ship safety purposes

To obtain data for on-board diagnosis and monitoring, the service utilizes **VS9** On Board Data Collection & Interfacing for Vessels. In order to reduce the influence of the human factor in risk assessment and the possibility of making poor decisions, **VA3** uses the data for remote inspection and risk assessment.

Upgrades to RO testbed

UC2 revolves around the use of sensors and ML for improving business operations in the port. A network of IP cameras, interconnected with the 5G network using a 5G gateway, has been deployed and the related video streams are available for 3rd parties. Locally the connection to the gateway is done using 5G, Wi-Fi or by a LAN Cat 6 cable, depending on the location of the camera. Some areas experience a lot of shielding due to the large metal walls and the Wi-Fi signal is unreliable; for this reason, some cameras have been connected to the 5G gateway using cables. On the video stream received from the camera located on the vessel, we implement object detection. The video stream on which the detection is applied along with all other data that is captured is sent

to the 5G network using the gateway and is gathered in the testbed servers where it is logged in an InfluxDB database or streamed to a logged in user (camera video), so that they can be easily consumed by new Network Applications developed by 3rd parties. Moreover, 3rd parties can also access real-time or historical data collected from a monitoring station that measures the air quality in its proximity, as well as a wide set of engine data. The installation of additional equipment, as needed for the execution of additional 3rd party experiments, can be discussed, evaluated and negotiated on a per-experiment basis.

Examples of 3rd party experiments in RO testbed

A number of 3rd-parties, including SMEs, industries and academia, has already expressed interest in the usage of VITAL-5G services on top of the RO testbed, including both the usage of developed Network Applications and facilities or the ability for 3rd parties to deploy and validate their own Network Applications. Examples are listed in Table 7.

Table 7: Interested 3rd parties for RO testbed.

3 rd party	Experiment title	VITAL-5G Network Application(s) used	How the Network Application is used
Always Connected Consultants SRL (ACC)	Threat monitoring platform for wetlands and port areas.	VS9, VA3	ACC has developed a threat monitoring platform for wetlands and wants to extend it for port areas. It wants to use VS9 for IoT data collection that will be fed in its platform and the VA3 ML modules for risk assessment in port area or ships.
GreenRIS SRL	Platform for management of diffuse dust emissions from industrial activities in port areas.	VA6	GreenRIS uses IoT technology in air quality assessment and has developed its own platform for management of diffuse dust emissions from industrial activities. It plans to use VA6 for organising data coming from diverse air pollutant and particulate matter sensors and feed it in its air pollutant modelling software.
BEAM INNOVATION SRL	Drones for landing on ships.	VS9, VA2	Beam has its own platform for location-based services using BLE beacons. It plans to develop BI tools for drone landing on ships including a positioning component which calculates the real-time position of a drone based on camera feed (using VS9) and a trajectory estimation component which calculates the optimal trajectory of the drone according to ship movement, estimated vessel trajectory (using VA2).
ALTFACOR SRL	Promotion of Tourist Areas using Real-Time immersive aquatic experience.	VA6	ALTFACOR has a technological framework of sustainable research and promotion of tourist areas using Computer Vision and Audio-visual Recognition and plans to offer a holistic immersive experience based on a hydrophone, the 5G infrastructure and extensions of VA6 for audio stream separation.

MIHA	Humanoid robotic platform for VS9.	VS9	MIHA plans to improve VS9 offering by adding data from a humanoid robotic platform to be used in port operations.
Continental Automotive division	New Network Application for Smart Intersections.	N/A	Development and testing of a new Network Application for analytics in Smart Intersections.

2.4.2.3 Athens facility (GR)

In the DIAKINISIS warehouse trial site, we deploy and demonstrate the “Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics)” use case, which leverages on **5G Standalone (SA) connectivity** and **network slicing** principles to demonstrate the optimization of warehousing operations through an integrated state-of-the-art operational system based on Automated Guided Vehicles (AGVs) (VS1). The current deployment re-uses part of the 5G-EVE Athens testbed which has been upgraded Rel. 16 SA and extended at the warehouse premises. In detail, a new 5G Rel. 16 Core and a new virtualized infrastructure has been installed, interconnecting the DIA warehouse with the 5G Core through a fiber-optic cable.

This use case also supports the automated and remotely assisted operation of AGVs, using HD video streaming functionality to enable human interaction (VS2), while additional AI/ML techniques have been introduced for the post-processing of operational data in order to improve the end-to-end functionality of the warehouse ecosystem (VA1). A visual representation of the use case is depicted in Figure 9. The concept of **Network Applications** defined in the scope of VITAL-5G project has been used to **design and develop** these **vertical services** that support the use case.

Figure 9: Athens use case high-level representation.

In this case, three different Network Applications instantiate the three services as shown in Figure 10. A different combination of the Network Applications is required for the realization of each service.

Figure 10: Athens services and Network Applications.

The same trial site can be leveraged by the external experimenters, i.e., the 3rd party experimenters, which can be either involved in the use case Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics) to enhance it and experiment with the existing vertical services, or create their own use cases by reusing the network infrastructure (radio, edge, and core), Network Applications, and other tools such as local monitoring platform and slice plugins.

Figure 11: Mapping the goals of the Automation & remote operation of freight logistics (Warehouse logistics) use case to supported operations that can be exploited and further built upon by the 3rd party experimenters.

In this Section, we provide further details on the 5G system components within the Athens trial site, as well as the Network Applications that can be reused by the 3rd party experimenters.

Concerning the Athens 5G-Testbed, as a core of the Athens trial site, it spans the usual 5G SA ecosystem components (as shown in Figure 12):

- User Equipment, i.e., an AGV, a dedicated sensor Gateway with attached environmental sensors and video camera.
- Radio Access Network (RAN) with a dedicated gNodeB with two cells installed in a selected area of the DIA warehouse.
- Transport and Core network.

- A Cloud compute resource server that hosts the Network Application platform, designed and deployed to provide Network Function Virtualization (NFVI) resources for hosting and orchestrating Network Applications tailored to Assisted Vessel Transport use case, by using Open-Source MANO (OSM)-based orchestrator and Openstack/Kubernetes.
- A testing room with a gNodeB (not shown in the picture), with similar configuration and located in the OTE premises. The partner/experimenter can choose to conduct preliminary experiments/tests in this facility before moving to the DIA warehouse.

Figure 12: High-level overview of the Athens trial site.

As already mentioned in this section, the overall use case is developed via creating vertical services, which are further composed by Network Applications as building blocks. Here we provide a brief overview of the assets that are available in the Athens trial site and can be used by 3rd party experimenters.

In terms of **Network Applications**, the “Distributed sensor data ingestion fusion & automation” (VA1) will be provided for experimentation. For example, this will enable 3rd party experimenters to create and configure a vertical agnostic and data ingestion and post-processing Network Application. This Network Application can serve as a basis for 3rd party experimenters to build their own applications by combining it with a service of their own. This can be realized mainly via REST-based interfaces.

In case 3rd party experimenters are not aiming to build new vertical services and Network Applications, but to rather leverage on VITAL-5G trial sites to collect realistic **data** for validating their theoretical or simulation-based models, we offer several data types, which can be further extended depending on the needs and requirements from the 3rd-party experimenters. At the moment, the data types available in the Greek testbed are:

- Data from mounted sensors in the warehouse, mainly coming from the telemetry station (temperature, humidity, etc.) and the camera.
- Non-sensitive data coming from the warehouse and AGV operations (e.g., velocity, location, direction etc.)
- Network data collected from radio and core functions, including the network performance.

Furthermore, for the Greek node specifically, WINGS will make available a message broker, a warehouse simulator, namely a Digital Twin and a simulated warehouse environment which includes virtual AGVs, and a Fleet simulator. This way 3rd party experimenters will be able to build applications on top of the 24/7 available simulated data, avoiding the need to integrate with specific equipment (e.g., AGVs). The simulators will be deployed in a field device in DIA warehouse and will communicate over the 5G network, therefore, experimenters will be able to evaluate their application over a realistic 5G deployment.

The role of the 3rd party experimenters in the Greek trial site depends on the background knowledge and expertise of the onboarded parties. Thus, we adjust the role based on that, and tune the support depending on whether the 3rd party belongs to T&L industry (SMEs and start-ups), or research and academia domains (research institutes, universities).

Partners from the Greek trial site are focused on the engagement activities with the 3rd party experimenters by being active in all dissemination activities organized in the WP6 (T6.3). In particular, WINGS is heavily involved in engagement activities such as presenting the VITAL-5G project, and the assets offered to 3rd party experimenters to different webinars. This way and through personal contacts we managed to attract 2 different 3rd party experimenters namely an ICT-52 research project (DEDICAT6G⁸) and an SME based in the Netherlands (diTTo BV⁹). Further information regarding the 3rd party experimenters in the Greek trial site will be provided in WP4 and WP6 deliverables.

In particular, DEDICAT6G is interested in deploying their smart warehousing use case as a set of Network applications that provide the required service when combining them. Furthermore, they are interested in exploiting the network-related data collected from the 5G testbed to validate their algorithms for intelligence distribution, coverage extension and enhanced security and trust. Furthermore, diTTo BV delivers products and services for Digital Twins of Water Infrastructures and aims to test one of their digital twin applications over the 5G network provided by VITAL-5G. To handle the diversity of data sources (virtual/real devices, assets and knowledge elements) diTTo Digital Twins incorporate mechanisms to manage data acquisition in real time. The aim is not only to retrieve data from devices but to also aggregate information from any other systems and data sources available.

⁸ <https://dedicat6g.eu/>

⁹ <https://ditto-engineering.com/>

3 VITAL-5G Platform Requirements

This section presents the requirements of the VITAL-5G Open Platform. Section 3.1 introduces the methodology followed to identify and categorize the requirements, while section 3.2 presents the list of requirements discussing their impact on the VITAL-5G system.

3.1 Methodology

The identification of the requirements for the VITAL-5G open platform has initially followed a customer-oriented approach. Starting from the definition of the main categories of users that will interact with the platform (see section 2.2), the characteristics of their profiles have been analyzed in terms of know-how, expertise and expectations. This initial phase has identified the major experimentation services that the VITAL-5G platform should provide for each category of users, in order to facilitate the design, creation and testing of new 5G-enabled vertical services in general and, more specifically, for the T&L service.

In parallel, the practical analysis of the use cases developed from the partners in the consortium, with their related vertical services and Network Applications (as document in deliverable D1.1 [4], has provided a concrete foundation to identify more technical requirements in terms of specific functionalities and capabilities to be offered by the VITAL-5G platform as a whole and by the various testbeds. Examples of these inputs are the kind of metrics and KPIs to be collected, not only at the 5G network level, but also at the virtual computing infrastructure and application level, or the variability of network slice types to be offered, as well as the characteristics and vertical-oriented understanding of Network Applications and services. This technical analysis has been complemented with a survey, performed in collaboration with WP3, of the initial capabilities of the three VITAL-5G testbeds, their roadmap and the possibility of introducing new functionalities or enhanced levels of programmability (e.g., for dynamic slice creation or re-configuration). This approach has allowed an early evaluation of the technical feasibility of some requirements and, where needed, their refinement in order to obtain a consistent set of indications that can concretely drive the design and implementation activities.

Another major source of information for the definition of VITAL-5G requirements, in particular associated to the support of 3rd party experiments, is the practical experience built through the participation in previous ICT-17 projects¹⁰, like 5G-EVE. These projects have offered similar experimentation facilities for 5G-enabled services, open not only for internal use cases but also for experimentations from external ICT-19 projects¹¹. Beyond the experience on methodology and best practices to train, onboard and support external experimenters during their design and testing activities, the received feedbacks have been fundamental to identify the required technical improvements, e.g., in terms of flexibility in the vertical service management, direct access to the service virtual functions, open interfaces for the programmable collection of KPIs and lifecycle management of the service. Similarly, this collaboration has helped to prioritize the functionalities offered by the platform following the external perspective of very different categories of potential users, from pure verticals, mostly interested in simple and network-agnostic service deployment, to software developers and system integrators keen to make use of more advanced features for network programmability and service orchestration.

For the second release of the architecture, we also add the opportunity to collect feedback from a selected set of 3rd parties acting as early adopters of VITAL-5G services and working with preliminary versions of the VITAL-5G platform (running in the testing environment) and RO testbed. This allowed to introduce new requirements, refine some of the existing ones or change their categorization or priority. A similar exercise has been performed considering the inputs received from the implementation, deployment and integration activities performed in WP2 and WP3, as well as the internal trials in WP4.

Moreover, on the basis of the feedback from WP2, WP3, and WP4, the architecture and the VITAL-5G system implementation have been evaluated verifying their matching with the requirements defined in section 3.2. This

¹⁰ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-3-1-projects/>

¹¹ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-phase-3-3-projects/>

evaluation is reported in the final section 7 of the document, as a way to qualitatively assess the VITAL-5G platform functionalities and prioritize additional implementation actions which can be scheduled for the final release of the platform, planned for D2.4 and D3.3.

3.2 VITAL-5G Platform Requirements

This section describes the requirements of the VITAL-5G Platform, initially identified in deliverable D1.1 [4] and D1.2 [5], on the basis of the analysis of the experimentation services defined in Section 2.3 and inputs received from implementation, integration and trialing activities. Where relevant, the requirements have been associated to a specific experimentation phase.

The requirements are classified as mandatory and optional, and prioritized according to their importance in the overall experimentation process. This has provided a guideline to properly schedule the VITAL-5G implementation activities in WP2. Moreover, their impact on functionalities and components of the VITAL-5G system (both VITAL-5G platform and VITAL-5G testbeds) is analyzed as input for the architecture design.

It should be noted that some requirements defined as “optional”, even if not mandatory for the core experimentation services to be offered by the VITAL-5G Platform, are actually related to added value features that would greatly improve the usability of the system and the overall user experience. For this reason, their implementation has been or will be concretely addressed in WP2, even if introduced in the later releases of the platform. This approach has allowed to early provide a consistent set of functionalities with all the mandatory features, in support of the trials in WP4, and to progressively include enhanced features to improve the specific aspects of the design, validation or testing procedures.

Table 8 provides the updated list of requirements for the second release of the platform. Major changes from the previous list reported in D1.2 [5] are declared with “(NEW)”.

Table 8: VITAL-5G Platform requirements.

Requirement description	Category	Priority	Impact on VITAL-5G system
Generic Requirements (valid for all the experimentation phases)			
R_0_01: VITAL-5G Platform experimentation services The VITAL-5G Platform must provide and enable a centralized access for different actors to the VITAL-5G experimentation services during the various phases of the experimentation process: (i) Vertical Service design; (ii) Experiment design; (iii) Preparation of 5G testing environment; (iv) Vertical Service instantiation; (v) Experiment Execution; (vi) Vertical Service evaluation.	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform should provide a centralized access to the VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue with open interfaces to access the various experimentation services.
R_0_02: Web based UI The VITAL-5G platform should provide a web-based graphical user interface (GUI) to access all the VITAL-5G experimentation services.	Mandatory	Medium	The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI should provide a graphical and simplified access to the VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue services. The GUI may implement wizards to guide the users across the various experimentation steps and workflows.
R_0_03: OpenAPIs to access VITAL-5G platform functionalities in a programmable manner In addition to the GUI, a subset of the functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform services should offer REST-based interfaces.

experimentation services should be made available for external software components through programmable REST APIs.			Such REST APIs may be defined using the OpenAPI specification to simplify the development of external VITAL-5G clients.
<p>R_0_04: Users profiles and groups</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform should provide differentiated access permissions to multiple users, on the basis of their role (e.g., experimenter, Network Application developer, etc.) and their group (e.g., the use case where the user is involved).</p> <p>In particular, the users should have restricted access to private Network Applications, services and experiments, as well as limited visibility and control over assets of the T&L facilities (e.g., sensors, video camera, actuators).</p>	Mandatory	Medium	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should provide identity management and access control to protect digital assets and guarantee differentiated access to the functionalities offered by the platform, on the basis of the user role and group. The VITAL-5G access control should be based on RBAC (Role Based Access Control) mechanisms and differentiate the users' permissions (based on role and group) in terms of items visibility and permitted actions.</p> <p>The Web GUI should provide login functionalities and the access to REST API should be authorized. Mechanisms for user account registration should be supported.</p>
<p>R_0_05: Unified procedures across different VITAL-5G testbeds</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must expose common interfaces, information models and procedures to access the experimentation services, independent of the target VITAL-5G testbed where the experiments will be executed and the testbed's internal technologies or architecture.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G platform should implement unified interfaces, internal data models, procedures and workflows. The interaction with the various testbed should be enabled through a common abstract interface, complemented with testbed-specific drivers for adaptation and translation purposes.
Requirements related to Vertical Service Design			
<p>R_1_01: Browsing of existing Network Applications</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or to public Network Applications which can be re-used and composed in vertical services. The browsing of the Network Applications should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, category, etc. Network Application information should provide enough details to simplify their integration in vertical services and enable their testing and validation in the 5G network within the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should implement a catalogue of Network Applications and Vertical Services. Queries should allow to retrieve all the public Network Applications, while access control mechanisms should be applied for the visualization of private Network Applications.</p> <p>The Network Application package should include metadata describing the 5G related requirements and dependencies on T&L facilities hardware. These metadata will be encoded as part of the Network Application blueprint.</p> <p>NEW: Network Application packages and blueprints should be available for download from the VITAL-5G catalogue, to serve as examples for 3rd parties.</p>
<p>R_1_02: Onboarding of new Network Applications</p> <p>The user should be able to onboard new Network Applications in the VITAL-5G Platform. The onboarding should be properly authorized, taking also into account the level</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G catalogue of Network Application should enable the creation, update and removal of new Network Application packages, managing their synchronization with the catalogues at the target VITAL-5G testbed. Access control

<p>of access required by the Network Application to IoT devices and hardware in the T&L facility.</p>			<p>mechanisms should be applied, in compliance with the user's roles and groups, as well as the Network Applications' dependencies on T&L facilities hardware.</p>
<p>R_1_03: Validation of new Network Applications at onboarding stage The VITAL-5G Platform may enable the automated validation of new Network Applications, in terms of Network Application package format verification, functional validation in the target testbed, and compatibility with capabilities offered by the testbed (NEW).</p>	Optional	Low	<p>The VITAL-5G platform may provide tools to validate the format of the Network Application package, verify the consistency of the Network Application metadata with the capabilities of the target VITAL-5G testbed and verify their correct deployment and normal behaviour in the target testbed.</p>
<p>R_1_04: Unified Network Application and service modelling The VITAL-5G platform must expose a common format and methodology to onboard, edit, update, delete, and monitor Network Applications and T&L service experiments, independent of the target 5G testbed and the format of the descriptors used in the testbed's internal catalogues.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform must support a unified format for the Network Application package, independently on the information model of the VNF packages handled in each VITAL-5G testbed. Suitable translation procedures may be required when onboarding the packages in specific VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
<p>R_1_05: Network Applications onboarding with possibility to declare metadata that helps Network Applications composition, testing, and validation When a Network Application is onboarded, the user must be able to include metadata to facilitate composition, testing, and validation of the Network Application in an automated manner.</p>	Optional	Medium	<p>The Network Application package should include metadata describing the characteristics of the Network Application, e.g., interfaces, protocols, testing procedures, service KPIs, etc. These metadata will be encoded as part of the Network Application blueprint. NEW: Custom configuration and testing scripts should be supported as part of the definition of Network Applications and related experiments, combined with procedures for automated execution of configuration commands and test cases handled at the VITAL-5G Platform.</p>
<p>R_1_06: Onboarding of new Vertical Services The user should be able to define and onboard new Vertical Services composed of Network Applications in the VITAL-5G Platform. The onboarding of vertical services including Network Applications with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include a Vertical Service blueprint (VSB) catalogue, which should enable the creation, update and removal of new VSBs. The VSB information model should enable the definition of service-level characteristics and Network Applications' composition and linking to NSDs defining their instantiation in a VITAL-5G testbed. The catalogue should keep the synchronization with the catalogues at the target VITAL-5G testbed. Access control mechanisms should regulate the onboarding of VSBs with restricted Network Applications.</p>

<p>R_1_07: Browsing of existing Vertical Services</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Vertical Services. The browsing of the Vertical Services should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, use case, etc. Vertical Service information should provide service-level information related to their Network Applications, 5G requirements and validation criteria.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G platform Vertical Service catalogue should allow queries for VSB retrieval, with suitable access control mechanisms.
<p>R_1_08: Browsing of information related to VITAL-5G testbed capabilities</p> <p>The user should be able to visualize information related to the capabilities of the VITAL-5G sites, e.g., in terms of 5G network infrastructure, available network slices, edge/cloud computing resources, IoT devices and hardware in the T&L facility (e.g., sensors, video cameras, actuators, etc., including their permitted access type, i.e., in read-only, write-only or read-write mode). The access to some information may be restricted, depending on the user profile and group.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include an inventory service with open interfaces to retrieve the details of the various VITAL-5G sites.</p> <p><i>Note:</i> in the early version of the platform, the same kind of information can be provided statically with suitable testbed documentation. Such documentation will be collected in a web page linked in the portal.</p>
<p>R_1_09: Facilitated composition of Network Applications in vertical services</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform can provide mechanisms to facilitate the composition of Network Applications into end-to-end services, which could be partially automated according to the metadata defined in the Network Application package and in the vertical service blueprint.</p>	Optional	Low	The VITAL-5G Platform may include a tool to automatically build the NSD associated to a vertical service blueprint, composing the Network Applications' functions of its components.
<p>R_1_10: Specification of 5G requirements for Network Applications and Vertical Services</p> <p>The user must be able to declare the 5G related requirements for Network Applications and Vertical Services, using a simplified approach based on the declaration of pre-defined parameters.</p> <p>NEW: The user must be able to declare 5G requirements at the vertical service level different than the original ones associated to Network Applications composing the end-to-end service.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>Network Applications and Vertical Service blueprints must enable the modelling of 5G requirements, e.g., in terms of characteristics of the mobile connectivity or required 5G services, using a simplified and service-oriented model. The VITAL-5G platform should internally translate these requirements into network slices, e.g., through Network Slice Templates.</p> <p>NEW: 5G requirements declared at the service level should override the ones associated to the internal Network Applications.</p>
<p>R_1_11 NEW: Specification of computing infrastructure requirements for Network Applications</p>	Mandatory	Medium	Network Application blueprints must enable the modelling of requirements on the target virtual computing infrastructure. The VITAL-5G platform should provide internal

<p>The user must be able to declare the requirements on the target computing infrastructure where the Network Applications will be deployed (e.g., support of Graphics Processing Units - GPUs).</p>			<p>mechanisms to select accordingly the computing nodes to deploy the Network Applications' components.</p>
<p>Requirements related to Experiment Design</p>			
<p>R_2_01: Browsing of existing Experiment blueprints The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Experiment blueprints. The search should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, use case, etc.</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include an Experiment blueprint catalogue. Access control mechanisms should regulate the queries of Experiment blueprints.</p>
<p>R_2_02: Onboarding of new Experiment blueprints The user should be able to define and onboard new Experiment blueprint for the experimental validation of vertical services available in the VITAL-5G catalogue. The onboarding of experiment blueprints referred to vertical services with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>The Experiment blueprint catalogue should enable the creation, update and removal of new experiment blueprints. Access control mechanisms should regulate the onboarding of experiment blueprints associated with vertical services with restricted access.</p>
<p>R_2_03: Wizard for guided definition and onboarding of new Experiment blueprints The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI may provide a wizard to guide the user in the definition of the various parameters that constitute an experiment blueprint.</p>	<p>Optional</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>This requirement should be implemented through a dedicated functionality in the VITAL-5G Platform GUI.</p>
<p>R_2_04: Validation of new experiment blueprints at onboarding stage The VITAL-5G Platform may enable the automated validation of new experiment blueprints, in terms of format verification and compatibility with the existing vertical services.</p>	<p>Optional</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G platform may provide tools to validate the format of the experiment blueprint and verify the availability of the related vertical service in the catalogue.</p>
<p>R_2_05 (NEW): Onboarding of new Test Case blueprints The user should be able to define and onboard new Test Case blueprints specifying the scripts to be executed during the automated testing and the related variables. Test Cases should be linked to the experiment blueprints.</p>	<p>Optional</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>VITAL-5G Catalogue should include a Test Case blueprint catalogue, enabling their creation, update, query and removal.</p>
<p>Requirements related to preparation of 5G testing environment</p>			
<p>R_3_01: Onboarding of new Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors for experiment customizations</p>	<p>Mandatory</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G platform should include catalogues for Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors in the VITAL-5G Catalogue. Access control mechanisms</p>

<p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Vertical Service descriptors and Experiment descriptors in the VITAL-5G Platform catalogue, in order to declare the specific configuration and customization of services and experiments, based on their blueprints. The onboarding descriptors referred to blueprints with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>			<p>should regulate the onboarding of descriptors associated to blueprints with restricted access.</p>
<p>R_3_02: Browsing of existing Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The Vertical Service and Experiment descriptor catalogues in the VITAL-5G Platform should include access control mechanisms to regulate the queries of the various descriptors.</p>
<p>R_3_03: Scheduling of service and experiment instances</p> <p>The user must be able to declare a preferred time slot for the provisioning of a vertical service and the execution of the experiments.</p> <p>NEW: The aspects of this requirement related to automated scheduling and resource reservation has been removed, since the preferred approach is based on agreements between experimenters and testbed owners in offline mode. The motivations are related to the flexibility needed in the execution of the experiments, allowing the developers to adjust their applications and repeat their test without strict time constraints.</p>	Mandatory	Medium	<p>The information models and the interfaces related to service provisioning and experiment executions should allow to specify a time slot.</p>
<p>Requirements related to Vertical Service instantiation</p>			
<p>R_4_01: On-demand provisioning and LCM of vertical services</p> <p>The user must be able to provision a vertical service on-demand and request the execution of lifecycle management actions, like scaling, re-configuration and termination. The service instantiation should be enabled only for public vertical service blueprints, the ones owned by the user or associated to his/her use cases. Other LCM actions on instantiated services should be enabled only to the users associated to the given use case.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G Platform, at the Portal level, should include a component in charge of managing the lifecycle of vertical services, triggering the instantiation of the related network services in the target testbed and thus coordinating the lifecycle of the associated Network Applications. The component should be integrated with access control mechanisms.</p>
<p>R_4_02: Secure user access to instantiated Network Applications</p> <p>The user must be able to access the Virtual Machines or containers where his/her own Network Applications are running in a secure manner.</p>	Mandatory	High	<p>The VITAL-5G testbeds must enable a secure connectivity (e.g., via VPN) to the Network Applications running in their virtual environments. The VITAL-5G Platform should visualize the information required to access the Network Applications (e.g., IP addresses assigned to the management interface of the running instances).</p>

<p>R_4_03: Hosting and execution of concurrent vertical services, guaranteeing target QoS</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must be able to deploy, manage and monitor multiple and simultaneous instances of Vertical Services, each of them with their own Network Applications.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G testbeds must support the provisioning of multiple network services, with the instantiation of their Network Applications, within isolated or shared network slices, each with guaranteed QoS.
<p>R_4_04: Automated management of network slices</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must coordinate the management of the network slices required for a given vertical service in a fully automated and transparent manner. Where required, the usage of edge resources for deployment of Network Application components should be enabled.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G platform must enable the coordinated management of the network slices required to deploy a Vertical Service and its Network Applications. Such management can be based on the dynamic provisioning, configuration and termination of network slices or rely on the selection of pre-defined and pre-existing network slices at the VITAL-5G testbeds, depending on the specific testbed capabilities. These mechanisms should be triggered internally during the provisioning and lifecycle management of a vertical service, and be fully transparent for the users.
<p>R_4_05: Transparent interaction between the VITAL-5G Platform and the VITAL-5G testbeds</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must be able to interact with the local NFV MANO and NG-RAN/5G CN control systems available at the three trial facilities. The details of such interaction must be fully transparent for the VITAL-5G users.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform should adopt unified abstract interfaces for its southbound interaction with the various testbeds and adopt testbed-specific drivers to communicate with the specific orchestrator, controllers and monitoring platforms available in each testbed.
<p>R_4_06: Centralized license management for Network Applications</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform should provide mechanisms to verify and manage different types of licenses associated to the Network Applications.</p>	Optional	Low	The VITAL-5G Platform should include a component responsible for Network Applications' license validation in coordination with service deployment and lifecycle management procedures. Network Applications' licences should be modelled and declared in the Network Application package.
<p>R_4_07: Logic for optimized placement of virtual functions or automated slice management</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform may implement internal logic and procedures to optimize resource orchestration, slice management and virtual function placement e.g., on the basis of the slice type and profile, resource utilisation and service demands. Such mechanisms may be implemented through AI/ML algorithms e.g., for load prediction.</p>	Optional	Low	The VITAL-5G Platform may include an internal component, potentially implementing AI-based algorithms, responsible for optimizing the decisions on placement of Network Applications virtual functions and infrastructure resource orchestration.
Requirements related to experiment execution			

<p>R_5_01: On-demand experiment execution The user must be able to request the execution of an experiment, starting from its experiment descriptor, over an instantiated vertical service. The user must be able to request experiments only on his/her own vertical services, when in running mode.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform, at the Portal level, should include a component in charge of managing the lifecycle of the experiment execution, in cooperation with the associated vertical service management, triggering the collection of monitoring data and the analysis of the results. The component should implement access control mechanisms.
<p>R_5_02: Automated execution and configuration of test scripts The user can declare test scripts that will be automatically configured and executed during the running of an experiment.</p>	Optional	Medium	The VITAL-5G platform component responsible for experiment management should be able to trigger the execution of test scripts, e.g., in specific Network Applications. The modelling of the experiment should support the declaration of test scripts with configurable variables.
<p>R_5_03: Support for secure, manual execution and configuration of test scripts on Network Applications during experiment execution. During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to access the Network Applications in a secure manner, in order to manually trigger the execution of commands or test scripts.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G testbeds must enable a secure connectivity (e.g., via VPN) to the Network Applications running in their virtual environments during the experiment execution phase.
<p>R_5_04: Decoupled service lifecycle management during experiment execution. During the execution of an experiment, the user (or an external entity) must be able to trigger lifecycle management actions on the associated vertical service (e.g., to scale up and down, terminate or re-configure some Network Applications).</p>	Optional	Low	The logic of the VITAL-5G Platform components responsible for vertical service and experiment execution lifecycle management should be decoupled and independent.
<p>R_5_06: Monitoring, collection and visualization of 5G network metrics and KPIs. During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize monitoring data related to 5G network KPIs, as declared in the experiment blueprint.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G Platform, at the Portal level, should include a monitoring platform for the collection, storage and visualization of monitoring data, coming from different data sources. VITAL-5G testbeds should be able to measure 5G KPIs and publish the data into the VITAL-5G monitoring platform.
<p>R_5_07: Monitoring, collection and visualization of service-level metrics and KPIs. During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize service-level KPIs, as declared in the blueprint, assuming that the Network Applications implement the mechanisms required to collect and publish such data.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G monitoring platform should give the possibility to receive monitoring data in a standard format, facilitating the publishing of monitoring data from the Network Applications deployed in VITAL-5G testbeds.

<p>R_5_08: Monitoring, collection and visualization of metrics and KPIs related to the virtual computing infrastructure.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize monitoring data related to the virtual computing infrastructure (e.g., CPU or memory utilization), associated to the consumption of resources for the service Network Applications.</p>	Optional	Medium	VITAL-5G testbeds should be able to collect KPIs from their virtual computing infrastructure and publish the data into the VITAL-5G monitoring platform.
<p>R_5_09: Secure access to real-time and historical monitoring data via open interfaces.</p> <p>The user (or an external entity) must be able to access the various monitoring data collected during the execution of an experiment in a secure and authorized manner through open interfaces. These interfaces should support the efficient consumption of the data both in real-time or through queries for historical data.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G monitoring platform should provide a secure and open interface for external entities to retrieve the monitoring data stored and/or collected. Access control mechanisms should regulate the access to the different categories of monitoring data.
<p>R_5_10 <i>NEW</i>: Automated AI/ML-based diagnostic for closed-loop LCM actions.</p> <p>During the experiment execution, the insights coming from the diagnostics functionality, potentially based on AI/ML techniques and applied to both computing infrastructure and network, should trigger automated LCM actions during the Network Applications' execution, following a closed-loop approach.</p>	Optional	Medium	The diagnostics component of the VITAL-5G platform should be able to recognize under-performing conditions and suggest actions to be undertaken in terms of network slice reconfiguration or scaling of Network Applications to enhance the performance of the service. The component in charge of service LCM should be able to enforce such suggestions, interacting with the underlying VITAL-5G testbeds and depending on their specific capabilities.
Requirements related to Vertical Service evaluation			
<p>R_6_01: Visualization of information related to executed experiments, with reports on the service and network KPIs collected during their execution.</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the list of executed experiments and, for each of them, visualize its details, graphs related to its service and network KPIs, as well as results related to the experiment execution.</p>	Mandatory	High	The VITAL-5G monitoring platform should store the service and network KPIs and enable their visualization on a per experiment basis. The VITAL-5G platform component responsible for experiment management should be able to store the results of executed experiments and expose them to the GUI. The VITAL-5G platform should include a component responsible for the analysis of the monitoring data, in order to produce experiment results (e.g., based on KPIs' thresholds declared for the experiment).
<p>R_6_02: Automated diagnostic for identifying service bottlenecks and root cause of performance degradation.</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform should be able to process the KPIs collected during an</p>	Optional	Medium	The VITAL-5G platform may include a diagnostic component, potentially adopting AI techniques, that examines the collected monitoring data and outputs an analysis of

experiment and identify in an automated manner the potential causes of performance degradation, related to issues at the 5G network or computing infrastructure level.			the possible reasons of the service underperformance.
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4 Network Applications in VITAL-5G

This section describes the concepts of Network Applications in VITAL-5G, how they are modelled and how they can be composed in Vertical Services. In particular, Section 4.1 introduces the concept of Network Application and the service-oriented approach defined in VITAL-5G to represent them. The categories of Network Applications are presented in Section 4.1.1, while Section 4.1.2 explains how various Network Applications can be combined together to build a more complex vertical service. The concept of Network Application package, used to distribute the Network Applications and make them available through the VITAL-5G Catalogue is described in Section 4.2, defining the format of the package (Section 4.2.1) and its information model (Section 4.2.2), including the elements of the Network Application blueprint. The related data model has been specified in WP2 and documented in deliverable D2.1 [6]. Updated blueprints of VITAL-5G Network Applications are available in VITAL-5G open-source software repository¹². The modelling of a vertical service is defined in Section 4.3, where the concepts related to Vertical Service Blueprints, Vertical Service Descriptors and their translation into NFV Network Service Descriptors and Network Service instances are explained. The Experiment and Test Case blueprints introduced in the second release of the platform are described in section 4.4. Finally, Section 0 provides a survey of Network Application modelling and management in the context of other 5G PPP projects, highlighting commonalities and differences with the VITAL-5G approach.

4.1 Concepts and modelling

One of the key objectives of VITAL-5G is the realization of the Network Application concept, which aims to simplify the vertical service design, lifecycle management and testing on top of 5G infrastructures. In this sense, in VITAL-5G we envision vertical services, and in particular T&L services, as the composition of Network Applications into service-chains with multiple virtual application components that make use of 5G connectivity. Here, each Network Application provides its own complete functionality, even when deployed as a stand-alone entity, but it can cooperate and interact with other Network Applications to deliver more complex T&L services aligned with the overall business target of a Service Provider. The focus is therefore set on establishing mechanisms that on the one hand enable simple composition of Network Applications and, on the other hand, abstract the low-level orchestration details required to deploy the service on top of 5G infrastructures.

In practical terms, the Network Application concept extends the typical orchestration-oriented descriptors proposed in ETSI NFV (e.g., VNFDs, NSDs) with enhanced declarations of the service level information that simplify the re-usage and integration of Network Applications into vertical services. For example, the definition of Network Applications interfaces allows to compose together different Network Applications and share their adoption across multiple T&L services. From the 5G slicing and orchestration capabilities perspective, the Network Applications also extend the orchestration descriptors with the specification of the main characteristics of the required 5G slice profile, and with declaration of the 5G Core services which the Network Application leverages for optimized orchestration decisions.

The VITAL-5G Network Application concept also covers the integration and validation phases of the Network Application development lifecycle. For this the VITAL-5G Network Application package also includes the definition of the test scripts and the targeted metrics and KPIs which allow the assessment of the Network Application on a certain scenario from both a functional integration and overall performance perspective.

¹² https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vital-5g-netapp-blueprints

Figure 13: Example of Network Application.

Figure 13 represents an example Network Application, in particular an IoT Management Platform Network Application that handles IoT data from/to local IoT supervisors installed in the field at the UE side, e.g., in various vessels. These IoT supervisors act as IoT gateways towards a number of multi-protocol and multi-vendor IoT devices, both sensors and actuators, and use the 5G connectivity to interact with the IoT Management Platform Network Application, which can be deployed dynamically in the virtual computing infrastructure (edge or cloud) offered by one of the VITAL-5G testbeds.

The picture highlights some of the concepts related to the modelling of a Network Application. Following an approach similar to the structure of a Virtual Network Function (VNF), a Network Application can be considered as a set of internal *Atomic Components* (the red boxes in the Figure 13), which correspond to virtualized deployment units (e.g., a container or a Virtual Machine) and implement the different parts of the application logic. These components interact with each other through a number of internal *Connectivity Services* (the dotted line in the Network Application box), i.e., the equivalent of virtual networks. Each component has one or more endpoints that enable this interaction. The endpoints can be internal ones (light-grey circles in Figure 13), used only for the interaction among the components of the same Network Application or external ones, used to interact with elements external to the Network Application. For example, external endpoints are used to model the connection points associated to the Network Application interfaces that provide access to the application functionalities for final users or other service elements that interact with the Network Application itself.

A particular case of external endpoint is the one through which the Network Application is interconnected to the 5G network, i.e., on the N6 interface of the 5G system. In the Network Application modelling, this endpoint is characterized by one or more 5G service profiles, which describe the characteristics of the network slices required for the given Network Application's functionalities. The 5G service profile includes information like the slice service type (i.e., eMBB or URLLC), relevant QoS parameters (e.g., uplink and downlink data rate, latency, jitter) and additional attributes related to the 5G mobile connectivity, like coverage area, radio access technology, etc. Moreover, the possibility to deploy a Network Application in the context of a 5G infrastructure gives also the opportunity to consume some of the services offered by the 5G network, for example the network

data analytics service and the localization service, used to retrieve information about the performance of the 5G network and the position of the UEs, respectively.

In the particular T&L sector, several Network Applications interact with hardware devices that are deployed in the T&L facility, e.g., with IoT gateways, AGVs, etc. In the Network Application modelling, this is expressed as hardware dependency (the grey box on the left of the picture) since the Network Application functionalities are strictly related to its interaction with these components and its validation requires their presence in the testing environment.

All these characteristics contribute to define a service-oriented description of the Network Applications, which can be used by the vertical actors to easily select and manipulate Network Applications for building their own vertical services. Following this modelling, the vertical does not need to go into the details of the internal structure of the Network Application, to have the know-how related to its deployment over a virtualized infrastructure or to understand the complex configuration of a 5G network slice. The Network Application package, as a consequence, needs to include two levels of modelling:

- the abstract and service-oriented model, captured in the Network Application blueprint, which defines the metadata used by the vertical to search, operate, combine and test Network Applications through the functionalities exposed by the VITAL-5G platform;
- the orchestration-oriented and network-oriented model, captured by the VNF descriptor/package and any related 5G network slice template, which defines how the Network Application components need to be instantiated, dimensioned and interconnected over the virtual computing infrastructure and how the network slices must be configured to properly serve the expected traffic flows. This model is not directly exposed to the vertical, but it is used internally in the VITAL-5G platform and in each of the VITAL-5G testbeds to drive the deployment of the Network Applications in their target environments.

4.1.1 Categorization of Network Applications

In VITAL-5G Network Applications have been classified following two different types of categorizations: (i) vertical-specific versus vertical-agnostics Network Applications and (ii) service-based versus component-based Network Applications.

A **vertical-specific Network Application (VS)** implements functionalities designed specifically for a given vertical scenario and vertical service. Its usage is related to a specific use case and it is not designed to be easily customized or configured to adapt to different environments or services. Examples of vertical-specific Network Applications are software-based IoT gateways specialized for a single type of IoT device, data processing engines with specialized and service-driven logic, dashboards for a predefined type of data, etc. A **vertical-agnostic Network Application (VA)**, instead, is a generalized Network Application that can be easily adopted in different services since it supports multiple customizations, data models, processing types, etc. Example of vertical-agnostic Network Applications are databases, message brokers, generalized monitoring probes or generalized AI/ML engines. It should be noted that the classification in vertical-specific and vertical-agnostic Network Applications is only used to facilitate the search and browsing of Network Applications in the VITAL-5G catalogue through dedicated filters, but it does not imply any difference in their modelling or composition.

The other categorization type differentiates between component-based and service-based Network Applications. **Component-based Network Applications** are atomic and elementary software components that operate in a generalized manner and can be composed together and configured in a flexible manner, so that they can be customized to serve different purposes. A component-based Network Application can be delivered as a packaged set of software images with predefined configurations and interfaces, which can be then updated and customized to build more specialized Network Applications delivering their own service. These are typically defined as **service-based Network Applications**, i.e., Network Applications providing independent services that can be accessed in a standardized manner to support specific business requirements. In this sense, a service-based Network Application can be deployed in stand-alone mode, without any dependency on additional Network Applications, and it is able to provide its own complete set of functionalities. A service-based Network

Application can include multiple software components, providing added-value services through their interaction. An example of service-based Network Application could be a data collection function that includes authorization mechanisms and translation of raw data into a common format. In general, multiple component-based Network Applications, properly configured and customized, can be combined together to form a service-based Network Application, as shown in Figure 14. Here, for example, the component-based “Data Storage” Network Application, which can be used in general to store different types of data, is configured with specific data models and then used as part of a wider service-based Network Application which implements a monitoring system.

Figure 14: Composition of customized component-based Network Applications in a service-based Network Application.

4.1.2 Network Applications and (T&L) Services

As described in the previous section, a Network Application can provide its own complete set of functionalities even when deployed as a stand-alone entity. However, it can also cooperate and interact with other Network Applications to deliver more complex vertical services. While in VITAL-5G the focus is mostly on T&L services, the concept of 5G-enabled vertical services composed of multiple Network Applications is applicable to very different sectors and the VITAL-5G architecture, service modelling and procedures can be considered as general ones, not only limited to the T&L services.

Vertical (T&L) services are loosely coupled chains of cloud-native and 5G ready Network Applications, which can leverage the 5G infrastructure and services for their instantiation in virtual environments and their interaction with mobile users and/or IoT and T&L devices deployed in the field in the T&L facilities. Network Applications can be reused and composed across multiple vertical services, speeding up and facilitating the design and delivery of new services.

The key difference between a service-based Network Application, composed of multiple software functions, and a Vertical Service composed of multiple Network Applications is the fact that a service-based Network Application is distributed with a single package (potentially integrating multiple software images) and delivered by a Network Application developer, following the same principle of VNFs. On the opposite, a Vertical Service is composed of multiple Network Applications that can be provided by different vendors and it does not include the internal package distributions, but only their references, following the approach of NFV Network Services.

Figure 15: Example of Vertical Service composed by two Network Applications.

Figure 15 represents an example of a Vertical Service resulting from the composition of two Network Applications, a Data Collection Network Application and a Digital Twin Network Application. The Data Collection is a service-based Network Application that internally is composed of multiple component-based Network Applications and offers functions to retrieve data from the field, authorize the data access, translate the data into a common format, store and visualize them. The Data Collection Network Application provides a set of functionalities, accessible from external entities, to (i) configure the Network Application, (ii) retrieve the data from the internal storage and (iii) visualize the data through a dashboard. These functionalities are modelled as “provided interfaces” and they describe the details required by a service provider to compose the Network Application with other ones in order to create a vertical service with additional features. In this example, the Data Collection Network Application provided interfaces are “consumed” by the Digital Twin Network Application, which uses the data retrieved from the storage to build the digital twins of particular objects of interest. As represented in the picture, the Digital Twin Network Application is characterized by a “consumed interface”, that models the need to interact with a Network Application offering those kinds of functionalities. Moreover, the internal details of the Data Collection Network Application can be fully omitted when building a vertical service: as shown in Figure 16, all the Network Applications appear as black boxes in the Vertical Service model, keeping only the details of the respective interfaces.

Figure 16: Example of Vertical Service composed by service-based and component-based Network Applications.

The criteria to compose the vertical services depend on the specific requirements of the service, while the Network Application and vertical service modelling provides the highest level of flexibility in a service-independent manner. In the example reported in Figure 16, the vertical service is composed of Network Applications of different types (both service- and component-based) and provided by different vendors. In this particular example, the service provider may be interested in developing its own algorithms and logic for data aggregation and processing, without focusing too much on the techniques to retrieve the data from the various

protocol busses in the field or the development of dashboards for graphical interfaces. As a consequence, in order to quickly build a complete end-to-end solution to propose to its customers, he/she complements the “Sensor data ingestion, fusion & post-processing” Network Application, which constitutes the core of its offering, with a data collection and a visualization Network Application provided by 3rd parties and available in the VITAL-5G catalogue.

Obviously, the decision on the composition logic lies with the service provider, who should take into account both functional and non-functional requirements. The functional requirements can be verified through the analysis of the Network Applications’ interfaces, while the non-functional ones need to take into account the performance that can be measured during the experimental validation on the VITAL-5G platform. In this particular example, the composition with the 3rd-party Data Collection Network Application on one hand simplifies the data ingestion from heterogeneous sensors exposing a single interface to consume data in a unified format, but on the other hand introduces an additional delay in the whole data collection chain. This may make the overall service suitable for a data processing applied to reporting and medium/long term data analysis, but less applicable for real-time reactions. The experimental validation functionalities offered by the VITAL-5G platform, with the features to collect and analyze network-level and service-level metrics, will help to identify potential issues in this sense.

It should be also noted that different versions of the same type of Network Application, potentially provided by different vendors, can be adopted to build a vertical service. This approach gives the opportunity to exploit and evaluate the particular customization, internal logic and proprietary algorithms offered by different Network Applications and to select the most suitable ones for different operational environments. In the example in Figure 17, two vertical services for the visualization of sensors data are adopting two different versions of a Data Collection Network Application, developed by different software providers. This can be useful e.g., in case of Network Applications specialized to retrieve data from different field busses or implementing data collection techniques that guarantee different latency. The compatibility of multiple Network Applications within a given vertical service depends on their external interfaces, which must be open and specified in the Network Application metadata to allow the service providers to easily compose the Network Applications in their end-to-end vertical services. The Network Application internal logic, instead, can be kept proprietary and fully hidden to service providers and experimenters, who would be interested only in the Network Application performance within the overall vertical service.

Figure 17: Example of vertical services using two implementations of the same Network Application.

The possibility to use different Network Application versions to replace a logical component of the vertical service is expected to increase the market opportunities for Network Application developers, often SMEs, which can propose custom solutions with added value designed for specialized targets. Similarly, the possibility to build services with extreme flexibility, choosing their components from a wide catalogue and validating their performance in variable contexts is fundamental for the service providers. In fact, on the basis of the experiment results obtained through the VITAL-5G platform, they can deploy a variety of service customizations with different Network Applications’ versions and optimized service tuning, to better match the expectation of

particular customers’ segments or the 5G network characteristics expected in their target operational environments.

4.2 Network Application Packages

4.2.1 Network Application Package format

Traditional VNF packages provide the software images of the Virtual Deployment Units (VDUs) composing the VNF itself (or Containerized Deployment Units in case of Container-based Network Functions - CNFs) and a VNF descriptor defining how the VNF should be deployed in a target virtual environment (e.g., number and size of VDUs for different deployment flavours of the same network function, internal and external network connectivity, performance metrics to be collected, etc.). Moreover, a typical VNF package also includes a set of additional files and metadata related to the VNF configuration files and software licenses.

Network Applications packages extend the concept of VNF packages to provide additional information that facilitates the distribution, deployment and re-use of Network Applications in several environments and across multiple application services, focusing particularly on aspects related to:

- Network Applications integration into end-to-end service chains combining multiple Network Applications and interacting with on-field devices, in the VITAL-5G case specific for the T&L sector;
- Automation of Network Applications testing and validation, from a functional and non-functional perspective, in a variety of 5G environments.

The definition of this additional information is modelled through Network Applications metadata embedded in the Network Application packages and encoded in a Network Application blueprint. Such metadata has a twofold purpose in the context of the VITAL-5G Platform. On one hand they can be shown on the VITAL-5G Catalogue to facilitate and enhance the searching and the browsing of Network Applications. On the other hand, they specify the application-specific logic which is used to drive the automation of Network Application provisioning, lifecycle management, testing and validation in the VITAL-5G testbeds. Moreover, a number of optional files can be embedded in specific folders of the Network Application package to provide additional documentation and test cases to facilitate the usage and validation of Network Applications for software developers.

Figure 18: High-level representation of a Network Application package.

Figure 18 represents the composition of a Network Application package. In general, the Network Application package is a zipped file that includes a textual file in JSON format with the Network Application blueprint, used

to describe the Network Application metadata, and a variable number of folders including various files, like VNF packages, software licenses, specification documents related to the software design and test cases.

The Network Application packages are used to onboard new Network Applications and to download them from the VITAL-5G catalogue. In order to make it more manageable, a Network Application package may not include directly the entire VNF package with the related software images (the size of VM image is in the order of GB), but only their references. In this case, the package includes a textual file with URLs to retrieve the VNF package from the NFV Orchestrator catalogues in the VITAL-5G testbed where it is available or from an external software repository used by the Network Application developer to distribute the software.

4.2.2 Information model

Table 9 provides the list of information elements which compose the information model of a Network Application, identifying how they are mapped into the various items that compose a Network Application package. The format of the VNF package and VNF descriptor follows the specification defined in the ETSI GS NFV-SOL 004 [7] and NFV-SOL 006 [8]. More in detail, the VNF packages used in VITAL-5G are compliant with the format adopted by the OpenSource MANO (OSM) NFV Orchestrator (NFVO), which is available in all the three VITAL-5G testbeds. The format of the Network Application blueprint is a proprietary one, encoded in JSON format, and it follows a similar paradigm to the Vertical Service blueprint originally defined in the context of the 5G EVE project and extended in VITAL-5G to represent the blueprint of a T&L Vertical Service. On the basis of the Network Application package information model, WP2 has defined the related data model, which is documented in deliverable D2.1 [6]. A few updates have been introduced in the second release of the architecture, e.g., to refine the description of the required IoT and T&L devices available on-field and to model criteria for the selection of the computing nodes where the Network Application components should be deployed (e.g., GPUs for efficient ML training, as requested by a 3rd party). Examples of Network Application blueprints are available in VITAL-5G open-source software repository¹³.

The Network Application blueprint data model is reported in Annex 2 – Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint data models – updated version.

Table 9: Information elements of a Network Application package.

Network Application package element	Source	Description
Software images	VNF package	Images of the software to be deployed in the virtual environment to instantiate the components of the Network Application. Software images can be Virtual Machine (VM) images or container images, depending on the adopted virtualization.
Virtual Function (VF) Descriptor	VNF descriptor in VNF package	Descriptor providing the details about the deployment of the Network Application software components in the virtual environments and their lifecycle management. Includes information about the interconnectivity among the components, the external connection points, the virtual resources required to instantiate (or to scale to) different flavours of the function, the configuration, the monitoring metrics, etc.
Software license	License files in Network Application package	Provides the licensing term for the Network Application as a whole and, if needed, for its components. License metadata in the Network Application blueprint enables the VITAL-5G platform to perform the e-licenses validation during the instantiation and lifecycle management of Network Applications.

¹³ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/vital-5g_netapps/vital-5g-netapp-blueprints

	License element in Network Application blueprint	
Network Application features	Network Application blueprint	Describes the high-level characteristics of the Network Application, like type, category, target VITAL-5G testbed, access level (public/restricted), related use case, detailed description for users and developers, etc. This information would be used in the VITAL 5G Catalogue to classify and filter the Network Applications and to visualize their details.
Network Application high-level structure	Network Application blueprint	Provides the high-level and service-oriented description of the Network Application structure, defining its atomic components, how they are interconnected, and the internal and external endpoints used to interact with the Network Application.
5G mobile connectivity requirements	Network Application blueprint	Identifies the Network Application requirements in terms of 5G mobile connectivity, e.g., slice type, target KPI values for minimum throughput in uplink or downlink, maximum latency, etc. These requirements are associated to the external endpoints interconnecting to the 5G network.
5G services requirements (optional)	Network Application blueprint	Identifies the list of 5G services exposed by the 5G core network which may be required by the Network Applications. Currently, the network data analytics and the localization services are defined. Their support depends on the capabilities of the 5G network deployed in the VITAL-5G testbed.
Monitoring information	Network Application blueprint	Provides a list of the application and infrastructure metrics that must be monitored to evaluate the performance of the Network Application. Application metrics are generated by the Network Application itself, while infrastructure metrics must be measured at the infrastructure level in the testbed where the Network Application is running. Infrastructure metrics include both 5G network KPIs and metrics related to the usage of computing resources (e.g., used CPU, memory, disk).
Software-related documentation	Network Application blueprint Additional files in Network Application package (optional)	Provides software documentation with the aim of facilitating 3 rd party software developers to integrate the Network Application in T&L services. For example, it provides information about the Network Application interfaces, e.g., protocols, message formats, etc. Optionally, the Network Application package can include additional files with protocol-specific interface specification (e.g., OpenAPI spec. for REST API, SQL schemas, etc.).
Test and validation specification (optional)	Additional files in Network Application package (optional)	As an option, Network Applications can also specify a list of test cases (with test environment, test scripts, variables to automate the testing execution, etc.) with the related validation criteria to assess the Network Application performance in the target 5G infrastructure. Such testcases can be embedded as files in the Network Application package and they may follow the VITAL-5G Test Case format specified in D1.4 [9].
Hardware requirements (optional)	VNF descriptor	Defines hardware requirements related to the physical servers where the virtualized component of the Network Application will run.

Hardware compatibility (optional)	Network Application blueprint	Provides the list of hardware devices (e.g., IoT sensors/actuators, IoT gateways, AGVs, vessels control system, etc.) which must be installed in the T&L facility and reachable from the Network Application in order to enable its functionalities. New types of devices have been considered in the second release of the platform, according to their real availability in the three testbeds.
Target compute nodes selection criteria (optional) [NEW]	Network Application blueprint	Defines criteria, like the availability of GPUs, that the VITAL-5G platform should consider in the selection of the target computing nodes to deploy the Network Application components.

4.3 (T&L) Vertical Services Blueprints

As discussed in section 4.1.2, multiple Network Applications potentially provided by different vendors can be stitched together in a service chain that composes a vertical service. The representation of vertical services in VITAL-5G follows the approach originally defined by the 5G-TRANSFORMER project [10] and then further extended in the 5G EVE project [2]. The Vertical Service Blueprint (VSB) is used to provide a service-oriented, high-level description of the service characteristics and it constitutes a template that the vertical users can use to customize their services. The VSB includes the list of the service components, which in VITAL-5G are Network Applications, with details about their endpoints and interconnectivity. As for Network Applications, the service external endpoints interconnecting to the 5G network are characterized by a service profile that identifies the requirements of the 5G mobile connectivity and drives the selection or provisioning of the 5G network slices. The VSB provides additional information related to the service logic, for example application or infrastructure-level monitoring metrics, a number of variable service parameters that the user can customize to request different versions or deployment flavours of the same service, as well as variable configuration parameters that can be specified at the instantiation time.

The VSB is associated to a Network Service Descriptor (NSD) that describes how the service must be instantiated and orchestrated in an NFV Infrastructure (NFVI) deploying an NFV Network Service (NFV-NS). The NSD is composed of VNFs that, in VITAL-5G, correspond to the VNF packages associated to the Network Applications composing the service. The instantiation of the service can follow different flavours, e.g., including or excluding some Network Applications and deploying a variable number of instances of the same Network Application. This approach allows, for example, to remove some functionalities or to scale the service dimension based on the target operational environment, e.g., presence of some types of sensors, number of expected mobile users, number of vessels to be controlled, etc.

The various service flavours are modelled internally in the NSD and they can be selected automatically by the VITAL-5G platform on the basis of the vertical service customization requested by the user. This customization can be defined assigning specific values to the variable service parameters declared in the VSB. Such values are encoded in the Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD), that provides the specification of a vertical service requested by the user (e.g., a vertical service provider) filling the template of the VSB. Using some translation rules defined as part of the service design process, the VITAL-5G platform selects the flavour more suitable to meet the requirements specified by the user and instantiates the NFV-NS accordingly in the target VITAL-5G testbed (see Figure 19). In order to simplify the overall service definition, the translation rules are optional in VITAL-5G and, if missing, the service is automatically instantiated with the NFV-NS default flavour.

It is worth to mention that the NFV MANO systems, available in the VITAL-5G testbeds and interfaced by the VITAL-5G platform, are compliant with the NFV MANO functionalities specified by ETSI NFV standards. In this sense, they provide interfaces at the NFV Orchestrator level to instantiate and operate on the lifecycle of NFV network services, while the management of single VNFs is not permitted. In fact, VNFs are usually handled internally through dedicated VNF Managers (VNFMs) that are not exposed via external interfaces. This means that the instantiation and testing of single Network Applications need to be associated in any case to a

corresponding network service, where this network service would include just a single VNF, i.e., the target Network Application itself.

Figure 19: Vertical Service design, customization and instantiation.

Table 10 provides a list of the information elements of a (T&L) Vertical Service, specifying where they are defined, i.e., at the VSB, VSD or NSD level. The definition of related data model is in the scope of WP2, and it is documented in D2.1 [6]. The format of the NSD follows the ETSI GS NFV-SOL 006 [8] specification, as adopted by the OSM orchestrator.

In the second release of the architecture, a new information element has been introduced to describe rules that regulate the closed loop automation of the service lifecycle, handled at the VITAL-5G platform level. Actions for service and Network Application scaling, migration of Network Application components and updating of network slices characteristics are supported, on the basis of pre-defined thresholds on monitored metrics or events triggered by the AI-based diagnostics tool (see sections 6 and 6.4-6.5 for further details). The related VSB data model updates are reported in D2.3, section 4.1 [1] and also documented in Annex 2 – Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint data models – updated version.

Table 10: Information elements of a Vertical Service Blueprint.

Information element	Defined in	Description
Vertical Service high-level structure	VSB	Provides the high-level and service-oriented description of the vertical service structure, with a list of its Network Applications (referred through their Network Application blueprint), their min/max multiplicity, interconnectivity, endpoints and functions chain. Vertical service endpoints must be mapped to a subset of the Network Applications external endpoints.
NFV Network Service Descriptor	NSD	Descriptor providing the details about how the vertical service can be instantiated over a NFVI, identifying the virtual functions to be deployed, how many and the related size, how they must be interconnected internally and to external infrastructure networks, etc. The NSD must refer the VNFDs of the Network Applications included in the vertical service.
Vertical Service features	VSB	Provides the high-level description and characteristics of the vertical service, for classification and filtering purposes, e.g., VITAL-5G testbed, access level (public/restricted), related use case, visibility level, human readable description, etc.

Vertical Service customizable parameters	VSB	Provides the list of service-level parameters, configurable from the user, that influence the deployment of the service.
Translation criteria (optional)	Translation rules	Rules that map ranges of values for a subset of the service-level parameters into the corresponding flavour of the NSD. They are used to translate the high-level definition of the service provided by the vertical into the technical description of the NFV-NS to be instantiated. If not defined, the NFV-NS is deployed with its default flavour.
Vertical Service configuration parameters	VSB	Provide the list of parameters that the user can set and configure when requesting the service. Such values are configured on the single Network Applications after the instantiation procedure.
5G mobile connectivity requirements	VSB	Identifies the overall service requirements in terms of 5G mobile connectivity. These requirements are associated to the external endpoints of the service interconnecting to the 5G network and, when present, they override the corresponding parameters declared in the Network Application blueprint.
Monitoring information	VSB	Provides a list of the application and infrastructure metrics that must be monitored to evaluate the performance of the service as a whole. The application metrics must be a subset of the ones declared in the Network Applications included in the service. Infrastructure metrics may include additional items than the ones defined in the Network Applications.
Test and validation specification (optional)	Additional files in Network Application package (optional)	As option, Network Applications can also specify a list of test cases (with test environment, test scripts, variables to automate the testing execution, etc.) with the related validation criteria to assess the Network Application performance in the target 5G infrastructure. Such testcases can be embedded as files in the Network Application package and they may follow the VITAL-5G Test Case format specified in D1.4 [9].
Hardware compatibility (optional)	VSB	Provides the list of hardware devices which must be installed in the T&L facility to run the service. The list can be a subset of the corresponding items declared in the Network Application blueprints.
Closed loop action rules (optional) [NEW]	VSB	Provides optional rules that allow to automatically scale or migrate the vertical service and/or to modify the profile of the associated network slices on the basis of predefined thresholds on monitored metrics or events triggered by the diagnostic.

4.4 Experiment and Test Case Blueprints

The second release of the VITAL-5G architecture introduces experiment blueprints and descriptors (ExpB, ExpD) to provide a formal definition of the experiments to be performed on the VITAL-5G platform, describing their characteristics, procedures, context configurations, metrics and KPIs to be collected and evaluated, as well as some criteria to evaluate their results. The experiment blueprint provides a template for the configuration of a category of experiments associated to a virtual service and it is used as a template that the experimenters can customize in different ways (through experiment descriptors) to repeat the same experiment emulating different environment conditions or focusing of different sets of results. Experiment blueprints and descriptors are used as input for the VITAL-5G platform component responsible to launch and manage the lifecycle of concurrent experiments. In case of automated testing procedures, the testcase blueprint (TCB) provides the list of actions and/or scripts to be executed on the components of the deployed Network Applications and vertical services. The related configuration parameters can be declared in the testcase descriptor used to launch an experiment.

The information model of experiment and testcase blueprints are described in Table 11, while the related data models have been documented in D2.3 [1].

Table 11: Information elements of Experiment and Testcase Blueprints.

Information element	Defined in	Description
Experiment high-level description	ExpB	Provides the high-level and vertical-oriented description of the experiment, referring the type of vertical service it can be applied to (through its Vertical Service blueprint).
Experiment configuration parameters	ExpB	Provide the list of parameters that the user can set and configure when launching the experiment.
Monitoring information	ExpB	Provides a list of the application, infrastructure and network metrics to be monitored and evaluated to verify the performance of the service. The metrics must be a subset of the ones declared in the blueprint of the vertical service the experiment is associated to.
Result analysis criteria	ExpB	Provides information about how to compute KPIs, as well as process and evaluate the collected metrics.
Testcases (optional)	ExpB	List of testcases to be used for automated testing. If not available, the execution of the experiment is based on manual actions, like real users that access the service via smart phones or tablets during the trials.
Scripts for automated testing execution	TCB	List of scripts or actions to be automatically launched at the different phases of the experiment execution. The scripts include variables which are automatically valorized by the VITAL-5G Platform on the basis of the input provided by the experimenter when launching the experiment execution or the parameters assigned automatically by the platform for the given service instance (e.g., IP addresses, etc.)

4.5 Network Applications in the context of 5G PPP activities

A total of nine projects (including VITAL-5G) have been funded by the European Commission in the context of the “H2020-ICT-41-2020: 5G innovations for verticals with 3rd party services” call, targeting the development, validation and promotion of Network Applications in various vertical sectors and the engagement with 3rd party experimenters of the respective sectors. Each project is working on precisely defining the concept and capabilities of the Network Applications and their related components, as integrated in the overall system architecture as envisioned by each project. The Technical managers of the projects and their experts are currently discussing relevant approaches and insights in the 5G PPP Technology Board (TB) sessions and the respective 5G PPP Working Groups, such as the Architecture WG and the Software Networks WG. Based on the work carried out individually from the projects and through active collaboration, it is the vision of the ICT-41 projects to progress some guidelines regarding the definition, deployment and best practices on the use of Network Applications in various vertical sectors. Such a common approach will be defined through the common organization of workshops and webinars, as well as through 5G PPP WG discussions. For the time being each project has defined some key elements that are related to the deployment and use of Network Applications, as presented in Table 12.

Table 12: Key elements for Network Applications use & deployment.

Project Name	Testbeds	Vertical	Considered Network Application aspects
5GASP	Aveiro (PT) Bucharest (RO) Patras (EL) Bristol (UK) Ljubljana (SK) Murcia (ES)	Automotive PPDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Automated and open DevOps based CI/CD process for developers, to translate their applications / services into Network Applications, based on vertical-specific requirements. Network Application store providing access to Network Applications, Network Functions and Network Services Network Application marketplace incl. Network Application catalogue
5G-EPICENTRE	Malaga (ES) Aveiro (PT) Barcelona (ES) Berlin (DE)	PPDR	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Open-source repository for PPDR 5G Network Applications Cloud native transformation Decoupling of network functions from virtual machines (VMs) toward Containerized Network Functions (CNFs) Accommodate a microservices-based model, e.g., deconstructing VNFs into microservices, that can be deployed on a shared cloud infrastructure
5G-ERA	-	Robotics automation for PPDR Automotive Healthcare Manufacturing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A middleware which enables cloud native resource provision over autonomous robots Extending 5G open environment and standard APIs of testbeds into robotic vertical sectors
5G-IANA	Ulm (DE) Ljubljana (SK)	Automotive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network Application Orchestration and Development framework (NOD) 5G-IANA Network Application toolkit linked with a new Automotive VNFs repository Data model with a simplified high-level representation of different service components, to hide network complexity <p>It is worth to mention that 5G-IANA adopts a Network Application modelling aligned with the VITAL-5G Network Application blueprint, which has been extended to cover additional requirements for the provisioning of application functions in extreme edge and edge nodes deployed on OnBoard Units and Road-Side Units. Moreover, 5G-IANA adopted a subset of the VITAL-5G catalogue as baseline for the implementation of the 5G-IANA NApp Toolkit, where it has been extended and integrated with mechanisms for CI/CD of Network Applications.</p>
5G-INDUCE	Spain Greece Italy	Industry 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Full stack Network Application Management platform Network Application composition API Break Network Application into cloud native components Build/Generate the interconnection of Network Application components Showcase the full Network Application deployment chain
5G-MEDIAHUB	Norway Spain	Media & Entertainment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Network Applications: Application enablement services, offering PaaS extensions (e.g., CDN) Hiding NFVI and 5G complexities, while supporting cloud-native vertical applications

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offering domain specific (i.e., media) and domain agnostic (e.g., security) Network Applications • Unified Northbound APIs for vertical applications • Network Applications can span across multiple testbed facilities within Network Slice Instances (NSIs)
EVOLVED-5G	Athens (EL) Malaga (ES)	Industry 4.0	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Middleware layer that will simplify the implementation and deployment of vertical systems at large scale • 5G-Enabled vertical apps with the aid of Network Applications that consume 5G core Northbound APIs • Network Application marketplace and open repository • New North-bound APIs and/or vertical enablers that could fulfil more vertical requirements, such as app-level analytics
SMART 5GRID	Italy Greece Bulgaria	Energy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Integrated, open, cooperative, and fully featured 5G network platform, customised for smart energy distribution grids • In conjunction with the 5G network facility, the Open Service Repository will have access to network resources and it will be used to develop and accommodate Network Applications
VITAL-5G	Antwerp (BE) Athens (EL) Galati (RO)	Transport & Logistics	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Online Network Application repository • Cloud-native design and deployment over 5G infrastructures (edge/cloud) • Service-based Network Applications: Each Network Application can include multiple virtual components and provides “added-value” services composing different software modules • Component-based Network Applications: Atomic software components working in a generalized manner, which can be composed together and configured in custom manners to serve different purposes

5 VITAL-5G Architecture

This section describes the architecture of the overall VITAL-5G system, introducing in section 5.1 the two major elements, i.e., the three VITAL-5G testbeds integrating 5G infrastructures and edge/cloud computing resources on T&L facilities and the VITAL-5G platform that operates on top of the three testbeds. The platform offers unified access to the entire set of VITAL-5G experimentation services, which are detailed in section 5.2 explaining how they are mapped to the three categories of VITAL-5G users (Network Application developers, service providers and experimenters). Section 5.3 focuses on the VITAL-5G platform, presenting the architectural principles adopted for its design and describing its functional architecture, listing its internal components (the related software design and implementation is covered in WP2). The description of the architecture includes the workflows that regulate the interactions among the platform components, as well as the definition of the NBI exposed towards the platform’s users and the SBI that enables the communication with the different testbeds.

5.1 VITAL-5G System: the overall picture

The high-level architecture of the VITAL-5G system, as originally defined at the proposal stage, is still valid in its main concepts and principles. The overall system is structured in two layers. At the upper layer, the **VITAL-5G Platform** (section 5.1.1) provides the various users with a unified access to all the VITAL-5G experimentation services. The VITAL-5G Platform operates over the lower layer of the architecture, composed of a set of **three VITAL-5G testbeds** (section 5.1.2) deploying a 5G network infrastructure with virtual computing capabilities and SDN/NFV technologies in three different types of T&L facilities, i.e., a sea and a river port and a warehouse, as shown in the simplified schema of Figure 20.

Figure 20: Simplified schema of VITAL-5G system.

5.1.1 VITAL-5G platform

The VITAL-5G Platform is the element of the VITAL-5G system architecture that offers the first unified interface towards the VITAL-5G users interested in experimenting and trialling with T&L Network Applications and services in realistic 5G environments. The Platform provides a single point of access for all the VITAL-5G experimentation services and all the Network Applications and vertical services onboarded in the system, wrapping and hiding the underlying interactions with the three testbeds.

Internally, the Platform is composed of two macro blocks, i.e., the VITAL-5G Portal and the VITAL-5G Catalogue (i.e., the Open Online Repository module represented in the initial draft of the architecture at the proposal stage), assisted by a third backend element for Platform management. All the VITAL-5G Platform components expose their functionalities through a programmable interface based on REST API and a web-based graphical

interface. The former enables the access to external software entities (e.g., service orchestrators, other vertical applications, etc.), while the latter is designed to facilitate the usage of VITAL-5G services for human actors (e.g., Network Application developers, experimenters, etc.). The VITAL-5G catalogue offers the list of Network Applications, vertical services and experiments onboarded in the system and allows to upload new services or Network Applications and preliminary validate their compatibility with the target testbed. The VITAL-5G Portal offers the mechanisms to provision and manage Network Applications and vertical services, execute experiments, retrieve and store monitoring data and visualize experiment results and reports. The VITAL-5G Platform Management Backend provides inventories and support services for the internal management of the platform and the handling of its interactions with the various testbeds. The internal design of the VITAL-5G Platform is further described in section 5.3.

5.1.2 VITAL-5G testbeds

The VITAL-5G system offers three 5G testbeds installed in operational T&L facilities (in the sea port of Antwerp, the river port of Galati and a warehouse in Athens) where VITAL-5G users can run their experiments and trials in realistic environments and interact with real equipment. Each testbed provides a secure access towards the VITAL-5G Platform, exposing a set of functionalities for 5G network management, instantiation and orchestration of NFV services, monitoring of network and infrastructure KPIs. Moreover, the testbeds offer VITAL-5G users (both internal and 3rd parties) a secure VPN access to the virtual environment where the Network Applications are deployed, giving the possibility to directly interact with them.

The VITAL-5G Platform interacts with the testbeds performing a set of common actions which are automatically translated into the commands supported by the testbed-specific internal systems and platforms, which are often proprietary. These actions include onboarding of new VNF packages, descriptors and software images, instantiation and lifecycle management of services and Network Applications in virtual environments, configuration or selection of 5G network slices in support of the provisioned services, collection of 5G network KPIs and interaction with running Network Applications components for configuration and monitoring purposes.

Each testbed deploys internally its own 5G infrastructure, including RAN and Core Network, with their own 5G management system. The 5G network is complemented by an NFV framework for instantiation of virtual network functions and virtual applications in edge/cloud resources, SDN platforms for control of transport network and monitoring platforms for collection, processing and storage of network and computing infrastructure metrics. The networking environment is integrated within the target T&L trial facilities, which deploy specific types of T&L and IoT devices (e.g., sensors, AGV, video cameras, etc.) connected to the 5G network directly or via 5G CPEs. Despite the wide technological fragmentation, all the testbeds expose a unified set of basic functionalities towards the VITAL-5G platform. Additional functionalities can be offered as options for more advanced and dynamic procedures. A more detailed description and the internal design of each testbed have been reported in WP3 deliverables D3.1 [11] and D3.2 [3].

5.1.3 Deployment Models for VITAL-5G System

The deployment model selected for the reference implementation of the VITAL-5G architecture, which will be used during the execution of the project, is based on a centralized pattern. This model, shown in Figure 21, is characterized by a central cross-testbed platform deployed in a single instance (placed on the Romanian testbed), which provides a unified access to all the VITAL-5G users, independent on the target testbed where they will execute their experiments. The VITAL-5G platform is managed in centralized mode, in the context of the VITAL-5G project execution and activities, and it handles internally multi-site inventories, catalogues, repositories for all the users, Network Applications, services, network slices, IoT devices, etc. At its southbound, it is interconnected to all the three testbeds via secure VPNs and implements testbed-specific drivers to mediate the interaction with the heterogeneous orchestrators, monitoring systems, 5G network infrastructures, etc. deployed in each testbed.

Figure 21: Centralized deployment model for VITAL-5G architecture.

The choice of this solution is particularly suitable during the project runtime since it simplifies the development, integration, testing, configuration, troubleshooting and maintenance activities, which are applied to the single platform. In other terms, we can consider a single and centralized administration of the VITAL-5G platform, operating within the project consortium, that is responsible for the overall platform operation and interacts with the various testbeds administration, responsible instead for the single T&L facilities and 5G infrastructures, with related users, services, devices, etc. The users that want to access the VITAL-5G services require an agreement in place with the VITAL-5G consortium and can interact with the overall system using the unified and centralized access of the VITAL-5G platform.

However, in order to guarantee a proper exploitability of VITAL-5G results and testbeds after the termination of the project, the testbed owners can deploy per-testbed instances of the VITAL-5G platform in order to continue to offer 5G experimentation services over their own 5G infrastructure and T&L facility. The resulting deployment model, applied to the Antwerp testbed as an example but applicable to all the three testbeds, is represented in Figure 22. In this case, the VITAL-5G Platform is deployed in Antwerp and it is managed by the Antwerp testbed administrator, together with the testbed itself. At the southbound, only the Antwerp testbed driver is adopted, simplifying the maintenance and troubleshooting when the single testbed is updated with new releases of 5G networks, orchestrator, monitoring systems, etc. Similarly, the internal databases of the VITAL-5G platform will store only the information related to the Antwerp site users, Network Applications, services, devices, etc., simplifying the overall operational and management procedures. Finally, in this post-project scenario, the users will have business agreements directly with the operators of the target testbed, or 3rd-party entities managing the business of experiment validation services over the given testbed. In this scenario, additional business agreements may be in place between the testbed operators and the developers of the VITAL-5G platform software, e.g., for licenses of closed source software components, for software support and maintenance of open-source software components, for system integration and/or new software developments to support updates in the testbeds' systems.

Figure 22: Distributed, per-testbed deployment model of VITAL-5G architecture.

5.2 Services offered by VITAL-5G Platform

The VITAL-5G Platform offers a set of services and tools that facilitate the entire experimentation process, during the different experimentation phases introduced in Section 2.3. Table 13 provides an overview of these services and tools, mapping them to the particular experimentation phase and identifying the associated VITAL-5G macro-components (i.e., VITAL-5G testbeds or VITAL-5G Platform, with VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue).

Table 13: Experimentation services and tools offered by VITAL-5G.

Experimentation phase	VITAL-5G service or tool	Involved VITAL-5G component
Vertical Service design	Inventory of VITAL-5G testbeds, providing information on 5G network capabilities and available devices in each testbed.	VITAL-5G testbeds VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Schemas and examples for Network Application blueprints and Vertical Service blueprints, to facilitate the design and modelling of new Network Applications and services.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Catalogue of public Network Applications that can be re-used as components to build new vertical service.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Onboarding of new Network Applications, with validation of Network Application blueprint format, verification of the compatibility with the selected site, onboarding of VNF packages in the NFV orchestrator of the target testbed and functional verification of a successful instantiation in the virtual environment.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue VITAL-5G testbeds

	Onboarding of new vertical service blueprints with automated onboarding of NSDs in the NFV orchestrator of the target testbed.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue VITAL-5G testbeds
Experiment design	Schemas and examples for Experiment and Testcase blueprints, to facilitate the design and modelling of new experiments.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Onboarding of new experiment and testcase blueprints, with validation of blueprint format and verification of compatibility with the declared vertical services.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Guided definition of experiment blueprints to select vertical service, network and service KPIs, evaluation criteria, test cases, and configuration parameters	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Catalogue
Preparation of 5G testing environment	Guided customization and configuration of experiments, starting from their blueprints available in the VITAL-5G Catalogue.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue
Vertical Service instantiation	Automated provisioning of vertical service with instantiation and configuration of its Network Applications.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Automated configuration or selection of 5G network slices to support the vertical service.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Activation and configuration of service and network KPIs monitoring.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Validation of software licenses for Network Applications to be instantiated or scaled up.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue
	Manual or automated lifecycle management of instantiated services and Network Applications, with closed-loop mechanisms based on predefined rules or triggers launched by AI-based diagnostics during experiment execution (e.g., for scaling or migration of Network Applications or update of network slice profiles).	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Secure interaction between Network Applications and well-defined sets of devices in T&L facilities.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Direct and secure access to instantiated Network Applications for manual re-configuration and troubleshooting.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
Experiment execution	Customization, configuration and launch of experiments.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal

	Automated configuration and execution of test scripts.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Collection and elaboration of monitoring data: retrieval of network and computing infrastructure KPIs from the testbed infrastructure and collection of service KPIs from Network Applications components.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	Visualization of monitoring data collected in near-real-time through graphs and dashboards.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Direct and secure access to instantiated Network Applications for execution of test scripts and troubleshooting.	VITAL-5G testbeds
	APIs to trigger lifecycle management actions on the instantiated service and Network Applications in a programmable manner.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
	APIs to retrieve monitoring data for service and network KPIs in a programmable manner.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal VITAL-5G testbeds
Vertical Service evaluation	Analysis of experiment results.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Validation of network and service KPIs.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	AI-based diagnostics for identification of bottlenecks and origin of performance degradation, with possible triggering of closed-loop re-configuration actions.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal
	Experiment reporting.	VITAL-5G Platform: VITAL-5G Portal

5.2.1 Mapping between VITAL-5G Services and VITAL-5G user categories

Section 2.2 introduced three different categories of VITAL-5G users, i.e., Network Application developers, service providers and experimenters. In VITAL-5G all users, during their registration, are associated to one or more of these three categories, which regulates the kind of actions that they can perform over the VITAL-5G platform. Moreover, users are associated to user groups, corresponding to VITAL-5G use cases or additional use cases introduced with 3rd parties. The user group regulates the visibility and accessibility to items that are not public, but specifically associated to a use case and, consequently, that can be visualized, used or manipulated only by the members participating in that use case. For example, sensors deployed in the T&L facility for a specific use case will be visible only to the participants of that use case; similarly, private Network Applications designed for a single use case will be available only to compose vertical services and run experiments related to that use case.

Table 14 summarizes the actions permitted for the three user categories in each of the experimentation phases, assuming that the user belongs to the related use case. All the functionalities offered by the VITAL-5G platform for the related actions are implicitly supported, as described in the previous section. For example, the onboarding of a new Network Application includes the access to the Network Application blueprint schemas, the verification of the Network Application compatibility with selected testbed, the validation of the Network Application package format, the onboarding of the VNF package in the target testbed, etc.

Table 14: Actions enabled for VITAL-5G user categories.

Action on VITAL-5G platform enabled for...	Network Application Developer	Service Provider	Experimenter
Vertical Service design			
Visualization of information on VITAL-5G testbed capabilities	Y	Y	Y
Visualization of available Network Application packages	Y	Y	Y
Onboarding of new Network Application packages	Y	N	Y
Modification or removal of existing Network Application packages	Y (Only owned Network Applications not in use)	N	Y (Only owned Network Applications not in use)
Visualization of available Vertical Service Blueprints	N	Y	Y
Onboarding of new Vertical Service Blueprints	N	Y	Y
Modification or removal of existing Vertical Service Blueprints	N	Y (Only owned services not in use)	Y (Only owned services not in use)
Experiment design			
Visualization of available experiment and testcase blueprints	N	N	Y
Onboarding of new experiment and testcase blueprints, via REST API or upload via web GUI.	N	N	Y
Modification or removal of existing experiment and testcase blueprints	N	N	Y (Only owned experiments not in use)
Preparation of 5G testing environment			
Visualization of available Vertical Service Descriptors	N	Y	Y
Onboarding of new Vertical Service Descriptors, via REST API or upload via web GUI.	N	Y	Y
Modification or removal of existing Vertical Service Descriptors	N	Y (only owned services not in use)	Y (only owned services not in use)
Visualization of available Experiment Descriptors	N	N	Y
Onboarding of new Experiment Descriptors, via REST API or upload via web GUI.	N	N	Y
Modification or removal of existing Experiment Descriptors	N	N	Y

			(only owned services not in use)
Vertical Service instantiation			
Request to instantiate new vertical services	N	Y	Y
Visualization of details about instantiated vertical services and related Network Applications	N	Y	Y
Request to scale up/down a vertical service (via GUI or REST API)	N	Y	Y
Request to terminate a vertical service (via GUI or REST API)	N	Y	Y
Visualization and access to monitoring data related to a vertical service	N	Y	Y
Access to vertical service's Network Applications	N	Y	Y
Experiment execution			
Request to launch new experiments	N	N	Y
Visualization of details about running experiments	N	N	Y
Launch of test scripts and access to Network Applications during experiment execution	N	N	Y
Visualization of monitoring data related to the experiment execution on the VITAL-5G Portal web GUI	N	N	Y
Retrieval of monitoring data related to the experiment execution via REST API	N	N	Y
Request to scale up/down a vertical service involved in the experiment execution (via GUI or REST API)	N	N	Y
Request to terminate a vertical service involved in the experiment execution (via GUI or REST API)	N	N	Y
Vertical Service evaluation			
Visualization of experiment results	N	N	Y
Visualization of diagnostics results	N	N	Y
Visualization and download of experiment reports	N	N	Y

5.3 VITAL-5G Platform Design

This section describes the functional architecture of the VITAL-5G platform. Starting from the main architectural principles that have driven its design (Section 5.3.1) also on the basis of the requirements discussed in Section 3.2 and the feedback received from WP2 and WP3 implementation/integration activities, the main system components of VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue are identified in Section 5.3.2. It should be noted that this deliverable, and WP1 in general, addresses the functional architecture of the system, while the particular software implementation is covered in WP2. For this reason, the internal software design of the reference architecture components is reported in WP2 deliverables, with the latest version documented in D2.3 [1]. The high-level workflows, northbound and southbound interfaces are finally described in Section 5.3.3, 5.3.4, and 5.3.5, following an abstract and protocol-independent approach. The specification of protocol messages and

Open API have been addressed in the context of WP2 and they are reported in D2.3 [1] and available in the public software repository of the VITAL-5G Platform¹⁴ (within the API folder of each software component).

5.3.1 Architectural Principles

The VITAL-5G Platform has been designed according to the following guidelines and architectural principles:

1. The VITAL-5G Platform should be designed to enable experimentation services for internal and external users, with different profiles and access rights, providing functionalities and features customized for the various levels of expertise of the planned user categories. In particular, the access to the VITAL-5G experimentation services should be facilitated and simplified following a vertical-driven perspective but providing additional options for enhanced configurability, programmability and flexibility in 5G network configuration and service management.
2. The access to the VITAL-5G Platform services should be enabled both via graphical user interfaces for human interactions and via programmable, open interfaces for 3rd party systems interactions.
3. The VITAL-5G Platform should support multi-tenancy and concurrent experimentations for multiple users over the same infrastructure.
4. The VITAL-5G Platform should provide secure and isolated access to private or restricted resources, based on user profiles and user groups, while guaranteeing full visibility and access to public resources¹⁵.
5. The VITAL-5G Platform should be compatible with the architectures, functional elements and interfaces of 5G systems, as defined in the 3GPP specifications, assuming that VITAL-5G testbeds will deploy 5G network infrastructures compliant with the standards and will make use of the latest NFV and SDN technologies for deployment of virtualized network and service functions and, where needed, configuration of the transport network.
6. The VITAL-5G Platform should be compliant with 3GPP and ETSI standards for its interaction with the VITAL-5G testbeds, adopting where relevant de-facto standards. This will guarantee the exploitability of the VITAL-5G Platform software (even beyond the project termination) facilitating its interoperability with common deployments of 5G networks and infrastructures.
7. The VITAL-5G Platform should be designed following a modular approach with unified abstract interfaces that enables a simple integration with (additional) testbeds supporting enhanced functionalities or proprietary interfaces, to be supported developing testbed-specific adaptors.
8. The design of the VITAL-5G Platform should maximize the re-usage of existing architectural components from previous 5G PPP projects (in particular 5G EVE) which have developed open platforms for experimental validation of 5G-enabled services for internal and external users. In particular, the introduction of new components should be limited to the support of additional functionalities or features, while solutions based on extensions, adaptations and customizations of existing modules should be preferred. When new functional elements are required, their interfaces should be designed to facilitate their integration with the existing platform components and workflows, without a major impact on the overall system.
9. The design of the VITAL-5G Platform should be inspired by Service Based Architecture (SBA) principles, with each functional element providing an interface to enable the consumption of its services from the other elements of the system or the final users. Depending on the type of expected interactions, query/reply patterns for synchronous communication as well as subscribe/notify patterns for asynchronous communication should be supported.
10. The design of the VITAL-5G Platform should enable the deployment of its components in a virtualized computing environment, with mechanisms for modular, dynamic, configurable and automatic orchestration.

¹⁴ https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform

¹⁵ Here a resource represents a generic item managed by the VITAL-5G platform, e.g., a Network Application blueprint or a Network Application instance, an IoT device in a VITAL-5G testbed, a deployed service, a 5G network slice, an experiment, etc.

11. At the functional architecture level, the design of the VITAL-5G Platform should be protocol and language agnostic, enabling different implementations of the same functionalities and components. The specific decisions on protocols, formats and language of the messages, etc. will be taken during the implementation activities in WP2.
12. All the north-bound interfaces of the VITAL-5G Platform should be open to facilitate its integration with 3rd party systems.
13. The VITAL-5G Platform should follow a modular design easy to extend and configure for supporting additional capabilities, technologies and functionalities that may be introduced in next releases of the platform itself or in the VITAL-5G testbeds.

5.3.2 Functional Architecture

The functional architecture of the VITAL-5G system is represented in Figure 23, highlighting the centralized VITAL-5G Platform (the red box) that operates over the three VITAL-5G testbeds (the three brown boxes at the bottom of the picture). The VITAL-5G Platform is structured in two main components, i.e., the VITAL-5G Portal backend and the VITAL-5G Catalogue, each of them including a number of functional elements and supported by a set of management backend services. The VITAL-5G platform functional elements provides interfaces to expose their functionalities, which can be consumed by all the other elements following the pattern of Service Based Architectures. The VITAL-5G Catalogue and Portal backend north-bound interfaces (NBI) allow the VITAL-5G users to securely access the authorized VITAL-5G services in a programmable manner, mostly via REST APIs. Access control mechanisms, based on roles and groups, regulate the type of services and resources which are visible and available to the various users, according to the user-service mapping defined in section 5.2.1. On top of the VITAL-5G Platform programmable interfaces, a centralized web-based GUI (with access based on username and password) offers an additional graphical Portal with dedicated tools, designed to simplify the users' manual interaction with the VITAL-5G Platform, for both VITAL-5G Portal and Catalogue services.

On its south-bound interface (SBI), the VITAL-5G Platform interacts with the three VITAL-5G testbeds. In particular, this interface mediates the interaction with the following components of VITAL-5G testbeds:

- the management system of 5G networks (*5G Slice management and inventory*);
- the NFV MANO platforms for onboarding and provisioning/management of Network Applications and vertical services (*Orchestrator catalogue* and *Orchestrator Lifecycle Manager – LCM*);
- the monitoring platforms for collection, storage and exposure of metrics and KPIs related to 5G network, edge/cloud computing infrastructure and vertical applications or services (*Monitoring*).

Depending on the capability of each testbed, the VITAL-5G Platform can also interact with additional management platforms and inventories (represented by the *Site mgt and inventory* box in the picture) to retrieve dynamically information about the hardware, IoT devices, physical functions, system settings, etc., configured in the testbed and its T&L facility. If this feature is not supported at the testbed level, the required information can be configured manually in the VITAL-5G Platform *Multi-site Inventory* by the administrator of the platform, via management interface.

The southbound interface of the VITAL-5G Platform is designed with a modular and plugin-based approach that deals with the diversity of capabilities and APIs related to the three testbeds while exposing a uniform layer towards the internal elements of the VITAL-5G Platform, as further detailed in section 5.3.5.

Figure 23: VITAL-5G Functional Architecture.

Table 15 provides the list of the VITAL-5G Platform functional elements, describing their functionalities and identifying their NBI and/or SBI¹⁶ where relevant. The objective of this table is to provide the reader with a high-level view of the features supported by each component in the global architecture, as foundation for the workflows defined in the next section to specify the interactions among the various elements. The internal details of each component and their software implementation are described in WP2 deliverables, in particular D2.2 [12] for the first release and D2.3 [1] for the second release of the VITAL-5G Platform (the reference sections are reported in the table).

Table 15: Functional elements of VITAL-5G platform.

VITAL-5G Platform Functional Element	Description	NBI	SBI
VITAL-5G Platform Web GUI	Provides the centralized web GUI for the secure access of logged users to all the VITAL-5G experimentation services. WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.1.	N.A.	N.A.
VITAL-5G Catalogue			
Network Applications Catalogue	Provides the catalogue of the Network Application packages and blueprints available in the VITAL-5G Catalogue, managing the synchronization with the	Onboarding, query and removal of Network	Onboarding, query and removal of VNF packages

¹⁶ Only NBI/SBI functions related to external interactions are reported, i.e., with VITAL-5G platform users on the NBI and with VITAL-5G testbeds on the SBI.

	<p>related VNF packages onboarded in each VITAL-5G testbed.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.2.</p>	<p>Application blueprints, packages or internal artefacts.</p>	<p>(associated to Network Applications) on VITAL-5G testbed NFVO catalogue.</p>
Services Catalogue	<p>Provides the catalogue of the VSBs and VSDs available in the VITAL-5G Catalogue, managing the synchronization with the related NSDs onboarded in each VITAL-5G testbed.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.2.</p>	<p>Onboarding, query and removal of VSBs (with related NSDs) and VSDs.</p>	<p>Onboarding, query and removal of NSDs (associated to VSBs) on NFVO catalogue.</p>
Experiment Catalogue	<p>Provides the catalogue of the experiment blueprints (ExpB) and descriptors (ExpD), including potential test scripts, available in the VITAL-5G Catalogue.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.2.</p>	<p>Onboarding, query and removal of ExpBs and ExpDs.</p>	<p>N/A. (ExpB/ExpD kept locally in VITAL-5G Platform).</p>
Network Application Validator	<p>Provides the functionalities to validate the format of a Network Application package and blueprint, verify its compatibility with the target testbed and, as option, test its instantiation in the target virtual environment.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.4.</p>	<p>Validate Network Application package. Test Network Application deployment.</p>	<p>Instantiation of VNF package.</p>
Network Application License Storage & Manager	<p>Provides a storage for the licenses associated to the Network Applications and the functionalities to validate them during the provisioning and runtime of the vertical services.</p> <p>Note: the implementation of this component is planned for D2.4. A preliminary software design is available in D2.1 [6], section 7.3.</p>	<p>Onboarding of license information.</p>	<p>N.A. (Internal component)</p>
VITAL-5G Portal			
Service Lifecycle Manager (LCM)	<p>Implements the procedures to instantiate, manage the runtime and terminate vertical services composed of one or more Network Application. At provisioning time, it performs the translation to the NFV-NS, coordinating its lifecycle management interacting with the NFVO at the VITAL-5G testbeds, activating the monitoring and selecting or creating the required 5G network slices. In the second release of the architecture, it has been enhanced to support the closed-loop automation of service lifecycle management. In particular, in case of AI-based decisions, it implements the execution step of the closed loop automation for application scaling or network slice updating. In case of decisions based on static rules encoded in the blueprints, it implements the analysis, decision and execution steps of the closed-loop.</p>	<p>Instantiate, scale, configure, terminate, retrieve vertical services.</p>	<p>Instantiate, scale, configure, terminate NFV-NSs. Select, create, configure, update 5G network slices.</p>

	WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.3.		
Monitoring Platform	<p>Provides a centralized monitoring platform for the collection, storage, retrieval and visualization of monitoring data, for network, computing infrastructure, and service KPIs. The collection of monitoring data can be activated and terminated dynamically, via configuration API. Monitoring data are pushed into the monitoring platform in a unified format and using per-metric topics by the monitoring systems available in each VITAL-5G testbed and by Network Applications with service monitoring capabilities. Once collected, the monitoring data are stored in the monitoring platform and they can be consumed by other components of the VITAL-5G Platform (e.g., Result Analytics and AI-based Diagnostic), Network Applications or external systems and users.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.9.</p>	<p>Configuration of monitoring data and topics.</p> <p>Query and visualization of monitoring data.</p>	<p>Collection of service and network KPIs from the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
Experiment Lifecycle Manager (LCM)	<p>Implements the procedures to execute an experiment over a running vertical service, coordinating the execution of test scripts and triggering the analysis of the experiment results.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.5.</p>	<p>Launch and terminate experiments.</p> <p>Retrieve experiments' status and results.</p>	<p>Execution of test scripts through day 2 configuration actions on NFV Orchestrators.</p>
Result Analytics	<p>Elaborates the monitoring data collected through the Monitoring Platform to compute and validate KPIs and experiment results, generating the related reports and graphs.</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.10.</p>	<p>Query experiment results.</p>	<p>N.A.</p>
AI-based Diagnostic	<p>Elaborates the monitoring data and the experiment results through AI-based techniques for advanced experiment diagnostics, generating the related reports (e.g., for anomaly detection or vector statistics).</p> <p>WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.11.</p>	<p>Query experiment diagnostics.</p>	<p>N.A.</p>
AI-based Service Lifecycle Management Logic	<p>Internal function of the VITAL-5G Platform that elaborates the monitoring data collected at the <i>Monitoring Platform</i> with the objective of detecting suboptimal or underperforming conditions and triggering accordingly the execution of a re-configuration action, e.g., a service scaling or migration, or a network slice updating. At the software development level, it has been implemented in the second release of the architecture updating the <i>AI-based Diagnostic</i> component, for the analysis and decision steps of the closed loop, and the Service Lifecycle Manager, for the execution step of the closed loop.</p>	<p>N.A. (Internal component)</p>	<p>N.A. (Internal component)</p>
VITAL-5G Management Backend			

Multi-site Inventory	Provides the inventory of systems, platforms, tools and IoT/T&L devices available in each site. It can be statically configured using its management interface or, as option, retrieve information from the underlying VITAL-5G testbeds, if they expose the related APIs. WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.8.	Query info on site configuration, e.g., IoT/T&L devices, platforms URLs, etc. Management interface for static configuration.	Query per-site configuration info (if supported).
Access Control	Provides the mechanisms for authorizing the access to the various services of the VITAL-5G platform. WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.6.	Management of user accounts. Authentication and tokens' management.	N.A.
Multi-site 5G Slice Manager and Inventory	Provides a centralized inventory for the 5G network slices configured in the various VITAL-5G testbed. In case of testbeds with programmable APIs for slice management, it mediates the creation, retrieval, configuration, update and termination of network slices. WP2 reference: D2.3 [1], section 2.7.	Query of 5G network slices and slice management capabilities. Creation, termination, configuration and update of network slices.	Query, creation, configuration, update and termination of 5G network slices, if supported on the given VITAL-5G testbed.

5.3.3 High-level Workflows and Procedures

This section describes the high-level workflows for the main procedures implemented by the VITAL-5G platform, as follows:

1. Onboarding of a new Network Application package
2. Instantiation of a Vertical Service
3. Termination of a Vertical Service
4. Creation, execution and monitoring of an experiment
5. Validation and automated diagnostic in VITAL-5G experiments
6. Data-driven, closed loop management for Vertical Service lifecycle automation

The workflows are presented as message sequence diagrams showing the interactions among the various functional elements of the VITAL-5G platform and, where needed, the VITAL-5G testbeds. In these workflows the usage of the VITAL-5G Platform Web GUI is assumed as the single entry-point for the system when an explicit command from the user is required. Alternatively, the users may access the platform directly through the REST APIs of its components.

The workflows 1., 2., and 4. were already presented in the previous version of the deliverable (D1.2 [5]) and, where needed, they have been slightly refined on the basis of the feedback received from WP2 implementation activities. The others (3., 5., and 6.) have been introduced as new in this deliverable.

The access control mechanisms are omitted in this representation of the workflows, for readability reasons. However, they are implicitly applied to evaluate the feasibility of each action requested by the user on the basis of user category and user group, as well as the use case associated to the requests, following the criteria

explained in Section 5.2.1. The access control requires initially the authentication of the user via username and password. The authentication procedure can be mediated through the user login at the GUI or performed directly via REST API interacting with the Access Control component and returns a token that is used to authorize all the following requests: (i) Network Application Package Onboarding, (ii) Vertical Service Instantiation and Termination and (iii) Experiment creation, execution and monitoring.

5.3.3.1 Network Application Package Onboarding

The workflow to onboard a new Network Application package in the VITAL-5G platform, making it available on the VITAL-5G Catalogue, is shown in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Workflow for Network Application Package onboarding.

The first step is the onboarding of the VNF package, which includes the software image and the VNFD of the Network Application software. From the GUI, the VNF package is onboarded directly on the target VITAL-5G testbed, in its NFVO catalogue. The information about URL and credentials to reach the NFVO can be obtained with a query (omitted in the picture) to the Multi-site Inventory. The NFVO returns the unique ID assigned locally to the VNF package.

The second step is the onboarding of the Network Application Package, which includes the reference to the VNF package ID returned previously by the NFVO, the Network Application blueprint and all the other elements presented in section 4.2. The Network Application package is onboarded through the GUI, which preliminarily validate its format with the Network Application Validator and then forwards it to the Network Application Catalogue. Here the package is unzipped and the Network Application blueprint is processed to verify its compatibility with the target site. In particular, the Network Application requirements in terms of IoT or T&L devices, 5G connectivity, and hardware requirements are compared with the testbed information retrieved from the Multi-site Inventory. The objective is to verify the presence of the required equipment and capabilities and, in case of testbeds with pre-configured network slices, the availability of slices matching the service profiles declared in the Network Application blueprint. The Network Application package is then stored in the Network Application catalogue and the assigned unique ID is returned. As an optional step, the Network Application catalogue may initiate an additional interaction with the Network Application Validator in order to validate, from a functional point of view, the correct instantiation of the Network Application in the target testbed. In this case, the Network Application Validator interacts with the NFVO to request a testing instantiation of the VNF associated to the Network Application and verify its status.

The final step of the workflow is required only for proprietary Network Applications with licenses managed through the VITAL-5G Platform. In this case, the Network Application developer can onboard the licenses granted for the usage of the Network Application to specific users or customers. The licenses are stored into the Network Application License Storage & Manager component (License Manager in the picture) where they will be verified during the Network Application provisioning phase.

The onboarding of VSB, ExpB and TCB follows a similar procedure, also mediated through the GUI, but involving the Service Catalogue and Experiment Catalogue respectively. The VSB includes also the related Network Service Descriptor, which is onboarded in the NFVO at the target testbed. Once onboarded, all the Network Application packages, VSB, ExpB and TCB can be visualized and downloaded through the GUI or retrieved with queries to the REST APIs of the VITAL-5G Catalogue.

5.3.3.2 Vertical Service Instantiation

The instantiation of a Vertical Service allows the service to be deployed in its target testbed, with the creation of all its Network Applications and the interconnection to the 5G network through the usage of network slices compatible with the 5G slice profile characteristics defined in the blueprints. Once instantiated, the user can visualize the information of the service on the VITAL-5G Portal GUI and obtain details about its Network Applications, assigned network slice, IP addresses, etc., which can be used to properly interact with the various service components.

Figure 25: Workflow for definition of a Vertical Service via VSD specification.

The initial step that the user needs to perform is the specification of the desired service characteristics, configuring the variable service parameters which are declared in the service blueprint. This step is facilitated by the GUI, which can show the configurable fields for the selected service. The result is a Vertical Service Descriptor (VSD) which is onboarded in the Service Catalogue of the VITAL-5G catalogue, as shown in Figure 25. Here a unique VSD identifier is generated and the VSD is stored in the internal database, returning the VSD ID which can be visualized by the user on the GUI.

Figure 26: Workflow for instantiation of a vertical service.

Once created, the VSD can be used as reference for the instantiation of vertical services matching those characteristics. The procedure is depicted in Figure 26, which highlights in red the updates from the previous workflow reported in D1.2 [5], introduced in order to enable automated closed-loop control actions for runtime service optimization.

Using the GUI, the user selects the target testbed and the desired VSD, and specifies some information for the given service instance, e.g., the UEs to be connected, configuration parameters for the applications, license keys for proprietary Network Applications if required. The GUI triggers the instantiation request to the Service LCM component, which updates its internal records and coordinates the entire instantiation procedure operating in asynchronous mode and returning immediately the unique identifier of the Vertical Service instance (VS_ID in the picture). This ID can be used anytime to query the Vertical Service LCM about service status and information, in order to follow the progress of the instantiation steps.

The instantiation steps can be summarized as follows:

- The Service LCM retrieves from the Service Catalogue of the VITAL-5G Catalogue the VSD and the related VSB, which is used to identify the required Network Applications. The Network Applications blueprints (NAB) are also retrieved from the Network Application Catalogue. Processing the blueprints and VSD information, the Service LCM determines the NSD of the NFV network service to be instantiated in the VITAL-5G testbed and the profiles of the required 5G network slices. Moreover, it determines if there are Network Applications that require the validation of their software licenses before proceeding with their deployment.
- In case of Network Application software licenses to be validated, the Service LCM issues requests to the License Manager of the VITAL-5G Catalogue to get the approval for the Network Application deployment, providing information on the license key of the user and the expected size of the Network Application, in case of usage-based licenses.
- The Service LCM queries the Multi-site Inventory to get details about slicing capabilities and NFVO deployed at the VITAL-5G testbed where the service will be instantiated. This information is used to properly interact with the target testbed.
- The Service LCM interacts with the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory to request the configuration of the network slices, providing slice profiles and UEs (i.e., through their IMSI). The actual configuration of the slice depends on the testbed capabilities. If network slices can be managed dynamically and in a programmable manner, they are created and configured on-demand through the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory. If the testbed requires a static and manual management of the network slices, they must be created from the testbed administrator in advance and stored in the inventory. In this case, at this stage the network slices already exist, and they are just selected by the Multi-Site 5G Slice Inventory on the basis of the requested service profiles and configured with the UEs.
- Once the 5G network slices are in place and properly configured, the Service LCM interacts with the NFVO at the testbed to request the provisioning and configuration of the NFV network service that includes the Network Applications. Depending on the testbed information collected from the Multi-site Inventory, the Service LCM may indicate particular networks configured on the testbed to interconnect the service to the most suitable data networks available in the target infrastructure (e.g., to guarantee the external access, or the connection to local data networks placed at the edge, etc.). After the successful instantiation of the NFV network service, the Service LCM gathers all the details of the service and its Network Applications (e.g., assigned IDs and IP addresses) and updates its internal record.
- Depending on the type of Network Application software licenses, the Service LCM may need to notify the License Manager about the successful instantiation, so that it can update its internal counters (e.g., number of running Network Application instances for a given user).
- The Service LCM interacts with the Monitoring Platform component to activate the collection of the metrics and KPIs associated to the vertical service, as declared in the service and Network Applications' blueprints, specifying the topics where the monitoring data will be published.

At the end of this workflow, with the second release of the architecture, a further step (in red in the picture) has been added to activate the closed-loop control at service runtime. The service automation actions allow to: (i) modify the 5G network slices associated to the service; (ii) trigger network service scaling procedures to accommodate more resources for the VNF/CNFs of the network application; (iii) change service placement

decisions and migrate the application components in different computing nodes. These actions can be triggered on the basis of AI-driven decisions taken at the Diagnostic component or according to static threshold-based rules declared in the VSB (see section 4.3). In the final block of the service instantiation workflows, all these triggers are configured so that they can be properly activated during the service runtime. In details, the actions based on diagnostic event triggers are configured by the *Service LCM* into the *Results Analytics* module specifying the type of event and the action which shall be triggered upon occurrence. In a similar manner, threshold-based triggers are configured in the Service LCM itself to start the observation of the target metrics and set the thresholds and actions to be executed.

At the end of the procedure, the Vertical Service and all its Network Applications are properly instantiated, configured and running. Moreover, the collection of the monitoring data is in place. The user can visualize the details of the service using the GUI, as shown in Figure 27. Such information can then be used to connect to the various Network Applications, request LCM actions on the running service (e.g., scaling) or retrieve monitoring data with specific filters using the interface of the Monitoring Platform.

Figure 27: Workflow for retrieval of Vertical Service information.

5.3.3.3 Vertical Service Termination

The vertical service termination workflow is depicted in Figure 28. This workflow is triggered upon user request, through the GUI which subsequently forwards the request to the Vertical Service LCM. As depicted in the workflow, it processes this request and interacts with the rest of the platform modules for: (i) de-allocation of the automated control-loop triggers; (ii) de-allocation of the monitored configured metrics through the Service

and Network Monitoring; (iii) termination/de-allocation of the network services and network slices associated to the service; (iv) Update licensing usage and release of VSBs/VSDs.

Figure 28: Vertical Service termination workflow.

5.3.3.4 Experiment Creation, Execution and Monitoring

The updated version of the integration workflow for the creation, execution and monitoring of experiments is represented in Figure 29, highlighting in red the changes from the previous version reported in D1.2 [5]. As for the provisioning of vertical services, there is an initial phase where the user can specify the parameters of the experiment, through the creation of an Experiment Descriptor (ExpD), which will provide the values for the variable parameters defined in the Experiment Blueprint (ExpB). The ExpD is onboarded in the Experiment Catalogue of the VITAL-5G Catalogue, where it is stored in the internal database.

Then, the user can proceed with the request for the creation of the experiment, specifying its ExpD ID, the ID of the Vertical Service (previously instantiated) associated to the experiment and the configuration parameters for tuning the conditions of the testing environment and the test execution. The request is forwarded from the GUI to the Experiment Lifecycle Manager (LCM) component, which is in charge of coordinating all the procedures related to the experiment lifecycle. It initially retrieves ExpB and ExpD from the catalogue and locks the vertical service on the Service LCM. It should be noted that only a single experiment is permitted over a vertical service instance, in order to avoid overlapping test executions; as a consequence, if the vertical service is already locked the experiment is rejected.

If the experiment can be accepted, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager creates a new entry in its record and returns the unique experiment ID (Exp_ID in the picture). This ID can be used to query the status and the progress of the experiment during its entire lifecycle, as well as request actions related to its testing procedure. In particular, in order to start the experiment, the user needs to launch an experiment execution. As option, the user may provide configuration parameters that would override the ones set during the experiment creation.

This would allow the running of different experiment versions with changed configuration settings, enabling results to be compared.

Figure 29: Workflow for creation, execution, and monitoring of experiments.

The launch of the experiment execution triggers a number of actions under the coordination of the Experiment Lifecycle Manager. Some of these operations (configuration of Network Applications, execution of the test scripts

and cleaning operations) can be automatically performed by exploiting the mechanisms offered by OSM (Day2 actions), the NFVO used at the VITAL-5G testbeds. If one of these actions fails, a roll-back procedure is performed.

In particular, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager executes the following actions:

- Configuration of KPIs on the Monitoring Platform, activating the collection of the KPIs that will be computed during the execution of the experiments and published on a given set of topics.
- Configuration of the Network Applications with the testing parameters if the reference of a config Day2 action is specified in the ExpB/ExpD along with the input parameters.
- Configuration of the Results Analytics notifying the launch of the experiment execution and triggering the computation of the KPIs.

Once the configuration is completed, the VITAL-5G Platform is ready to process the monitoring data and elaborate the KPIs. At this stage, the user can connect to the Network Applications, execute scripts in manual mode, operate on the user equipment, etc., as required by the experiment execution. The scripts execution can be automated by the platform if the ExpB/ExpB contains the definition of the corresponding Day2 OSM Action. In the meantime, the monitoring data from all the configured sources at the VITAL-5G testbed (i.e., for 5G network, infrastructure, and service metrics) are published in the Monitoring Platform and consumed by the Result Analytics, which elaborates the KPIs following the criteria defined in the experiment blueprint. Such KPIs are in turn published in the Monitoring Platform. The collected metrics and KPIs are made available through the GUI, with graphs. Alternatively, the user may retrieve them using the programmable interface of the Monitoring Platform.

When the experiment execution is terminated, if the execution of the experiment is performed in manual-mode (not automatically executed by the platform) the user sends a request to stop it. Then, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager interacts with the Results Analytic component to notify the end of the experiment execution and to trigger the validation of the experiment results, on the basis of the target KPIs values defined in the ExpD. An experiment result report is generated and made available for the user. In this phase, if the diagnostic feature is enabled, the Results Analytic can further interact with the AI-based Diagnostic component to trigger the performance diagnosis algorithms. When the validation phase is concluded, the Experiment Lifecycle Manager cleans up all the testing configuration previously applied to the Network Applications through the clean Day2 action optionally specified in the ExpB/ExpB and updates the internal experiment record.

It should be noted that after the conclusion of an experiment execution, the user can launch another one over the same experiment. This can be repeated until the experiment as a whole is terminated by the user, triggering the release of the lock on the associated vertical service.

5.3.3.5 Experiment Validation and Automated Diagnostics

The second release of the VITAL-5G platform introduces the final version of Results Analysis and AI Diagnostic components, enabling new capabilities of the platform. One of these new capabilities is the generation and validation of high level KPIs in order to observe the performance of an examined service and validate its correct operation. This functionality is performed following the workflow seen in Figure 30.

Figure 30: Results Analysis workflow.

This component utilizes inputs from the Monitoring Platform and the Service LCM, for metric ingestion and management respectively, and generates output in the form of KPI threshold events sent to the Service LCM as input for the Data-driven Closed-loop Management mechanism, as well as reports to be viewed by the experimenter.

The second one of the new capabilities is the AI-based Diagnostic process. This functionality provides the platform with a mechanism that observes the behavior of the examined services for anomalies and performance degradations and also tries to locate the root cause behind them. These operations are performed following the workflow shown in Figure 31.

Figure 31: AI Diagnostics workflow.

This component utilizes inputs from the Monitoring Platform and the Result Analysis, for metric and KPI ingestion and management respectively, and generates output in the form of Diagnostic events sent to the LCM as input for the Data-driven Closed-loop Management mechanism. After the termination of the diagnostic process, the generated report for the service will also be enriched with the results of the diagnostic process automatically, through the Result Analysis component.

5.3.3.6 Data-driven Closed-loop Management of Vertical Service Lifecycle Automation

The VITAL-5G Platform aims to provide automated mechanisms for service optimization in order to support enhanced and dynamic allocation of 5G slices and computing resources associated to Network Applications and Vertical Services. In particular, the target is to support three different types of optimization actions to be triggered at runtime due to a service diagnostic event or to a pre-defined condition detected via service monitoring:

- **Network Slice modification:** VITAL-5G Vertical Service Instances are associated with a 5G slice, which is allocated at instantiation time using the 5G slice profile characteristics described in the VSB (see section

4.3). The network slice modification actions change the 5G slice profile characteristics (i.e., latency, uplink/downlink data rates, etc.) at runtime.

- **Network Service scaling:** At the instantiation time, the Network Applications’ functions are dimensioned in terms of computing and storage resources using static policies which map service attributes to a given NFV network service deployment flavors and instantiation levels. Network service scaling actions allows to increase the resources assigned to the Network Applications or the duplicate their instances at runtime, to better adapt the service performance to dynamic service demands and context conditions.
- **Service Migration:** Service Migration actions aim to improve service performance by moving Network Applications’ components (virtual machines or containers) to better fit the service requirements, for instance moving from the cloud to the edge segment of the network.

In VITAL-5G we consider the following triggers for closed-loop automation, which upon occurrence shall set in motion the workflows executing each type of action:

- **Trigger based on metric thresholds:** This kind of trigger is based on setting a pre-defined logical condition on some of the metrics collected for the service. When the logical condition is met, the action associated is automatically fired. This type of rule is statically defined in the VSB.
- **Trigger based on diagnostic events:** This trigger associates an action to a specific service diagnostic event. These diagnostic events are generated by the *Results Analytics and Diagnostic* modules, which adopt AI/ML techniques to detect underperformances or bottlenecks, at the mobile network connectivity or computing resources level, on the basis of service characteristics and collected monitoring information. In particular in VITAL-5G we consider underperformance events of the following types:

Figure 32 shows the workflows that originates the two types of triggers. In the first case, the monitoring data are processed directly by the Service LCM that, when recognizes the occurrence of the logical condition, starts the corresponding action. In the second case, the diagnostic event is fired by the Results Analytics module and further processed by the Service LCM that, as in the previous case, is responsible for starting and coordinating the execution of the corresponding action.

Figure 32: Closed- loop control action triggers.

The service scaling and migration action are executed interacting with the NFVO of the target testbed, while the slice modification is requested to the Multi-site 5G Slice Manager and Inventory specifying the new slice profile

characteristics (see Figure 33). Here a different slice is selected and activated, or, in case of testbed with the capability of creating/updating network slices, a new requests is sent to the local Slice Management agent.

Figure 33: Closed-control loop action specific workflows.

5.3.4 North-bound Interface

The design of the VITAL-5G Platform architecture follows the principles of a Service Based Architecture, with all its functional elements exposing open interfaces to provide access to their services and functionalities. All the consumers of these services can simply implement the client-side of such interfaces. Some VITAL-5G Platform functional elements, at the VITAL-5G Catalogue and VITAL-5G Portal, provide interfaces that are consumed by the platform users (experimenters, Network Application developers, service providers), as shown in Figure 34 and Figure 35. Moreover, the components of the VITAL-5G Platform Management backend offers interfaces for the platform administrators to configure and manage the VITAL-5G system (Figure 36). The whole set of these interfaces constitutes the VITAL-5G Platform North-bound interface (NBI).

Figure 34: VITAL-5G Catalogue North-bound Interface.

Figure 35: VITAL-5G Portal North-bound Interface.

Figure 36: VITAL-5G Platform Management North-bound Interface.

The implementation of the VITAL-5G Platform NBI in WP2 has adopted REST APIs based on HTTP protocol and messages encoded in JSON language; however different implementations based on different protocols are also possible (e.g., based on protocol buffers). All the requests received on the NBI must be authenticated and authorized, on the basis of the user’s profile and associated groups. The access to the NBI can be performed in a programmable manner or through the mediation of the VITAL-5G Platform GUI. In the former case, the user will need to compose the message and trigger the request. For example, assuming the adoption of REST APIs, the requests can be issued via REST clients embedded in users’ applications or via stand-alone REST clients (e.g., Postman¹⁷, Curl¹⁸ ...). In the latter case, the user will interact with the GUI, which will act as REST client and it will be responsible for the composition of the messages, the issue of the request and the reception and processing of the response.

Table 16 summarizes the NBI exposed by the relevant VITAL-5G Platform components. It should be noted that some elements provide only internal interfaces not belonging to the NBI (i.e., interfaces consumed only by other elements of the platform) and, consequently, they are not mentioned in the table. The implemented OpenAPI are specified in WP2 deliverables and they are available in the public Gitlab software repository. The table below reports the related references.

¹⁷ <https://www.postman.com/>

¹⁸ <https://curl.se/>

Table 16: North-bound Interface of VITAL-5G Platform

Functional component	Interface	Exposed operations	Implemented OpenAPI
Network Application Catalogue	N_Cat: management of Network Application packages and Network Application blueprints.	Onboard/Remove/Download Network Application package Download Network Application package artefacts Download VNF Package associated to a Network Application package Get Network Application blueprint Get VNFD associated to a Network Application package Get (filtered) lists of Network Application blueprints	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.2.4 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/tree/main/API
Service Catalogue	S_Cat: management of Vertical Service Blueprints (VSB) and Vertical Service Descriptors (VSD)	Onboard/Remove/Update/Get VSB Onboard/Remove/Update/Get NSD associated to a VSB Onboard/Remove/Update/Get translation rules to map VSBs and NSDs Onboard/Remove/Update/Get VSD Get (filtered) list of VSBs and VSDs	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.2.4 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/tree/main/API
Experiment Catalogue	E_Cat: management of Experiment Blueprints (ExpB) and Experiment Descriptors (ExpD)	Onboard/Remove/Update/Get ExpB Onboard/Remove/Update/Get ExpD Get (filtered) list of ExpBs and ExpDs	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.2.4 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/OpenOnlineRepository/-/tree/main/API
Network Application Validator	N_Val: validation of blueprints	Validate Network Application blueprints	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.4.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/blueprint-validator/-/tree/main/API
Network Application License Storage & Manager	NL_Mgt: management of licenses assigned to VITAL-5G users	Onboard/Remove/Modify/Get software license	N.A. - Implementation planned for D2.4. Preliminary specification of abstract interface available in D2.1 [6], section 7.3
Multi-site Inventory	Site_Mgt: management of devices and NFVO in VITAL-5G testbeds	Onboard/Remove/Update device in VITAL-5G testbed (admin action) Get device information Get (filtered) list of devices available in VITAL-5G testbeds	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.8.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/multi-site-inventory/-/tree/main/API

		Configure/Remove/Update NFVO information in VITAL-5G testbed (admin action) Get NFVO information	
Multi-site 5G Slice Manager & Inventory	Slice_Mgt: management of network slices in VITAL-5G testbeds	Onboard/Remove/Update network slice in VITAL-5G testbed (admin action) Get network slice information Get (filtered) list of network slices available in VITAL-5G testbeds Attach/Detach UE to/from a network slice (admin action)	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.7.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/multi-site-5g-slice-inventory
Service LCM	VS_Mgt: management of vertical service lifecycle	Instantiate/ScaleIn/ScaleOut/Configure/Terminate Vertical Service Instance Get (filtered) list of Vertical Service instances Get Vertical Service instance information Get Network Application instance information	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.3.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/service-lcm/-/tree/main/API
Experiment LCM	Exp_Mgt: management of experiments	Create/Remove experiment Launch/Stop experiment execution Get experiment information and results Get (filtered) list of experiment	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.5.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/experiment-lcm/-/tree/main/API
Monitoring Platform	Mon: retrieval of monitoring data and configuration of monitoring jobs	Read collected metrics and KPIs, on a per service and per experiment basis Configure new metrics and KPIs to be collected	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.9.3
Result Analytics	Res_Mgt: retrieval of experiment results	Get experiment results Get experiment execution results	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.10.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/results-analytics/-/tree/main/API
AI-based Diagnostics	Diag_Mgt: retrieval of diagnostic results	Get diagnostic events for a given service	D2.3 [1], sect. 2.11.3 https://gitlab.com/vital-5g/VITAL-5G_Platform/ai-based-diagnostics/-/tree/main/API

5.3.5 Unified South-bound Interface towards VITAL-5G Testbeds

The South-bound Interface (SBI) of the VITAL-5G Platform enables its interaction with the VITAL-5G Testbeds, to support the following types of functionalities:

- Interaction with 5G Slice Management system, for the selection and/or creation, management and configuration of 5G network slices over the shared 5G infrastructure available in the VITAL-5G testbeds;
- Interaction with NFV MANO system, for the onboarding, provisioning, management and configuration of Network Applications and Vertical Services to be deployed as VNFs and NFV Network Services in the virtual computing infrastructures offered by the VITAL-5G Testbeds;

- Interaction with the local monitoring system of each VITAL-5G testbed, for the centralized collection of monitoring metrics from the 5G infrastructure, addressing both the 5G network performance or load and the usage of computing/storage resources of the virtual computing nodes where the Network Apps are running.

Moreover, an additional interface may be provided as optional, to collect information related to the hardware devices (e.g., IoT sensors, AGVs, video cameras) installed in the T&L facilities at the VITAL-5G testbeds, with all the details required to properly interact with them. This interface can be considered as optional since, by default, the testbed administrator will configure the devices manually in the Multi-site Inventory using its NBI. However, in case of testbeds supporting open interfaces to access the inventory of the devices available there, automatic device discovery procedures can be implemented at the Multi-site Inventory to reduce the number of manual configurations required by the administrators.

Each VITAL-5G testbed implements its own NFV MANO orchestrators, slice management systems and monitoring platforms, each of them exposing their own interfaces. At the VITAL-5G Platform level, a unified SBI presents an abstract and common interface towards all the platform components that need to interact with the VITAL-5G testbed. Then, for each testbed, specific drivers (implemented in the form of per-testbed plugins in the context of WP3) perform the adaptation and translation towards the testbed-specific protocols and messages, as shown in Figure 37. From the perspective of the VITAL-5G Platform components, all the VITAL-5G testbeds thus appear as black boxes exposing a unified interface through their specialized plugins, independently of the variety of tools, platforms and systems implementing the actual functionalities.

Figure 37: VITAL-5G Platform South-bound Interface.

Figure 37 represents the interfaces defined on the unified SBI, indicating their consumers on the VITAL-5G Platform side. The testbed-specific sub-systems represented in the picture (i.e., Monitoring System, Slice Management System, NFV MANO System and their internal components) are provided just as examples; the decisions on the internal structure are delegated to each testbed, which can select their own solutions.

Table 17 provides the list of the interfaces that must be exposed by each sub-system of a VITAL-5G testbed, with the related functionalities. Where possible, the design of the interfaces adopts standards or makes use of the APIs offered by components deployed in all the three testbeds. This reduces the need of implementing new plugins at each testbed level and simplifies the potential adoption of the VITAL-5G Platform on top of other

testbeds, even beyond the duration of the project. For example, the SBI for the interaction between the VITAL-5G Platform and the NFV MANO systems at the VITAL-5G testbed is based on the ETSI NFV SOL 005 standard [13], which is implemented by the ETSI OSM orchestrator used in all the testbeds. For this reason, the implementation of the orchestration drivers has not been necessary. Instead, the monitoring and the network management systems of the three testbeds are based on completely different deployments and provides different interfaces, thus requiring the implementation of dedicated drivers.

The OpenAPI and the publish/subscribe protocol messages at the unified SBI have been defined in WP2 and documented in D2.3 [1]. For monitoring, REST APIs are used to request the activation and termination of monitoring data collection processes at the local VITAL-5G testbeds. Then, the data collected on each testbed are translated in the common format and published in the centralized Monitoring Platform using publish/subscribe ZeroMQ mechanisms (see D2.3 [1], section 2.9.3). For network slice management, the interaction is based entirely on REST APIs (see D2.3 [1], section 2.7.3). The implementation of the respective drivers for each site has been addressed in WP3 and further details are available in D3.2 [3], section 6.

Table 17: VITAL-5G Platform South-bound Interface.

VITAL-5G Testbed sub-system	Interface	VITAL-5G Platform Component	Main functionalities
NFV MANO System	Nfvo_cat: management of VNF packages and Network Service Descriptors.	Network Application Catalogue Service Catalogue	Onboard/Remove/Download VNF packages Get VNF package info Get VNFD Onboard/Remove/Get NSD Get (filtered) list of VNF package info Get (filtered) list of NSD
	Nfvo_lcm: Management of the lifecycle of NFV Network Services and configuration of their virtual functions	Service LCM Experiment LCM	Instantiate/ScaleIn/ScaleOut/Configure/Terminate NFV Network Service Instance Configure VNF instance Get (filtered) list of NFV Network Service instances Get Network Service instance information Get VNF instance information
5G Slice Management System	Slice_conf	Multi-site 5G Slice Manager & Inventory	Get (filtered) list of network slice instance Get network slice instance information Attach/Detach UEs to/from a network slice instance Create/Remove/Update network slice instance (optional, valid for testbed where on-demand network slice provisioning is supported)
Monitoring System	Mon_conf	Monitoring Platform (acting as consumer)	Create and remove topics for monitoring metrics and activate/terminate data collection processes for network and service KPIs.

	Mon_pub	Monitoring Platform (acting as provider)	Publish network and service metrics with given topics
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6 VITAL-5G Platform Evolution: Architectural Features introduced in 2nd Release

This section describes the new architectural features introduced with the second release of the VITAL-5G platform.

6.1 Access Control

The Access Control component in the VITAL-5G Platform is responsible for securely managing user information, credentials, roles, and groups. It implements authentication and authorization for other components by utilizing Keycloak, an Identity and Access Management platform.

The authentication process uses Role Based Access Control (RBAC), where registered users can obtain a time-limited access token to specific resources. The access token is accompanied by a refresh token, which allows users to renew their access once the token expires. The access token also includes a list of project use-cases for added granularity in access control.

The Access Control component is configured through a realm called "vital5g", which manages the set of users, credentials, roles, and groups. Each VITAL-5G Platform component (e.g., Network Application Catalogue, Service LCM, etc.) is registered as a client with Keycloak¹⁹ to validate access tokens and retrieve information about the token owner (roles and groups). More details about the implementation are available in D2.3 [1], section 2.6.

6.2 Network and Service Monitoring

The main goal of the VITAL-5G centralized Monitoring Platform is to perform real-time network and service monitoring by collecting the data that reflects on the network and service performance within the VITAL-5G testbeds, and making that data available to other platform components that are responsible for analytics. This particular software component is designed as a centralized module within the VITAL-5G Platform, which interacts with other platform components and with the 5G testbeds, thereby leveraging on the combination of pub/sub mechanism for real-time data collection and REST-based communication with other components for the purpose of configuring the data topics.

Thus, the contribution of this component to the VITAL-5G architecture is two-fold:

- It collects performance metrics such as network, service, platform, and infrastructure, in real-time with the predefined frequency (depending on the metric type), by interfacing with the distributed 5G testbeds.
- Once collected, it exposes the performance metrics to the other VITAL-5G platform components such as AI-based Diagnostics and Result Analytics, to perform advanced analysis of Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and to trigger various life-cycle management operations on the vertical services in order to improve service performance.

This platform component is heavily involved in the following experimentation phases: Vertical Service Instantiation, and Experiment execution. During the instantiation phase, it involves the interaction with the Service Lifecycle Manager, which triggers the creation of various topics that will be used for collecting data from network, service, infrastructure, and platform, during the experiment runtime. Once the topics are created, the centralized monitoring platform is interfacing with the corresponding 5G testbed using southbound interface communication, and configures the topics that local monitoring system (running on the 5G testbed) needs to use to publish measurements.

Concerning the real-time metric influx, it is collected either real-time or in a bulk format. Afterwards, during the experiment runtime, the centralized monitoring platform is in charge of monitoring the performance of ongoing experiments, as it enables diagnostic elements such as AI-enabled diagnostics and Result Analytics to detect

¹⁹ <https://www.keycloak.org/>

anomalies and changes in service and network quality, and to correspondingly act upon those detected events. Finally, the centralized monitoring platform interacts with the Portal Web GUI component for the purpose of showing in real-time the graphical overview of collected metrics.

The detailed architecture of the centralized monitoring platform, the details about the actual implementation status and all features, as well as the interaction of monitoring platform with the other VITAL-5G architecture elements, are presented in the deliverable D2.3 [1], section 2.9.

6.3 Network Slicing Management

The Network Slicing Management is an important feature of the VITAL-5G architecture, which is delivered in the form of the Multi-site 5G Slice Management and Inventory (Slice inventory in the following) component, i.e., a management backend software component that performs real-time management of network slices in all three trial sites (Antwerp, Galati, and Athens), more precisely, all three 5G testbeds. Given the importance of selecting and configuring the network slice for vertical service runtime in the 5G ecosystem, this component is essential for communicating the Quality of Service (QoS) needs of vertical services during experiment creation to the 5G testbeds that further deploy and make available the required 5G Radio and Core resources, and for life-cycle management of the deployed 5G slices.

With reference to the overall VITAL-5G architecture, the Slice inventory component belongs to the VITAL-5G Portal (within the VITAL-5G Platform), and it interacts with other internal components such as Service Lifecycle Manager and the centralized Monitoring Platform, as well as the external components such as slice management plugins on each of the testbeds (southbound interaction with testbeds). The overall functionality of the Network Slicing Management combines the following features:

- *Real-time overview of 5G slices in VITAL-5G testbeds:* Slice inventory component of the VITAL-5G architecture is in charge of storing and updating the information about the available 5G slices in the 5G testbeds. The stored information includes the following: i) lists of available slices per testbed, ii) slice profile characteristics, and iii) subscribers attached to a particular slice (if available on the testbed). If 5G slices are pre-configured and static, the information is stored only once and not queried during the vertical service runtime. However, if dynamic slice provisioning is supported by the 5G testbed, then the up-to-date information about slices is reported by the corresponding 5G testbed anytime the change in configuration and performance happens. This slice-related information is essential for optimal slice selection during Experiment Creation and Vertical Service Instantiation, as Slice inventory component needs to consult the records before applying the slice selection algorithm. The stored information includes the lists of available slices per testbed, their profile characteristics, and subscribers attached to a particular slice (if available on the testbed).
- *Dynamic provisioning and life-cycle management of 5G slices:* This feature corresponds to capabilities of Slice inventory module to provision slices, attach UEs to the selected slices, and reconfigure the existing slices based on the current and targeting performance levels. These operations are triggered by Slice inventory through sending corresponding management requests towards slice management agents on each of the VITAL-5G testbeds. The network performance of all slices during service runtime is collected from the other VITAL-5G software component, i.e., centralized Monitoring Platform, and this information is used by Slice inventory to further optimize the life-cycle management operations.
- *Optimal 5G slice selection during Vertical Service Instantiation procedure:* During the experiment creation, a vertical service description comes with the set of requirements that this particular vertical service demands in order to properly work in the 5G-based T&L ecosystem. These requirements are taken into account by Slice inventory module when making decision about the particular slice that will be used during vertical service operation. The decision is further communicated with the corresponding 5G testbed to whom the selected slice belongs, after which the further configuration and UE attachment to the slice is the responsibility of the 5G testbed. Thus, Slice inventory component is in charge of

selecting the optimal slice for the vertical service and Network Application deployment, mapping the vertical service and Network Application requirements to the capabilities of the available 5G slices.

The detailed architecture of the Slice inventory component, the details about the actual implementation and status of the Network Slicing Management features, as well as the interaction of Slice inventory module with the other VITAL-5G architecture elements, are presented in the deliverable D2.3 [1], section 2.7.

6.4 AI/ML Techniques and Data-driven Analysis applied in VITAL-5G Platform

The VITAL-5G Platform incorporates -among others- advanced analytics, as well as AI/ML functionalities. Their purpose is two-fold:

- To help aggregate, interpret/export statistics and formula results, offering a report of the related information and KPIs about the network, service, platform, and infrastructure and experiments/trials conducted.
- To analyze the above-mentioned further and extract insights that can then
 - a) be used by experimenters for improving the results of future experiments and
 - b) be utilized by other platform components.

More specifically, while some statistics are provided in dashboards real-time in the monitoring component, all AI/ML and Data-driven functionalities of the VITAL-5G Platform (such functionalities are found also in selected Network Applications) reside in the Results Analysis and Diagnostics components described in more detail in section 6.7.

More specifically, the Result Analysis component:

- Performs statistical analysis of these metrics during the process of a service or experiment: These statistics refer to the selected KPIs per case, such as CPU load, where average, minimum, maximum, percentile values can be calculated.
- Applies formula transformations: indicatively adding or subtracting KPIs to generate new high-level KPIs and then export the previous statistics.

This way, a KPI validation process can take place, i.e., whether the preset criteria for the selected KPIs are met.

On the other hand, the AI diagnostics component utilizes the aforementioned information collected, as well as the new high-level KPIs, and performs further analysis based on anomaly detection techniques. Anomaly detection (also known as outlier detection) techniques are a type of unsupervised methods, i.e., that do not require prior knowledge of the ground truth such as label or target value. Their purpose is to “learn” the underlying patterns that reflect “normal”/healthy operations and thus detect cases of anomalies. This would ultimately aid decision-making based on the results and possibly trigger corrective actions when fed to the Service LCM component (see section 6.5). The current implementation of such anomaly detection approach is described in more detail in D2.3 [1] and is based on Self-Organizing Maps (SOM).

6.5 Closed-loop Reactions for Automated Lifecycle Management

The second version of VITAL-5G Platform has introduced closed-loop mechanisms to autonomously react in case of service degradation or network underperformances, with new workflows (described in section 5.3.3.6) that enforce service scaling and slice modifications at the VITAL-5G Platform level upon automatic triggers without requiring any manual intervention from the user. These triggers are defined during the vertical service design and specified in the Vertical Service Blueprint. Accordingly, the VITAL-5G Platform components for service management execute the related LCM actions whenever a triggering condition is recognized. There are two main types of triggers:

- Diagnostic Event trigger: These triggers enable automated actions upon detection of specific diagnostics events. We target two diagnostic events which signal underperformance in the computing and in the networking domain: (i) COMPUTING_UNDERPERFORMANCE, which is triggered when the Results

Analytics detects that the computing resources allocated for the service might become a limitation given the current service constraints (e.g. more CPUs need to be allocated for the service to process the amount of IoT data coming from the devices); (ii) 5G_SLICE_UNDERPERFORMANCE, used to signal that the allocated 5G slice profile might be not fitted for the service given the current service constraints.

- Metric event triggers: This trigger enables the automated reaction upon verification of a certain logical condition of a service or infrastructure metric.

It is worth highlighting that, in case of failures at the infrastructure level affecting either the computing or the network slice domain, this mechanism complements the preventive measurements taken at the testbed level with its internal failover mechanisms. This means that in case of a failure, this is addressed immediately at each testbed, e.g., relying on the high-availability mechanisms of the edge/cloud infrastructure or the path recovery procedures at the transport level. Just in case of persisting failures, they are scaled up to the VITAL-5G platform.

6.6 Automated Configuration and Testing Execution

The VITAL-5G platform, in its second release, provides mechanisms to automatically create, configure, execute and terminate testing procedures over Network Applications running on the VITAL-5G testbeds, by leveraging the usage of Day2 Actions provided by OSM. The experimentation and testing procedures are coordinated by the Experiment Lifecycle Manager, following the directives specified in the experiment and testcase blueprints (ExpB and TCB) loaded by the users. Experiments can be launched several times with different configurations, which are declared in the Experiment Descriptor (ExpD) assigning specific values to the variable parameters defined in the ExpB. This approach allows the user to compare the performance of the same Network Applications, when running with different settings. In order to further facilitate the execution and the replicability of some tests, the OSM Day2 routines are adopted to launch automatically some configurable scripts and commands on the running applications. Their role in the experiment execution workflow is explained in the following:

- The experiment configuration relies on a set of blueprints and descriptors (ExpB, ExpD and TCB) to be onboarded on the VITAL-5G Catalogue. TCB can define a set of configuration actions or commands, implemented through OSM Day2 routines, together with their variable parameters. The user (through the VITAL-5G GUI) can start an experiment over a running Vertical Service and launch the execution of automated test cases selecting a TCB, the target application and setting the values of the configuration parameters. If the TCB specifies a Day2 Configuration Action, this will be automatically triggered with the selected settings. Alternatively, the configuration of the Network Application and the launch of commands can be done manually if the TCB does not specify a configuration Day2 action. This second option is maintained to give the maximum flexibility in the execution of the trials.
- Once the experiment is configured, the Service Lifecycle Manager receives the request to temporarily lock the Network Application in order to prevent lifecycle operations that may be triggered by external entities (e.g., a request to stop the service) and that would alter the correct execution of the experiment. The user now (through the VITAL-5G Portal) can run the experiment scripts that implement the algorithms/routines to be monitored by the platform. This, like the experiment configuration procedure, can be automated from the Experiment Lifecycle Manager just specifying an Experiment Execution Day2 Action on the TCB, along with the input parameters to be used. Before starting the actual execution of the experiment, the Result Analytics and the Monitoring Platform components are properly notified, so that they can start monitoring the performances of the service/testbed.
- The termination of an experiment includes also a set of operations to reset or clear the Network Application to roll its status back. This ensure that the Experiment Lifecycle Manager does not alter the lifecycle of an application as well as the possibility to execute multiple experiments starting from a clean situation. Optionally, this can be automated by the Experiment Lifecycle Manager specifying leveraging the OSM Day2 Action like the configuration and execution procedures.
- After the conclusion of the experiment, the Service Lifecycle Manager is notified about its termination, so that it can release the lock on the application and make it available for further experiments.

6.7 Automated Results Analysis and Diagnostics

In this 2nd release of the VITAL-5G platform, the Result Analysis and AI Diagnostics components have been introduced, along with the required functionalities from the Monitoring platform component to support them.

The Result Analysis component is responsible for collecting the metrics generated during the operation of a service or experiment by a vertical, performing statistical analysis of these metrics, and finally applying high level formulas to generate defined KPIs. These KPIs become available to the vertical in order to provide an image of the performance of the service under examination, in the form of a report. To accomplish that, the Result Analytics component uses the platform's Monitoring component for the ingestion of metrics and the Service LCM handles the management of the requested executions. Additionally, this component provides an output, KPI performance triggers, to the Service LCM as part of the closed-loop automated control of the services and experiments. The internal implementation of this component, along with analytical capabilities and its interfaces, are described in more detail in Deliverable D2.3 [1], section 2.10.

The AI Diagnostics component is responsible for retrieving information regarding an executed service or experiment as well as all the generated metrics and high level KPIs. The metrics and KPIs, after being correlated spatiotemporally, will be semantically mapped to other collected information, like topological and deployment information, in order to be examined as part of the diagnostic process. To accomplish that, the AI Diagnostic component uses the platform's Monitoring component for the ingestion of metrics and KPIs, the Service Catalogue for retrieval of the service's information and finally the Result Analysis component for the operational management of the diagnosed executions. Furthermore, this component produces as output, generated from detected anomalies or performance degradations, requests to trigger the Service LCM as part of the closed-loop automated control of services and experiments. The internal implementation of this component, along with details of the utilized algorithms and its interfaces, are described in more detail in Deliverable D2.3 [1], section 2.11.

7 Matching of requirements with VITAL-5G architecture and platform implementation

This section analyses if and how the requirements presented in section 3 are supported by the architecture and the latest implementation of the VITAL-5G platform, explaining which architectural components have been impacted for the implementation and/or the support of each of them. All the mandatory requirements are currently supported (see Table 18). Some optional features (see Table 19) have not yet been included in the second version of the VITAL-5G platform implementation, released in D2.3 [1], since the priority has been given to mandatory requirements. The final version, planned for D2.4, will implement the full set of functionalities.

Table 18: VITAL-5G Platform mandatory requirements.

Requirement description	Priority	Supported	Analysis
Generic Requirements (valid for all the experimentation phases)			
<p>R_0_01: VITAL-5G Platform experimentation services</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must provide and enable a centralized access for different actors to the VITAL-5G experimentation services during the various phases of the experimentation process: (i) Vertical Service design; (ii) Experiment design; (iii) Preparation of 5G testing environment; (iv) Vertical Service instantiation; (v) Experiment Execution; (vi) Vertical Service evaluation.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI provides a centralized access to all the experimentation services, hiding the details of the interaction with the various testbeds. Vertical Service and Experiment design are facilitated through the VITAL-5G catalogue, which offers a set of Network Applications to use as example or building blocks for new services and experiments. The VITAL-5G portal offers the procedures for service provisioning and monitoring, as well as for launching, validating and monitoring experiments on running services.
<p>R_0_02: Web based UI</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform should provide a web-based graphical user interface (GUI) to access all the VITAL-5G experimentation services.</p>	Medium	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI provides a centralized and secure access to all the experimentation services. It operates on top of the VITAL-5G Platform NBI and it is integrated with the access control mechanisms.
<p>R_0_03: OpenAPIs to access VITAL-5G platform functionalities in a programmable manner</p> <p>In addition to the GUI, a subset of the functionalities of the VITAL-5G platform experimentation services should be made available for external software components through programmable REST APIs.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	Each component of the VITAL-5G Platform offers its own REST APIs, which can be consumed by external entities with access control grants.
<p>R_0_04: Users profiles and groups</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform should provide differentiated access permissions to multiple users, on the basis of their role (e.g., experimenter, Network</p>	Medium	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	The access control mechanisms are based on the role and the groups assigned to the users.

<p>Application developer, etc.) and their group (e.g., the use case where the user is involved).</p> <p>In particular, the users should have restricted access to private Network Applications, services and experiments, as well as limited visibility and control over assets of the T&L facilities (e.g., sensors, video camera, actuators).</p>			
<p>R_0_05: Unified procedures across different VITAL-5G testbeds</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must expose common interfaces, information models and procedures to access the experimentation services, independent of the target VITAL-5G testbed where the experiments will be executed and the testbed's internal technologies or architecture.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	The VITAL-5G Platform provides a single and testbed-independent interface towards the users, while all the adaptation and translation mechanisms are handled internally at the southbound interface with the various testbeds.
Requirements related to Vertical Service Design			
<p>R_1_01: Browsing of existing Network Applications</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or to public Network Applications which can be re-used and composed in vertical services. The browsing of the Network Applications should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, category, etc. Network Application information should provide enough details to simplify their integration in vertical services and enable their testing and validation in the 5G network within the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented at the VITAL-5G Network Application Catalogue and VITAL-5G Web GUI.
<p>R_1_02: Onboarding of new Network Applications</p> <p>The user should be able to onboard new Network Applications in the VITAL-5G Platform. The onboarding should be properly authorized, taking also into account the level of access required by the Network Application to IoT devices and hardware in the T&L facility.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Application Catalogue, Network Application Validator, and Multi-site Inventory.
<p>R_1_04: Unified Network Application and service modelling</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must expose a common format and methodology to</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	The format of the Network Application and Vertical Service blueprints is independent from the descriptors used at each testbed.

<p>onboard, edit, update, delete, and monitor Network Applications and T&L service experiments, independent of the target 5G testbed and the format of the descriptors used in the testbed's internal catalogues.</p>			
<p>R_1_06: Onboarding of new Vertical Services The user should be able to define and onboard new Vertical Services composed of Network Applications in the VITAL-5G Platform. The onboarding of vertical services including Network Applications with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Application and Service Catalogues, and Access Control.
<p>R_1_07: Browsing of existing Vertical Services The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Vertical Services. The browsing of the Vertical Services should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, use case, etc. Vertical Service information should provide service-level information related to their Network Applications, 5G requirements and validation criteria.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Application and Service Catalogues, and Access Control.
<p>R_1_08: Browsing of information related to VITAL-5G testbed capabilities The user should be able to visualize information related to the capabilities of the VITAL-5G sites, e.g., in terms of 5G network infrastructure, available network slices, edge/cloud computing resources, IoT devices and hardware in the T&L facility (e.g., sensors, video cameras, actuators, etc., including their permitted access type, i.e., in read-only, write-only or read-write mode). The access to some information may be restricted, depending on the user profile and group.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI and Multi-site Inventory.
<p>R_1_10: Specification of 5G requirements for Network Applications and Vertical Services The user must be able to declare the 5G related requirements for Network Applications and Vertical Services,</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is enabled through the information model of the Network Application and Vertical Service blueprints, which declare the characteristics of the required mobile connectivity.

<p>using a simplified approach based on the declaration of pre-defined parameters.</p> <p>NEW: The user must be able to declare 5G requirements at the vertical service level different than the original ones associated to Network Applications composing the end-to-end service.</p>			
<p>R_1_11 (NEW): Specification of computing infrastructure requirements for Network Applications</p> <p>The user must be able to declare the requirements on the target computing infrastructure where the Network Applications will be deployed (e.g., support of GPUs).</p>	Medium	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is enabled through the information model of the Network Application blueprint, which declare requirements on the hardware capabilities.
Requirements related to Experiment Design			
<p>R_2_01: Browsing of existing Experiment blueprints</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Experiment blueprints. The search should be facilitated with suitable filters, e.g., based on target testbed, use case, etc</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Experiments Catalogue, and Access Control.
<p>R_2_02: Onboarding of new Experiment blueprints</p> <p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Experiment blueprint for the experimental validation of vertical services available in the VITAL-5G catalogue. The onboarding of experiment blueprints referred to vertical services with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue, and Access Control.
Requirements related to preparation of 5G testing environment			
<p>R_3_01: Onboarding of new Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors for experiment customizations</p> <p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Vertical Service descriptors and Experiment descriptors in the VITAL-5G Platform catalogue, in order to declare the specific configuration and customization of services and experiments, based on their blueprints. The onboarding descriptors</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue, and Access Control.

referred to blueprints with restricted access should be validated on the basis of the user groups.			
<p>R_3_02: Browsing of existing Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the information related to its own or public Vertical Service and Experiment descriptors.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue, and Access Control.
<p>R_3_03: Scheduling of service and experiment instances</p> <p>The user must be able to declare a preferred time slot for the provisioning of a vertical service and the execution of the experiments.</p> <p>NEW: The aspects of this requirement related to automated scheduling and resource reservation has been removed, since the preferred approach is based on agreements between experimenters and testbed owners in offline mode. The motivations are related to the flexibility needed in the execution of the experiments, allowing the developers to adjust their applications and repeat their test without strict time constraints.</p>	Medium	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Partially	This feature has been implemented in terms of definition of time slots for services' and experiments' execution. The automated scheduling has been not implemented due to negative feedback on its practical usability from testbed administrators and experimenters.
Requirements related to Vertical Service instantiation			
<p>R_4_01: On-demand provisioning and LCM of vertical services</p> <p>The user must be able to provision a vertical service on-demand and request the execution of lifecycle management actions, like scaling, re-configuration and termination. The service instantiation should be enabled only for public vertical service blueprints, the ones owned by the user or associated to his/her use cases. Other LCM actions on instantiated services should be enabled only to the users associated to the given use case.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications and Services Catalogue, Service LCM and Access Control.
<p>R_4_02: Secure user access to instantiated Network Applications</p> <p>The user must be able to access the Virtual Machines or containers where his/her own Network Applications are running in a secure manner.</p>	High	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	All VITAL-5G testbeds offers VPN connectivity towards the Network Applications.

<p>R_4_03: Hosting and execution of concurrent vertical services, guaranteeing target QoS</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must be able to deploy, manage and monitor multiple and simultaneous instances of Vertical Services, each of them with their own Network Applications.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications and Services Catalogue, Service LCM and Access Control.</p>
<p>R_4_04: Automated management of network slices</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform must coordinate the management of the network slices required for a given vertical service in a fully automated and transparent manner. Where required, the usage of edge resources for deployment of Network Application components should be enabled.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications and Services Catalogue, Service LCM, and 5G Slice Manager and Inventory, together with their interfaces towards the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
<p>R_4_05: Transparent interaction between the VITAL-5G Platform and the VITAL-5G testbeds</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform must be able to interact with the local NFV MANO and NG-RAN/5G CN control systems available at the three trial facilities. The details of such interaction must be fully transparent for the VITAL-5G users.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>The VITAL-5G users have a single access to the VITAL-5G Platform, while the interaction and the adaptation to the various testbeds is handled at the VITAL-5G Platform southbound interfaces through per-testbed drivers.</p>
<p>Requirements related to experiment execution</p>			
<p>R_5_01: On-demand experiment execution</p> <p>The user must be able to request the execution of an experiment, starting from its experiment descriptor, over an instantiated vertical service. The user must be able to request experiments only on his/her own vertical services, when in running mode.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Applications, Services and Experiments Catalogue, Service LCM, Experiment LCM, with their interfaces towards the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
<p>R_5_03: Support for secure, manual execution and configuration of test scripts on Network Applications during experiment execution.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to access the Network Applications in a secure manner, in order to manually trigger the execution of commands or test scripts.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>All VITAL-5G testbeds offers VPN connectivity towards the Network Applications, which the users can exploit to launch commands and scripts.</p>

<p>R_5_06: Monitoring, collection and visualization of 5G network metrics and KPIs.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize monitoring data related to 5G network KPIs, as declared in the experiment blueprint.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, Experiment LCM, Monitoring Platform, with its interface to the local monitoring systems of the VITAL-5G testbeds.</p>
<p>R_5_07: Monitoring, collection and visualization of service-level metrics and KPIs.</p> <p>During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize service-level KPIs, as declared in the blueprint, assuming that the Network Applications implement the mechanisms required to collect and publish such data.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, Experiment LCM, and Monitoring Platform, with its interface that allows Network Applications to publish monitoring data in the centralized Monitoring Platform.</p>
<p>R_5_09: Secure access to real-time and historical monitoring data via open interfaces.</p> <p>The user (or an external entity) must be able to access the various monitoring data collected during the execution of an experiment in a secure and authorized manner through open interfaces. These interfaces should support the efficient consumption of the data both in real-time or through queries for historical data.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented at the Monitoring Platform</p>
<p>Requirements related to Vertical Service evaluation</p>			
<p>R_6_01: Visualization of information related to executed experiments, with reports on the service and network KPIs collected during their execution.</p> <p>The user must be able to visualize the list of executed experiments and, for each of them, visualize its details, graphs related to its service and network KPIs, as well as results related to the experiment execution.</p>	<p>High</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Platform web GUI, Experiment LCM, Monitoring Platform, and Result Analytics.</p>

Table 19: VITAL-5G Platform optional requirements.

Requirement description	Priority	Support	Analysis
<p>Requirements related to Vertical Service Design</p>			

<p>R_1_03 (NEW): Validation of new Network Applications at onboarding stage</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform may enable the automated validation of new Network Applications, in terms of Network Application package format verification, functional validation in the target testbed, and compatibility with capabilities offered by the testbed.</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, VITAL-5G Network Application Catalogue, Network Application Validator, and Multi-site Inventory.</p>
<p>R_1_05: Network Applications onboarding with possibility to declare metadata that helps Network Applications composition, testing, and validation</p> <p>When a Network Application is onboarded, the user must be able to include metadata to facilitate composition, testing, and validation of the Network Application in an automated manner.</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>The Network Application and Vertical Service metadata are modelled in their blueprints and they are used as input for the execution of internal provisioning, monitoring and validation procedures at the VITAL-5G Platform.</p>
<p>R_1_09: Facilitated composition of Network Applications in vertical services</p> <p>The VITAL-5G platform can provide mechanisms to facilitate the composition of Network Applications into end-to-end services, which could be partially automated according to the metadata defined in the Network Application package and in the vertical service blueprint.</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is enabled through the information model of the Network Application blueprint, which declares the interfaces provided and consumed by each application.</p>
<p>Requirements related to Experiment Design</p>			
<p>R_2_03: Wizard for guided definition and onboarding of new Experiment blueprints</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform web GUI may provide a wizard to guide the user in the definition of the various parameters that constitute an experiment blueprint.</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: No</p>	<p>This optional feature is not yet implemented in the second release of the VITAL-5G Platform.</p>
<p>R_2_04: Validation of new experiment blueprints at onboarding stage</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform may enable the automated validation of new experiment blueprints, in terms of format verification and compatibility with the existing vertical services.</p>	<p>Low</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: No</p>	<p>This optional feature is not yet implemented in the second release of the VITAL-5G Platform.</p>
<p>R_2_05 (NEW): Onboarding of new Test Case blueprints</p> <p>The user should be able to define and onboard new Test Case blueprints</p>	<p>Medium</p>	<p>Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This optional feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI,</p>

specifying the scripts to be executed during the automated testing and the related variables. Test Cases should be linked to the experiment blueprints.			Experiments Catalogue, and Access Control.
Requirements related to Vertical Service instantiation			
R_4_06: Centralized license management for Network Applications The VITAL-5G Platform should provide mechanisms to verify and manage different types of licenses associated to the Network Applications.	Low	Architecture: Yes Implementation: No	This feature is not yet implemented in the second release of the VITAL-5G Platform (planned for D2.4).
R_4_07: Logic for optimized placement of virtual functions or automated slice management The VITAL-5G platform may implement internal logic and procedures to optimize resource orchestration, slice management and virtual function placement e.g., on the basis of the slice type and profile, resource utilisation and service demands. Such mechanisms may be implemented through AI/ML algorithms e.g., for load prediction.	Low	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Partially	This feature is implemented in terms of automated slice management, only on the testbeds supporting the dynamic update of network slices.
Requirements related to experiment execution			
R_5_02: Automated execution and configuration of test scripts The user can declare test scripts that will be automatically configured and executed during the running of an experiment.	Medium	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Experiments Catalogue and Experiment LCM, exploiting the interfaces for Day 2 Configuration available at the NFV Orchestrator in VITAL-5G testbeds.
R_5_04: Decoupled service lifecycle management during experiment execution. During the execution of an experiment, the user (or an external entity) must be able to trigger lifecycle management actions on the associated vertical service (e.g., to scale up and down, terminate or re-configure some Network Applications).	Low	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature has been implemented decoupling the logic of Service LCM and Experiment LCM components.
R_5_08: Monitoring, collection and visualization of metrics and KPIs related to the virtual computing infrastructure. During the execution of an experiment, the user must be able to visualize monitoring data related to the virtual computing infrastructure (e.g., CPU or memory utilization), associated to the	Medium	Architecture: Yes Implementation: Yes	This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Web GUI, Experiment LCM, Monitoring Platform, with its interface to the local monitoring systems of the VITAL-5G testbeds.

consumption of resources for the service Network Applications.			
<p>R_5_10 (NEW): Automated AI/ML-based diagnostic for closed-loop LCM actions.</p> <p>During the experiment execution, the insights coming from the diagnostics functionality, potentially based on AI/ML techniques and applied to both computing infrastructure and network, should trigger automated LCM actions during the Network Applications' execution, following a closed-loop approach.</p>	Medium	<p>Architecture: Yes</p> <p>Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: Service LCM, Monitoring Platform, Result Analytics, AI-based Diagnostic.</p>
Requirements related to Vertical Service evaluation			
<p>R_6_02: Automated diagnostic for identifying service bottlenecks and root cause of performance degradation.</p> <p>The VITAL-5G Platform should be able to process the KPIs collected during an experiment and identify in an automated manner the potential causes of performance degradation, related to issues at the 5G network or computing infrastructure level.</p>	Medium	<p>Architecture: Yes</p> <p>Implementation: Yes</p>	<p>This feature is implemented through the cooperation of the following components: VITAL-5G Platform web GUI, Experiment LCM, Monitoring Platform, Result Analytics, and AI-based Diagnostic.</p>

8 Conclusions

This deliverable is an update of D1.2 [5] and it has described the final version of the VITAL-5G system architecture, with focus on the high-level specification of the VITAL-5G Platform, used as baseline for its implementation. The architecture design has been updated taking into account the results of the development and integration activities performed in WP2 and WP3, as well as the feedback from experimenters in internal and early 3rd party trials in terms of required features and usability.

The objective of this document is to provide a global picture of the main VITAL-5G concepts. It addresses aspects like experimentation procedures for defining and testing T&L services, modelling and management of Network Applications, VITAL-5G platform functionalities for design, provisioning, evaluation and results analysis of experiments in the area of 5G-enabled services for the T&L sector. Instead, the reader interested in the internal details of the VITAL-5G platform with its software components and the deployment of the three VITAL-5G testbeds can refer to WP2 and WP3 deliverables, respectively.

Starting from the definition of the main stakeholders involved in VITAL-5G ecosystem, the deliverable has initially presented the experimentation services offered by the VITAL-5G platform for the validation of Network Applications and T&L vertical services in 5G infrastructures. Particular attention has been paid to the experimentation tools, validation features, access to testbed devices and pre-onboarded Network Applications provided for external 3rd party users interested in building novel 5G-enabled applications and verify their performance in realistic environments. For each testbed, the document has described the capability of the network and computing infrastructure, the set of T&L devices, datasets and tools made available for 3rd parties, as well as the list of public Network Applications that can be re-used and extended to create new services. This information can be used by potential 3rd parties to select the VITAL-5G testbed more suitable for their experimentation objectives.

The document has presented the concept of Network Applications. The modelling proposed in VITAL-5G describes their interactions and requirements with respect to the 5G network maintaining a service-oriented and technology-agnostic perspective, suitable for the expertise of application developers and service providers. The information models for specification of Network Applications, T&L vertical services and experiments can be used as reference for 3rd parties to develop new applications and services capable of exploiting 5G network features in an easy manner.

The requirements, macro-components and deployment models of the VITAL-5G system have been presented to foster the deployment of similar 5G testbeds, thus promoting and facilitating the creation, experimentation and roll-out of new services and applications for 5G, especially from SMEs. The VITAL-5G system architecture can be considered as a reference for building other 5G experimental facilities, even beyond the T&L sector. Moreover, the architectural elements of the VITAL-5G platform (most of them available as open-source software) constitute valid assets to quickly setup tools for provisioning of network-enabled applications in a variety of virtual environments, with embedded features for monitoring, testing automation and validation. A set of new functionalities has been made available in this second version of the architecture, increasing the level of programmability, monitoring, network configuration, and service automation offered by the VITAL-5G platform. Where needed, the requests for additional features coming from internal and external experimenters have been taken into account updating the list of requirements and modifying accordingly the design and the platform implementation.

9 Annex 1 – State of the art

VITAL-5G has highly re-used existing resources and knowledge from previous 5G PPP projects (e.g., 5G EVE²⁰, 5GSOLUTIONS²¹, 5G-Blueprint²²) as well as other relevant projects and commercial assets to create innovation in support of a significant 5G enablement for the T&L sectoral actors. The details of the re-used software assets and related updates have been reported in WP2 deliverables. At the architectural level, VITAL-5G has integrated some of the concepts and system solutions proposed by previous projects, enhancing them to overcome critical limitations identified regarding the adoption of 5G in production services by T&L industry verticals: 1) a network-centric vision on 5G orchestration tools, 2) a substantial mismatch of backgrounds between Telcos and Verticals (from Phase II and Phase III), and 3) packages for 5G/NFV experimentation mostly network-centric and applicable to small trial experiments. Moreover, orchestration and network slicing platforms available in state-of-the-art (both in the form of design artefacts and prototypes/products) did not provide high level interfaces for allowing T&L verticals to design and deploy services in a completely automated and autonomous manner.

The VITAL-5G project has gone beyond these gaps and limitations by addressing specific R&D innovations:

- Enhancements to Intent-Based modelling and specification for Network Applications: translation of high-level T&L-oriented intents, modelled through enhanced Network Application and Vertical Service blueprints, into 5G network components, computing infrastructure resource and VNF or Network Application deployments and configurations. Provide the functionality extensions to the intent-based modelling in order to accommodate the more complex multi-vertical environment of the VITAL-5G trials, with the capability of capturing T&L specific requirements and software application dependencies.
- Platform-agnostic vertical slice design and control for Network Applications: VITAL-5G's portal logic for managing networks slices allows for translating application requirements into specific descriptors for the virtualized 5G infrastructure and for defining the proper resources and intelligent placement within the allocated slice (adapted dynamically through automated orchestration mechanisms according to the service's lifecycle behavior).
- Advanced KPI Analytics & Diagnostics tools for Network Applications: VITAL-5G integrates KPI validation for service performance evaluation and benchmarking towards business SLA verification. Vertical services are evaluated in a business-oriented perspective. Data from automation of operations collected are made available for further analysis and can serve as a basis for comparison in further similar Network Application implementations.
- Reusability of the 5G EVE and the 5G-Blueprint 5G facilities: VITAL-5G has reused and extended the 5G EVE and 5G-Blueprint infrastructures and benefit from the technology updates in their roadmap.
- Replication in non-ICT-17 5G facilities: VITAL-5G has integrate each one of the three facilities with the VITAL-5G Platform, providing secure connection and adaptation to the VITAL-5G Portal and VITAL-5G Catalogue.
- Seamless integration of 5G-powered devices for freight logistics (vessels, robots, AGVs): VITAL-5G has enhanced versions of current devices that use 5G connectivity for their communications and integration with edge computing for localized latency-sensitive application workloads.
- VITAL-5G Catalogue & Network Applications: VITAL-5G has implemented a catalogue of Network Application capable of onboarding packages, with extended role-based access controls to limit the visibility and actions on packages based on user's roles and additional policies.
- Network Applications for T&L sector: Development of 13 Vertical-Specific Network Applications to address specific industry challenges of the three facilities.
- Vertical-agnostic Network Applications: Development of 5 Vertical-Agnostic Network Applications which can be utilized by multiple participating parties in a variety of vertical use cases.

²⁰ <https://www.5g-eve.eu>

²¹ <https://5gsolutionsproject.eu/>

²² <https://www.5gblueprint.eu/>

9.1 Validation Platforms and Testbeds for 5G Services

VITAL-5G is part of the 5G PPP family of projects and as such, it is a natural follow-up of multiple innovative initiatives before it. In order to maximize the output produced by the project, the partners of VITAL-5G have focused their effort on the innovative Network Application based solutions for the T&L sector, as much as possible, instead of trying to “reinvent the wheel” and to create an experimentation platform from scratch. This has been only possible, by taking advantage of the accomplishments, know-how and expertise of the 5G PPP projects that preceded VITAL-5G, in terms of experimentation platform set-up, 5G network & vertical integrations, monitoring, result collecting and results analysis, etc., allowing VITAL-5G to build on-top of previous innovations. Figure 38 depicts the 5G PPP projects Heritage figure, indicating the links among the various projects up until March 2020.

Figure 38: 5G PPP Projects Heritage²³

The VITAL-5G partners have strong links with multiple of the predecessor projects, especially with ICT-17 and ICT-19 projects. Significant know-how, components (HW & SW) and operational and experimentation management expertise has been utilized from these projects, enabling the re-use of available elements and procedures, hence speeding up the delivery of VITAL-5G outputs, avoiding past development, deployment and experimentation mistakes and allowing for the further evolution of the provided solutions to verticals. More specifically, from ICT-17 projects a large amount of information and components has been inherited with regards to experimentation platform development, deployment and utilization, trial facilities interconnection and operation and experimentation tools usage. Besides the close relationship of VITAL-5G with 5G-EVE (multiple

²³ <https://5g-ppp.eu/5g-ppp-heritage/>

common partners), all three ICT-17 projects are extremely relevant for VITAL-5G, as they were the pioneering projects in terms of deploying, configuring and allowing experimentation over advanced 5G testbeds in Europe, and as such multiple lessons were learned from their experience. For this reason, the approach of 5G VINNI and 5GENESIS, are also analyzed in this section (along with 5G-EVE). From the ICT-19 projects, significant expertise and some tools have been inherited to support the verticals’ application integration within the experimentation platform, the support of vertical experimenters and the execution of extensive measurement and trial campaigns. The remainder of this section highlights the VITAL-5G relationship with some of the key predecessor projects, from which a significant amount of expertise, knowledge and components are drawn.

9.1.1 5G EVE

5G EVE is an H2020 ICT-17 project (July 2018 – June 2021) that built a European 5G validation platform for extensive trials of vertical services in advanced 5G infrastructures. The project created a multi-site 5G end-to-end facility developing and interconnecting four sites in Greece, Spain, Italy and France that has been extended further with Romanian cluster to give 5G experimenters the possibility to validate their services in a variety of operational conditions. The 5G EVE facility is still used for several trials and pilots from ICT-19 projects, addressing the requirements of different business sectors like smart factory, transport, city, farming, tourism, multimedia, etc. The facility has also been extended with additional sites to reach new areas and guarantee the 5G coverage in the various target premises (e.g., factories, museums, etc.) where the pilots are executed.

5G EVE offers a complete set of experimentation services, supporting vertical service developers and providers along all the steps of validation procedure, as represented in the workflow depicted in Figure 39 [2]. The initial phases of test design and test preparation usually require the direct interaction between experimenters and 5G EVE technicians in order to identify particular service requirements, customizations and/or additional hardware and infrastructure setups that would be needed for the particular validation campaign. The test design is facilitated through blueprints that provide a common template to define services and experiments, with the possibility to reuse tools from the 5G EVE portfolio, e.g., to reproduce variable environment and network conditions, and to on-board new application components. The preparation phase allows to customize the experiment settings and schedule the testing campaign in the selected testbed, so that the site administrator can take care of the environment and infrastructure configuration, which may involve manual interventions (e.g., for the installation of additional hardware, the reservation of some resources, etc.).

Figure 39: 5G EVE Experimentation Services ([2]).

The two following phases are mostly automated and they can be triggered and controlled directly by the experimenters through the 5G EVE portal or programmatically via open interfaces. At the execution time, the service is instantiated on the virtual environment and properly configured through the orchestration functionalities of the platform. Moreover, the retrieval of the monitoring data is activated and the test scripts defined for the experiment are automatically started, collecting the related results. During the test execution, metrics, logs and KPIs are collected and made available for the experimenters to facilitate the analysis of the experiment progress. At the final validation time, the collected data are analysed through automated tools

available in the 5G EVE platform for results analysis and diagnostics, providing the experimenters with reports about the obtained performance and, when degradation is detected, the identification of possible root causes. VITAL-5G inherits most of the 5G EVE concepts, workflow and methodology for the experimental validation of vertical services. VITAL-5G has extended the work of 5G EVE integrating the concept of Network Applications and applying the 5G EVE experimentation procedures to services composed of Network Applications, taking into account their additional characteristics, e.g., their dependencies and interactions with particular IoT and hardware devices, for the monitoring and control of the elements involved in a T&L service.

The 5G EVE architecture is depicted in Figure 40, identifying the components available in each 5G facility (represented in green) and the functional elements of the 5G EVE platform (represented in orange). In particular, the 5G EVE Interworking Framework (IWF) is the layer that unifies the access to the different 5G EVE sites and enables the orchestration of services with components deployed over multiple sites and interconnected together [14]. On top of the IWF, the web-based 5G EVE Portal provides the single access to all the experimentation tools and functionalities offered by 5G EVE. The Portal services include the onboarding of the experiment blueprints, the creation and configuration of experiment descriptors, the instantiation of new services and the launch of their experimental testing, the visualization of the collected monitoring data and the analytics and diagnostics reports.

Figure 40: 5G EVE Architecture.

The VITAL-5G platform has capitalized on the 5G EVE architectural concepts, with particular reference to the unified interaction with several 5G sites as well as to the features offered by the Portal for service definition, instantiation, monitoring and validation. One of the key assets that 5G-EVE facilities is providing is the high degree of flexibility in adapting the architecture for any specific vertical. For example, French-Romanian facility cluster (shown in Figure 41) is mainly based on the 5G OAI, Mosaic-5G, Open Networking Automation Platform (ONAP), RAN OAI (LTE/NR eNodeB/gNodeB and UEs), Core OAI (4G EPC, 5GC functional entities) providing the functionalities and meeting all requirements for an end-to-end use case deployment.

Figure 41: 5G FR/RO experimentation facility cluster from 5G EVE.

Moreover, considering the lessons learnt from validation activities performed by consortium partners in the context of 5G EVE, some extensions have been introduced to enhance the features of the VITAL-5G system. Some examples include the increased flexibility and configurability of the testing procedures, the possibility to manually control the service components instantiated in the virtual environments (i.e., the possibility to access and operate on the Network Applications components) and the decoupling between the service lifecycle and the testing execution logic. Even more important, considering the current trend of implementing AI/ML-based solutions for closed loop automation applied to service orchestration and re-configuration, as well as ML-driven application logic, more powerful mechanisms and APIs have been provided, for enhanced collection and consumption of monitoring data, both historical and real-time, with advanced filtering capabilities and external triggers of lifecycle management actions on the instantiated services, even during the testing execution time.

9.1.2 5G VINNI

5G VINNI²⁴ is an H2020 ICT-17 project (July 2018 – December 2021) that developed an E2E 5G facility to first demonstrate the practical implementation of infrastructure to support the key 5G KPIs, and then to allow vertical industries to test and validate specific applications that are dependent upon those KPIs [15]. 5G VINNI is underpinned by principles that allow for highly dynamic and flexible network architectures, service deployment and testing, that will create new technical and commercial service deployment models. These in turn drive inter-facility interconnection to enable virtualized functions from the network and service layer to be called upon from any facility, with complete location agnosticism (cloud-based network instantiation) that has no functional boundaries, implemented across multiple facility sites.

The 5G-VINNI facility sites (Figure 42) are classified into two different types:

- Main Facility sites: E2E 5G-VINNI facility that offers services to ICT-18-19-22 projects with well-defined Service Level Agreements (Norway, UK, Spain, Greece).
- Experimentation Facility sites: 5G-VINNI sites that provide environments for advanced focused experimentation and testing possibilities on elements and combinations of elements of the E2E model (Portugal, Munich, Berlin).

In addition, there is a mobile experimentation facility site in the form of a rapid response vehicle for public protection and disaster relief (PPDR) use cases and potentially a boat.

Figure 42: 5G-VINNI facility with Main Facility sites and Experimentation Facility sites.

²⁴ <https://www.5g-vinni.eu/>

5G-VINNI conceptual E2E facility architecture (Figure 43) has various building blocks organized in three layers: *Resources & Functional Level* (RAN, Backhaul, Mobile Core and Cloud Computing facilities) that will provide the physical resources to host the other two layers: *Service Level* and *Network Level* (e.g., VNFs). These are interconnected to build dedicated logical networks, customized to the respective telco services, e.g., eMBB, V2X, URLLC, mMTC.

Figure 43: 5G-VINNI high level conceptual E2E facility architecture.

The novelty of 5G-VINNI is the modularity which guarantees the highest degrees of freedom of both 5G-VINNI facility site configurations and facility interworking. Any Service Level or Network Level VNF from any 5G-VINNI facility, can be called upon to be included within the logical network of a use case driven from another facility creating an unlimited capability to implement and test use cases using the consolidated shared capabilities of all facilities. This so called “*Recursiveness*” offers the potential for new business models and partner relationships (between partner operators, or between operators and large enterprise customers) whereby the service provider may both expose and consume service at different levels in the network.

The execution of internal validation campaigns, as well as the vertical customer experiments, run through a user-friendly Testing Portal, which is the point where tests are configured, test campaigns are executed, and campaigns results are visualized and analyzed.

Figure 44: 5G-VINNI Test Framework.

5G VINNI’s combination of this comprehensive test framework (Figure 44), the multiple interworking 5G RAN and 5G core infrastructures, and zero-touch E2E service orchestration provide a unique platform for testing and trialling industry use cases. The platform facilitates the rapid on-boarding of verticals by exposing network slice life-cycle management functions through an open API. By using the API’s, the verticals are able to create, manage and de-commission network slices. This offers a high level of agility in the management of connectivity services and allows verticals to shorten their innovation cycles – quickly establishing network connectivity for E2E communication services and applying different test scenarios to the connectivity using the testing portal in order to evaluate the impact upon their E2E communication services.

9.1.3 5GENESIS

5GENESIS²⁵ project targets to facilitate the deployment and execution of the vertical industries’ services with real users, through the proposition of a homogeneous interface that can be supported by the various platforms [16]. Therefore, a 5G experimentation blueprint has been developed in order to serve as a common architectural reference and the total 5G facility has been separated into five, diverse in terms of capabilities, yet fully interoperable, experimentation platforms (Figure 45).

The main characteristics of the 5GENESIS infrastructure are:

- The facility is distributed and is comprised of various geographically dispersed platforms.
- The platforms are complementary in terms of features, nevertheless aligned to the proposed common reference architecture.
- The platforms are administratively independent, exposing open interfaces for inter-platform coordination and verticals experimentation.
- The platforms accommodate multiple experiments from various verticals with diverse requirements.
- The platforms are fully interoperable and can be interconnected in order to form a truly end-to-end Facility.

Figure 45: The 5GENESIS platforms.

²⁵ <https://5genesis.eu/>

Each one of the platforms participating in the 5GENESIS Facility shall have the flexibility to govern its own physical topology, architecture and particular technological features. Nevertheless, towards harmonizing the different platforms and experimentation infrastructures, elements of the common reference architecture are to be replicated across the five platforms. In this way, each platform can be administratively independent, yet interoperable with the other platforms. A schematic view of the proposed 5GENESIS Experimentation Blueprint, meant to implement all of the above-mentioned points, is depicted in Figure 46.

Figure 46: 5GENESIS Experimentation Blueprint.

9.1.4 5G Blueprint

The overall objective of the 5G-Blueprint project²⁶ is to design and validate a technical architecture, business model and governance model for uninterrupted cross-border teleoperated transport based on 5G connectivity [17]. The project's outcome should be usable as the blueprint for subsequent operational pan-European deployment of teleoperated transport solutions in the logistics sector and beyond. The 5G infrastructure design and deployment of 5G-Blueprint focus on enabling teleoperation and seamless cross border use with 5G technology. The use cases to demonstrate this capability are automated barge control, automated drive-in-loop docking, CACC based platooning, remote take-over operations. By providing Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra Reliable Low Latency Communications (URLLC) and massive Machine Type Communications (mMTC), the architectural design of 5G network is key to the success of the project. The architecture design covers from 5G User Equipment, Radio Access Network, Edge Computing, Transport, Core Network, to network APIs. The design has a focus on addressing network slicing parameters and design for the project use cases and seamless cross bordering roaming.

²⁶ <https://www.5gblueprint.eu/>

Figure 47: 5G Blueprint geographic scope.

The highlights of the 5G-Blueprint infrastructure are:

- The 5G facility in Port of Antwerp covers diversified industrial area including waterways, road networks, factories, infrastructure for logistic application on waterway and road networks (such as docking, parking, barging infrastructure, cranes etc), to support teleoperation uses cases.
- The 5G facility in North Sea Port covers a border-crossing area for both waterway and road network between Belgium and Netherlands to validate seamless 5G roaming.
- The 5G infrastructure is designed and built with an architecture aligned by KPN and Telenet based on different current network situation and network equipment suppliers, thus can be used as reference for further scaling in other networks.
- The platform is based on independent network infrastructure while utilizing existing commercial network footprint. Creates a good balance between exposing network interfaces towards 3rd parties and between MNOs with operational impact on commercial networks and maximizing network availability with hybrid network design.
- The test zone has a large physical area and strong ecosystem to accommodate and validates end-to-end application and new use cases.

The overall 5G architecture of 5G Blueprint is shown in Figure 48.

Figure 48: 5G-Blueprint architecture overview.

5G-Blueprint is very relevant to the VITAL-5G work as the two projects share the 5G infrastructure used in the port of Antwerp, which in VITAL-5G has been upgraded to Rel.16 SA for the completion of the VITAL-5G trials. The common partners shared among the two projects, namely IMEC, TEL and SF, have guaranteed the knowledge transfer from 5G-Blueprint and capitalized on lessons learned in order to more effectively set-up the VITAL-5G trials and to maximize the reuse of components.

9.2 Modelling of Vertical Applications for 5G Services

Regarding the modeling of various vertical and/or services, as well as the information models for the related VNFs, significant work has been carried out by the three ICT-17 projects, namely 5G EVE, 5GENESIS and 5G-VINNI.

In 5G EVE a Catalogue Service has been defined as a component of the Portal Backend responsible for management of the blueprints and descriptors required for the experiment design and definition (namely Vertical Service Blueprints (VSBs), Context Blueprints (CTXBs), Experiment Blueprints and Descriptors (EXPBs and EXPDs respectively) [2]. These descriptors are used to translate the service-oriented requirements from the verticals into formal definition of vertical service and experiment settings (defined as “context”) that run in the facilities to execute the experiment. These descriptors are based on distinct templates or “Blueprints” that the experimenters can use to help them define their desired experiment. These are practically information models used to obscure the underlying complexity and retrieve information from non-expert users to assist with the definition of the experiment on a service and network level [2]. Within 5G EVE the following blueprints have been defined: Vertical Service Blueprints, Context Blueprints, Experiment blueprints and Test Case Blueprints. As VITAL-5G inherits multiple elements from 5G EVE including its experimentation structure and tools, a lot of these information models will also be inherited and reused, after being updated to reflect and accommodate the specific needs of the VITAL-5G experimentation architecture, updated tools and targeted vertical services.

5GENESIS uses two key concepts for its experimentation process and the definition of the experiments, namely the test cases and the experiment descriptor. These entities utilize information models specified in 5GENESIS Deliverable D2.3 [18] to assist with the detailed definition and configuration of the testbed and experimental setup. The 5GENESIS test cases describe the experiment and its measurable objectives and include a

configuration file that specifies: i) the configuration of the environment (for all RATs and network); ii) the set of procedures; iii) the monitored metrics, and iv) formulas needed to calculate the KPIs. The experiment descriptor is a file that describes all the information needed to execute the experiment and compute the KPIs associated with the experiment. The 5GENESIS experiment descriptor, is not comprised of smaller entities as in 5G EVE and contains information such as the type and experiment meta-data, list of test cases to be executed, slice configurations, service configuration, traffic sources and more. The Experiment Life-Cycle Manager (ELCM) composes an experiment plan using the experiment descriptor and the information of the test cases. This is a similar approach to the one from 5G EVE (which has also been adopted in VITAL-5G) as the designated information models, define the same parameters and offer configuration capabilities, only using a different structure (mono-block experiment descriptor instead of multiple element blocks).

5G-VINNI also adopts model-based service templates for the definition of the experiments which are defined as structured document that provides a complete description of a given service, including information on service topology and expected behaviour. The service templates are offered via the 5G-VINNI service catalogue which offers the opportunity to providers and experimenters to instantiate and configure a customized experiment. The main tool/model used in 5G-VINNI for experiment definition and configuration is the Service Blueprint (SB), which is based on the GSMA Global Slice Template (GST), and consist of four main parts, namely the *service type*, the *service topology*, the *service requirements* and the *service exposure, testing and monitoring* [19]. Practically, the VINNI-SB contains all the same information that 5G EVE and 5GENESIS use for the definition of an experiment, but with a slightly different structure.

It becomes obvious that all three ICT-17 projects, which are considered very successful in experimenter engagement and 5G experimentation roll-out, use a similar approach when it comes to the definition of the VNF information models, and the blueprints and descriptors used for experiment definition and configuration. VITAL-5G has thus reused most of the successful elements of the above-mentioned models, updating them to accommodate 5G SA testbed functionality and new requirements from the T&L stakeholders.

Regarding the modeling of Net Applications and the relevant data models, they are only recently addressed as such, by the nine ICT-41 projects (including VITAL-5G) funded by the European Commission. Through cross-project interactions (via 5G PPP) VITAL-5G managed to create a high-level overview of the addressed vertical services targeted and the key Network Application aspects in scope of each of the ICT-41 projects, as presented in Section 0. VITAL-5G is closely collaborating with the rest of the 5G PPP projects to produce knowledge and documentation and to provide insights and guidelines regarding the development, deployment and validation of Network Applications in various vertical industries. A concrete outcome is the white paper published by the 5G-PPP Software Network WG in September 2022 “Network Applications: Opening up 5G and beyond networks” [20].

9.3 Tools for Monitoring and Automated Testing

Significant prior work has already taken place in terms of monitoring tools, automated testing and validation methodologies for 5G networks, and the services provisioned on top of them, by key stakeholder groups and previous 5G PPP projects. In order to identify the most suitable ones to be adopted for the platform and testbeds of VITAL-5G, a State-of-the-Art (SotA) study is necessary in order to understand the advantages and open issues of existing work. ETSI has performed significant work in terms of Interoperability Testing (INT) methodologies for the validation of vertical applications over 5G networks [21], which is considered as the reference point for VITAL-5G. The goal of such elaborate testing and validation methodologies is to streamline the vertical application testing and validation over 5G experimental platforms in a highly complex multi-stakeholder environment comprising Mobile Network Operators (MNOs), Original Equipment Manufacturers (OEMs), network and chipset vendors, vertical service providers and application developers. Through the definition of such methodologies, it is guaranteed that each stakeholder can draw useful insights regarding their product/service and find ways to further develop and increase the impact of their offering. For instance, verticals will better understand the true potential of 5G technologies for expanding their solutions or even innovating their business model, while MNOs and vendors will gain insight into the type of vertical application solutions utilizing the 5G networks, which will

help them make decisions on whether and how to evolve their portfolio to support verticals with similar demands [21].

9.3.1 Relevant standardisation work

From a network perspective, 3GPP has performed significant work to enable precise automated testing and validation procedures, mostly focusing on network aspects, e.g., 5G NR protocols [22][23] or Radio Resource Management (RRM) [24], but also addressing application level testing [25]. Additionally, a KPI definition template has been specified in [26] to allow categorization of the KPIs and the methods, tools, and calculations that are used in order to measure and validate end-to-end KPIs and the corresponding network slices used. As expected, the 3GPP methodologies and testing procedures heavily focus on the evaluation of the various components of the networks, and even though some attempts have been made to incorporate end-to-end testing and service validation from a vertical's point of view, the detailed scenario definition (including network conditions) that would allow for their reproducibility is missing, while a detailed test-execution plan (step-by-step) is also not provided. Significant efforts by 3GPP are ongoing to further onboard verticals into their processes and to try to work with them to update their testing and validation methodologies as evidenced by 3GPP TR22.804 [27], 3GPP TS22.261 [28] and 3GPP TS22.104 [29].

Another relevant stream of work is the work performed by ITU on “*APIs for interoperable testbed federations*” addressing the subject of testbed federation for 5G technologies, as portrayed in the currently ongoing definition of the recommendation ITU-T Q.API4TB [30]. This recommendation is expected to guide the development of testbeds that can be federated and enable the testing of complex vertical applications utilizing different network components and resources located in disjointed testbeds. The expectation is for federated testbeds to bring sustainability in fostering environments for quick innovations and testing of complex technologies and use cases, and for enabling quicker time to market for products and services [31].

ETSI has also performed considerable work to enable autonomous testing procedures for fixed and mobile networks, mostly under the umbrella of a sub-group of the ETSI TC INT Working Group, namely the Autonomic Management and Control (AMC) Intelligence for Self-Managed Fixed & Mobile Integrated Networks (AFI) WG. There are two kinds of Standards being developed in ETSI TC INT that are relevant to Vertical Applications over Autonomic/Autonomous 5G and Beyond Networks and Testing, namely:

- *Standards for Testing AI Models (including AI Models of Generic Autonomic Networking Architecture (GANA) Cognitive Decision-making-Elements (DEs) for AMC in 5G and Beyond Networks*: These standards describe a way to test GANA cognitive indirectly by measuring network service performance KPIs, i.e., KPIs of relevance to network services like those required by Vertical Applications. The analysis and comparison of the KPIs under different operating conditions and the effect of the various network Decision Elements (DE) provide an assessment of the impact or value of DE autonomics for the network.
- *Testing of Autonomic/Autonomous Networks (ANs), e.g., GANA based 5G ANs as Use Case for Standards for Testbeds Federations for 5G and Beyond (ITU-T – SG11)*: Through Federation, knowledge exchange and transfer, meta-data, events, triggers, synchronization and coordination messages, and many other forms of information are communicated in a collaborative fashion by testbeds/platforms to achieve E2E AMC operations such as E2E Self-Optimization of AN resources, Self-/Protection and Self-/Defense against detected security attacks, threats and risks to address security challenges that have impact on various network domains.

9.3.2 Relevant 5G PPP work

Some remarkable examples of state-of-the-art solutions can be found in the 5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership (5G PPP) initiative. 5G PPP is a joint initiative between the European Commission (EC) and the European ICT industry which aims to explore and demonstrate the key benefits of 5G technology to transform the various vertical industries and enable innovative applications which will ultimately contribute to European Union digital transformation. As discussed earlier, three recent 5GPPP research infrastructure projects (under

the H2020 call ICT-17-2018) stand out in terms of enabling multi-stakeholder vertical trials over state-of-the-art 5G networks, namely, 5G EVE, 5GENESIS and 5G-VINNI. Each of them provides an end-to-end testing platform for vertical industries to validate a wide variety of use cases in both controlled and large-scale setups. These projects provide feedback to the 5G PPP Test Monitoring and Validation Work Group (5G PPP TMV WG), that has delivered a set of highly valuable recommendations on automatic testing framework for vertical KPI validation (including Testing as a Service (TaaS) approach), model driven methodology, and the mapping of E2E vertical service KPIs vs technical network KPIs. The work of the three ICT-17 projects as well as that of the 5G PPP TMV WG, has been of high relevance to the VITAL-5G project and their procedures, methodologies and know-how play a major part on the definition of the equivalent processes and the architecture and tools utilized in VITAL-5G. As such, VITAL-5G has adopted the terminology definition embraced by the TMV group regarding fundamental testing and monitoring aspects [21], namely:

- **Monitoring:** A generally passive process that is providing metrics from various components/layers of the 5G network.
- **Testing:** Procedure that provides a greater observability due to the active control over the type and intensity of traffic that is pushed through the network and through subsets of the network elements. This provides more degrees of freedoms in selecting what can be tested and measured (e.g., scalability or security resilience)
- **5G system:** A system composed by several complex and heterogeneous components, blending IT, cloud, and telecommunication technologies, stacked on top of each other to create the full 5G network like the pyramid in Figure 49.
- **Testing as a Service (TaaS):** Testing process which reduces the effort that the MNOs’ engineers need to put in testing the 5G infrastructure and components, by simplifying the testing operations and providing an interface to connect to the Continuous Integration / Continuous Deployment (CI/CD) pipelines of the MNOs NetOps. TaaS streamlines the execution of the different types of tests that need to be performed in each level of the 5G system pyramid (see Figure 49), while deploying and integrating the network, onboarding the VNFs, and providing the services.

As the TMV recommends supporting and using a TaaS approach in the future 5G networks, and the group is currently working on identifying several commonly shared Test Cases. VITAL-5G closely follows this recommendation and is implementing testing approaches based on commonly defined Test Case templates (see Deliverable D1.4 [9]).

Figure 49: TaaS System overview [21].

The TMV’s priority is to provide methodologies and Test Cases for the validation of the E2E services delivered to the verticals. The first step to accomplish is to define proper Test Cases in a TaaS framework for 5G service validation and identify the KPIs that should be stressed in these tests. A list of basic 5G technical KPIs has been defined by the TMV in [32], containing the type and the observing points within the 5G network for each of them.

Moreover, an exhaustive analysis of 5G PPP projects' use cases of various verticals has been performed in [33] mapping their service performance KPIs to corresponding 5G network KPIs. It should be noted that the definition of the VITAL-5G use case service and network level KPIs, as provided in Deliverable D1.1 [4], have been based on these works of 5G PPP and the TMV.

VITAL-5G has leveraged the testing and validation solutions designed and implemented by the three ICT-17 projects, mentioned above, and built on top of them, following the guidelines and recommendations of the TMV and the relevant standards. An overview table of the key characteristics of the validation solutions implemented in the three ICT-17 projects is provided in ETSI TR 103 761 V0.0.7 [21]. The most relevant attributes for the implementation of the VITAL-5G monitoring and testing tools, are showcased in Table 20.

Table 20: 5G PPP projects validation solutions attributes.

Attribute	5G-EVE	5G-VINNI	5GENESIS
Validation Framework	TaaS platform supporting custom experiments, configurable virtual services, network slicing, service and network KPI collection and analysis, integrated diagnostics	TaaS platform supporting customized experiments and slicing configurations.	TaaS platform supporting standard experiments (project internal) and custom experiments (project external), slicing configurations, monitoring and analytics module, KPI collection and analysis
Experiment definition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Configurable Blueprints Vertical service elements & connections Service parameters Network requirements Context conditions Service & network KPIs Evaluation criteria Test cases Configurable test scripts Custom VNF/PNF onboarding 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Purpose Description Initial Conditions Parameters Procedures & expected results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experimenter descriptor template <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Test cases Scenarios Slices 5GENESIS portal Open APIs
Experiment workflow	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Experiment preparation Experiment execution and monitoring Experiment results evaluation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment design Experiment preparation Experiment execution Experiment assessment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Experiment consultation phase Experiment provisioning phase Experiment execution <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Pre-run Run Post-run Experiment decommissioning phase Analysis of the results
Interfaces to verticals / experimenters	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web-based Portal for the design, scheduling, deployment, execution and verification of 5G experiments Intent Based interface REST APIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> GUI for composing and scheduling tests REST APIs Results can be collected and stored to external databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Web-based Portal for experiment execution and results collection Open APIs

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Results can be accessed or downloaded 		
Testing Automation Capabilities	Automated execution of the experiment test cases, which includes the collection and validation of service and network KPIs and diagnostic analysis.	Tests can be scheduled in the TaaS user interface. TaaS can also be programmatically controlled through REST APIs.	Experiment Lifecycle manager which enables automating the execution of the experiments.
KPI Collection & Validation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service & Network KPIs collection supported Visualization through graphs supported in the portal Real time collection via REST APIs KPI Downloading supported for post-processing Threshold-based KPI validation supported Performance Diagnosis supported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Measurement results available via Grafana application Measurements can be stored in external database Threshold-based KPI validation supported 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Monitoring information collected from all elements of the platform Real-time access to KPIs supported via the analytics component KPI database storage supported for post-processing Advanced analytics offered via a correlation tool

10 Annex 2 – Network Application and Vertical Service Blueprint data models – updated version

Figure 50: Network Application blueprint.

Figure 51: Vertical Service blueprint.

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